

School of Business and Creative Industries

Division of Accounting, Finance and Law

**Corporate Accountability for Disclosing Circular
Economy, Servitisation and Industry 4.0
Practices: An Insight from Global Fortune 500
Listed Companies**

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Abstract

Sustainability reporting is gaining popularity among corporations. However, businesses require a clear approach to report on the integration of Circular Economy (CE) principles with servitisation and Industry 4.0 (I4.0) technologies. These integrations can create new revenue streams and opportunities for circular value production. Concerns about greenwashing, where companies falsely claim CE practices, underscore the need for firms to embed environmentally responsible practices into their servitisation strategies. This includes ensuring transparency in material sourcing, product lifecycle management, waste reduction, and product efficacy enhancement. The study employs a triangulation of theories—Resource-Based View (RBV), Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCT), and Stakeholder Theory (ST)—to understand the circular value of resources and capabilities of manufacturers. Thus, the researcher developed a comprehensive understanding of sustainable strategies for circular product development from the business ecosystem perspective. This addresses the gap in theoretical frameworks covering environmental sustainability and social responsibility in business strategy formulation. Despite the growing recognition of CE's importance, there remains a need for a framework to assess its implementation, especially in conjunction with servitisation and I4.0 strategies. To fill this gap, the researcher has developed a self-constructed CE disclosure index, a novel approach in the field. This index aims to provide practical guidance for businesses navigating the complexities of modern economic landscapes. It empowers stakeholders to make informed, environmentally conscious decisions, thereby safeguarding the integrity of CE initiatives and advancing sustainable practices in corporate environments. The research methodology involves three key steps: establishing relationships between latent variables, developing the CE disclosure index for content analysis, and conducting Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) using Smart-PLS. The main findings indicate that implementing CE and servitisation positively impacts product longevity and encourages extended use. However, the study found an insignificant relationship between I4.0 and CE, suggesting the need for further investigation into their complex interplay. Furthermore, the study highlights that integrating I4.0 technologies can facilitate the transition to servitisation and enhance operational capabilities. A robustness analysis identified a significant indirect effect of I4.0 on CE through servitisation, underscoring the importance of considering their interplay. Overall, the results show a promising trend in companies' transparency and accountability in reporting on CE, servitisation, and I4.0 initiatives.

Managerial Implications: Managers and practitioners in various industries can use the study's analysis to understand better how CE principles align with servitisation and I4.0 technologies. The results guide reviewing collaborative and augmented partnerships, empowering decision-makers to enhance strategic planning and implementation. The study's outcomes offer practical insights that managers can directly apply, providing a basis for informed decision-making. Managers can navigate the complexities of transforming their operations by understanding the challenges and opportunities associated with adopting a circular BM with a service-oriented approach.

Practical Implications: by using the provided self-developed CE disclosure index for reporting, manufacturing companies can effectively align their decisions and activities with their CE objectives and broader mission. While organisations may be at different stages of CE implementation, they should consistently strive to foster a culture of CE and report on their perceived impact. Although, it may be crucial to integrate stakeholders' feedback and recommendations about the strategic development and execution of sustainable and circular business practices. This integration promotes better governance and the successful implementation of CE strategies.

Policy Implications: Government bodies and policymakers can use the current study's findings as a reference for shaping effective CE policies. The insights gained provide a foundation for understanding CE compliance, aiding in developing a robust policy framework that supports and advances the transition from a linear economy (LE) to a CE paradigm.

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List of Publications

The author has published journal articles and conference papers, which include:

Research Papers

1. Atif, S. (2023). "Analysing the alignment between circular economy and industry 4.0 nexus with industry 5.0 era: An integrative systematic literature review". *Sustainable Development*, 31(4), 2155-2175. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.2542>
2. Atif, S. (2023). "The role of Industry 4.0-enabled data-driven shared platform as an enabler of product-service system in the context of circular economy: a systematic literature review and future research directions". *Business Strategy & Development*, 1-21. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/bsd2.238>
3. Hassan, A., Atif, S. and Zhang, J. (2024). "Investigating the Relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility activities and Innovation Performance with the Moderating Effect of CEO Gender Diversity: Empirical Evidence from the U.S". *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 17(1), 23. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm17010023>
4. Atif, S., (2023). "Mapping circular economy principles and servitisation approach in business model canvas: an integrated literature review". *Future Business Journal*, 9(1), p.33. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-023-00211-6>
5. Atif, S., Ahmed, S., Wasim, M., Zeb, B., Pervez, Z. and Quinn, L. (2021). "Towards a Conceptual Development of Industry 4.0, Servitisation, and Circular Economy: A Systematic Literature Review". *Sustainability*, 13(11), 6501. DOI: [10.3390/su13116501](https://doi.org/10.3390/su13116501)
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2. Atif, S. and Hassan, A. (2024). "Strategic Integration of Servitisation and I4.0 as Circular Economy Strategy: A Comprehensive Disclosure Analysis". *ICBTCAMBRIDGE'2024: The International Conference on Business and Technology*. 19-20 April 2024.
3. Hassan, A., Adhikari Parajuli, M., Roberts, L. and Atif, S. (2023). "UK Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) governance and accountability towards nature positive disclosure (NPD)". *EEEAGER: Environmental, Ecological, Extinction Accounting, Governance and Economics Research Group*. 11-12 April 2024.

4. Atif, S. and Hassan, A. (2024). "Exploring the Relationship between Circular Economy, Servitisation, and Industry 4.0 Disclosure: Empirical Evidence from Global Fortune 500 Companies". *EEEAGER: Environmental, Ecological, Extinction Accounting, Governance and Economics Research Group*. 11-12 April 2024.
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6. Atif, S. and Hassan, A. (2023). ¹ "The role of Circular Economy to address Africa's Environmental, Social and Governance Challenges: A systematic literature review and bibliometric analysis". *British Academy of Management* 2023.
7. Parajuli, M.A., Hassan, A., Roberts, L. and Atif, S. (2023). "The effects of corporate governance mechanisms and vice-chancellor characteristics on nature positive activities disclosure in UK HEIs". *Creating a Sustainable World through Accounting Research, Engagement and Education*
8. Atif, S. (2022). "The application of Industry 4.0 technologies and its effect on Circular Economy, in the context of R&D: A Narrative Review". *ScotDoc2022: Scottish Doctorate Colloquium in Accounting and Finance*. 13 June 2022.
9. Atif, S. (2022). "Exploration of supply chain management challenges in the transformation process towards Servitisation: A Narrative Review". International Accounting and Auditing Conference: *Accounting for Planet, People and Profit (APPP) challenges*: Conference Proceedings. University of the Witwatersrand, p. 10-10 1 p. · Aug 4, 2022.
10. Atif, S., Ahmed, S. and Rafi-ul-Shan, P. M. (2021). "An exploration of the relationship between Circular Economy and Servitisation: A Systematic Literature Review". *LRN21: Logistics Research Network*. 2021. Cardiff University, 8-10 September.

Awards Received¹

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List of Abbreviations

CE= Circular Economy

LE= Linear Economy

BM= Business Model

LEBM= Linear Economy Business Model

CBM= Circular Business Model

CEBM= Circular Economy Business Model

SER= Servitisation

CV= Control Variables

I4.0= Industry 4.0

AI= Artificial Intelligence

CER1/R1= Refuse

CER2/R2= Rethink

CER3/R3= Reduce

CER4/R4= Reuse

CER5/R5= Repair

CER6/R6= Refurbish

CER7/R7= Remanufacture

CER8/R8= Repurpose

CER9/R9= Recycle

CER10/R10= Recover

SER11= Servitisation as a CE strategy

SER12= Waste Recovery for servitisation

SER13= Minimising usage of virgin Material

SER14= End-of Life practices/Reverse Logistics

IND15= Transparency and Accountability

IND16= I4.0-enabled shared platform

IND17= Resource Efficiency

IND18= Extended Lifecycle

IND19= Functional Efficacy

IND20= Functional Efficacy

IND21= Monitoring Resource Use

CBM22= Circular Business Model

SCM23= Supply Chain Management

CVP24= Circular Value Proposition

IED25= Investment in Eco-design
SDS26= Statement of Sustainable Development Strategy
LCA= Lifecycle Assessment
GRI= Global Reporting Initiative
RBV= Resource-Based View
DCT= Dynamic Capabilities Theory
ST= Stakeholder Theory
KMO= Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin
AVE= Average Variance Extracted
CR= Composite Reliability
HTMT= Heterotrait- Monotrait Ratio
VIF= Variance Inflation Factor
SEM= Structural Equation Modelling
PLS= Partial Structural Modelling
PLS-PM= Partial Least Squares Path Modelling
df= Degrees of freedom
IoT= Internet of Things
CPS= Cyber-Physical System
AI= Artificial Intelligence
BDA= Big Data Analytics
BMI= Business Model Innovation
PSS= Product Service System
CLSC = Closed Loop Supply Chain
SDG= Sustainable Development Goals

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1. Introduction of the Chapter

This chapter presents an overview of the study. The chapter is divided into a number of sections that establish the main framework of the studies. These sections are as follows: section (1) is the introduction section; (2) provides a brief contextual background about the topic, presenting the current status and overlapping themes among circular economy (CE), servitisation and industry 4.0 (I4.0) literature and their reporting related information; section (3) details the statement on motivation; section (1.4) presents the problem statement that motivated the researcher to select this topic; section (5-8) illustrates the research aim, objectives, questions and hypotheses that are set to evaluate the correlation between the key variables; Section (9) summarises the adopted methodology; section (10) discusses the contribution elements of the research and finally section (11) presents the structure of the thesis.

Reconceptualize growth, emphasizing broad societal advantages

1.2. Background of the Study

The *circular economy (CE)* concept aims to reconceptualise growth, emphasising broad societal advantages (Singh et al., 2021). It involves gradually decoupling economic activity from consuming limited resources and creating a waste-free system (Garza-Reyes et al., 2019; Michelini et al., 2017). The businesses must report on the impact of this transition to circularity to establish stakeholder trust, demonstrate transparency, and ensure accountability (Scarpellini, 2022). Various frameworks have been developed to measure and report on CE reporting practices as the concept gains traction (Roberts et al., 2022). However, the plethora of these indicators has led to a call for harmonisation and a clearer understanding of their purpose and use. A gap in the current state of CE-reporting practices has been identified, which either captures circularity potential: Circulytics [Valls-Val et al., 2022, 2023] and Lifecycle assessment [C. Zhang et al., 2023; Romagnoli et al., 2023] or effective circularity (GRI: waste management [Gunarathne et al., 2021; Roberts et al., 2022; Opferkuch et al., 2022]). This gap highlights the need for a comprehensive and robust framework to monitor, optimise and report the circularity performance throughout a product's life cycle. The reporting framework must provide relevant and specific information that is fair, balanced, and comprehensible to stakeholders. Additionally, by integrating servitisation with Industry 4.0 technologies, manufacturers can create a robust CE reporting system that continuously monitors and optimises the circularity performance, ensuring that products are designed, used, and disposed of to maximise their value and minimise environmental impact (Atif, 2023a). Thus, to fully realise the benefits of servitisation and

14.0 as CE strategies, recent corporate reporting developments are advised to include broader non-financial sustainability metrics alongside traditional financial metrics. The inclusion of circular design, responsible consumption and production and return of used products back to the cycle considerations within the reporting standards, such as those established by the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) and the International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB), reflects a growing recognition of the interconnectedness of circular activities and environmental health (Adhikari Parajuli et al., 2022; Opferkuch et al., 2022; Tiscini et al., 2022; Alkaraan et al., 2024). These standards help companies communicate their CE-related risks and opportunities, drive long-term profitability, and contribute to broader environmental and social goals, guiding better decision-making and fostering stakeholder trust (Maroun, 2019) and rather than being treated as a branding opportunity (Bressanelli et al., 2018b; Ghisetti & Montresor, 2019; Cardoso de Oliveira et al., 2019; Piyathanavong et al., 2022). Considering the substantial increase in the global Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) challenges, the stakeholders demand accountability and transparency from the organisations about their operations (Barón Dorado et al., 2022; Javeed et al., 2022; Scarpellini, 2022). It is envisaged that industrial organisations would generate sustainable value by facilitating ecological and economic goals, referred to as the CE principles (Davies & Doherty, 2019). CE reporting is believed to be a regenerative tool for the stakeholders that provides a holistic view of the company's environmental commitment and can prevent biodiversity loss (ecology) and minimise air and water pollution (Roberts et al., 2021; Yu, et al., 2022). Thus, sustainability reporting is increasingly adopted by global corporations as they disclose ESG-related impacts, operations, and initiatives, demonstrating their dedication towards sustainable and circular practices. Many researchers have indicated a low level of awareness among large companies about CE reporting (Dagiliene et al., 2020). For instance, Roberts et al. (2022) stress the companies to report the transformational changes toward circularity. While Opferkuch et al. (2022) suggested the CE metrics within sustainability reports appears to be surface-level and sporadic.

In addition to the above discussion, the manufacturing companies consider productivity as a driving force for economic growth. However, what they don't realize is that mass production is also a source of a massive waste of resources that leads to environmental destruction. As the shift towards circularity gains momentum, stakeholders now expect businesses to demonstrate transparency regarding their products life cycle and manufacturing companies transition towards CE. Many manufacturing businesses are therefore integrating a *servitisation* approach into their business model (BM) to position themselves for accelerated growth across the value chain (Doni et al., 2019). Moreover, the CE paradigm has been developed through specialised service design and is considered to have the ability to accelerate and expedite transformation in today's competitive market (Mishra

et al., 2018; Fernando et al., 2022; Franconi et al., 2022; Lewandowski, 2016; Ranta et al., 2021; Scheel et al., 2020). Businesses however, facing challenges on reporting of their resource use and their progression towards a CE. Although many metrics and frameworks exist, they are designed to perform different functions and use complex indicators, making it difficult for businesses to report their CE transformation consistently. This inconsistency makes it harder for investors to identify the most successful circular opportunities and direct their investments accordingly. As a result, recent studies suggest that adding a robust reporting practise by manufacturing businesses will assist them to manage their CE strategies and will also help them to minimise the production of the single-use product and reducing waste in the product design (Doni et al., 2019). Realizing the importance of stakeholders growing interest in this process and the transparency required, Singh et al. (2021) suggested that stakeholders should be included in the materiality analysis to enhance a firm's ESG impact.

The CE paradigm is focused on creating a closed-loop system, while servitisation shifts the focus from selling products to selling services. Thus, **combining servitisation with CE** extends the product's lifecycle and reduces waste. Hence, it is not wrong to say that the combination of both concepts creates more robust CE. It keeps a product in use for a longer period based on its reliance on the systematic application of strategies that generates revenues by utilising an undervalued waste torrent (Di Vaio et al., 2022; Kama, 2015; Rehman et al., 2016). Currently, the market for products that are circular in use, highly functional and effective has increased due to technological advancements that utilise resources cautiously (Cano et al., 2022; Kama, 2015). Previous industrial revolutions have rapidly degraded environmental and ecological resources (Frank, Dalenogare, et al., 2019; Kovács, 2022). Therefore, academics, practitioners and businesses are exerting a proactive emphasis on embracing the technologically advanced CE paradigm as an integrated system replacing the traditional Linear Economy (LE) and report their findings in their sustainability reports (Dev, Shankar, & Qaiser, 2020a; Velte et al., 2020; Zara & Ramkumar, 2022). Traditional LE relied on the take-make-dispose consumption pattern, which created supply and price instability challenges because of the growing scarcity of resources (Lewandowski, 2016; Garza-Reyes et al., 2019; Atif et al., 2021; Fernando et al., 2022; Yu, et al., 2022).

Another widely spread belief among academics is that the fourth industrial revolution has created an exceptional, digitally machine intelligence that comes under servitisation will subsequently optimise a business's performance and productivity and potentially substitute excessive human labour (Schroeder et al., 2019; Kohtamäki et al., 2020). Industries constantly striving to enhance productivity, but recently, their primary focus has been on providing products instead of services enabled by technology (Bressanelli et al., 2018b). **Industry 4.0 (I4.0)** is the basis for uninterruptedly redefining a

businesses' operations which can improve performance by adopting sustainable models and reconfiguring their products consortium, processes, services provisions, and stratagems (Rymaszewska et al., 2017; Kohtamäki et al., 2019; Majeed et al., 2021; Birkel & Müller, 2021; Atif, 2023a). I4.0 refers to the fourth industrial revolution, which entails integrating various cutting-edge technologies to create value and facilitate the development of smart manufacturing factories. These fact-decentralised led to establishing intelligent, distributed and digital value networks (Bressanelli et al., 2018b). Zheng et al. (2022) provided an insight about advancement in digital technologies and recommended to conduct a study on digital disclosures/reporting.

Basically, servitisation is a process that drives economic advancement as technology brings about transformation. However, an effective CE reporting system is required to highlight how the CE constructs can play a pivotal role in creating employment opportunities and opening new markets, fostering broader societal benefits, and promoting sustainable integration of goods and services throughout their life cycle (Kühl et al., 2020; Lightfoot et al., 2013; Tukker, 2015). Yang et al. (2019) highlighted the need for a comprehensive CE reporting system in the manufacturing companies to include data about their business CE transformation including information about the product's circular design, reverse logistics, green procurement, responsible production, and consumption themes Integrating. A robust reporting system will also help in reduce manufacturing time and efforts and will create innovative sources of revenues and opportunities for value generation for the manufacturing companies (Kiel et al., 2017). Instead of a one-time sale, servitisation offers "outcome as a service" (Santamaría et al., 2012). Consequently, the require an intelligent product consortium with enhanced functionality and value-added services is increasing in today's competitive world. This innovative change is driving companies to embracing digitalisation through the adoption of technology-enhances smart services paired with circular products (Weking et al., 2020). It is not wrong to state that an efficient reporting system on i4.0 is crucial to boost and preserve company's competitiveness, enhance the value of industrial processes, improve their sustainability image significantly. Therefore, it is within businesses interests to facilitate, augment and report the technical advancement within the BM. To obtain a competitive market advantage, the reporting of the *CE transformation, servitisation, and I4.0 technologies* should be included in the company's sustainability This reporting will also help in improving functionality in the production of a circular product and facilitate reverse logistics. (Bressanelli et al., 2018b).

1.3. Motivation of the Study

The integration of CE, servitisation, and I4.0 technologies presents a promising avenue for enhancing business sustainability and competitiveness. However, despite the evident potential, there remains a

notable gap in prior research concerning the interconnection of these three concepts and their disclosure practices (Adhikari parajuli et al., 2021; Hassan et al., 2021, 2022; Hassan, et al., 2022). The current study seeks to address this gap by investigating the synergies and insinuations of integrating CE, servitisation, and I4.0 technologies, shedding light on their disclosure practices and their effect on business's sustainability and competitiveness. Despite the growing recognition of the importance of CE, there remains a need for a proper framework to assess its reporting, particularly in conjunction with servitisation and I4.0 strategies. To fill this void, the researcher has developed a self-constructed CE disclosure index, a novel approach not yet to be explored in previous studies. The current study strives to contribute constructive insights to the academic literature and provide practical guidance for businesses navigating the complexities of modern CE economic landscapes.

1.4. Problem Statement

Sustainability reporting is becoming increasingly popular for corporations (Adhikari Parajuli et al., 2022; Opferkuch et al., 2022; Tiscini et al., 2022; Alkaraan et al., 2024). However, businesses need a clear approach to report on CE (Dagiliene et al., 2020; Barnabè & Nazir, 2021) integration of services with product consortiums with the help of I4.0 technologies, which can generate new revenue streams and circular value-producing opportunities (Atif, 2023b). Many metrics and frameworks exist, but they can be overwhelming for businesses due to their complexity, which deals with holistic CE assurance (Hassan et al., 2022). Unfortunately, there is a growing concern regarding greenwashing, where companies falsely profess CE practices, misleading stakeholders and undermining genuine sustainability efforts (Opferkuch et al., 2023; Thimm & Rasmussen, 2023; Walker et al., 2021, 2022). Firms must embed CE and environmental responsibility practices into their sustainability reports to address this challenge, ensuring transparency in material sourcing, product lifecycle management, waste reduction, and product efficacy enhancement. Likewise, stakeholders must scrutinize companies' claims and seek evidence of their commitment to CE. Recognising the need for effective tools to discern genuine CE practices from greenwashing claims, the current study aims to develop a CE disclosure index. This index will empower stakeholders to make informed and environmentally conscious decisions, thereby safeguarding the integrity of CE initiatives and advancing sustainable practices in the corporate landscape.

1.5. Research Aim

The aim of the current study is to assess the adoption and reporting of CE disclosures in the manufacturing sector by examining the utilisation level of servitisation and I4.0 as integral components of CE strategy in disclosure activities within their sustainability reports.

1.6. Research Objectives

To achieve above mentioned research aim, three research objectives have been formulated that are:

- **Research Objective 1 (RO1):** To explore and explain the interconnectedness of CE, servitisation, and I4.0 by analysing the adoption of I4.0 technologies and implementation of servitisation as a CE strategy.
- **Research Objective 2 (RO2):** To investigate the frequency and depth of CE, servitisation and I4.0's reporting practices by Global Fortune 500 listed companies.
- **Research Objective 3 (RO3):** To investigate the extent of CE reporting practices related to using servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategy by Global Fortune 500 listed companies.
- **Research Objective 4 (RO4):** To explore the implications of CE reporting practices, specifically examining the use and impact of servitisation and I4.0 as integral components of CE strategy in disclosure activities.

1.7. Research Question

To achieve above mentioned aim and objectives, three research questions have been formulated to provide insight about the latent variables of this thesis that are:

- **Research Question 1 (RQ1):** How can the synergy between servitisation and I4.0 technologies be leveraged as a CE strategy by the manufacturing industry?
- **Research Question 2 (RQ2):** What is the frequency and extent of CE, servitisation, and I4.0 reporting practices in the sustainability reports of Global Fortune 500 companies?
- **Research Question 3 (RQ3):** To what extent do Global Fortune 500 companies report on the integration of servitisation and I4.0 as part of their CE strategies?
- **Research Question 4 (RQ4):** What are the implications of incorporating servitisation and I4.0 into CE reporting practices, and how do these integrations impact the transparency, accountability, and overall sustainability performance of Global Fortune 500 companies?

The researcher has prepared Figure 1.1 demonstrating the structure of research design, which is as follow:

Figure 1.1: Structure of the Research Design

1.8. Research Hypotheses

A thorough literature review addresses the first research question (RQ1), establishing the interconnectedness and interrelationship between the latent variables (CE, servitisation, and I4.0). Subsequently, RQ2 and RQ3 were explored through descriptive analysis, which examined the extent, frequency, and depth of the reporting practices of CE, servitisation, and I4.0 in sustainability reports. Finally, the research hypotheses (H1-H4) were developed to seek answers for RQ4, which evaluated the impact of integrating servitisation, and I4.0 as a CE strategy by analysing companies' disclosure practices. The hypotheses are as follows:

- H1: The adoption of servitisation positively effects the level of CE disclosures.
- H2: The adoption of I4.0 positively effects the level of CE disclosures.
- H3: The adoption of I4.0 technologies positively effects the level of servitisation in the disclosure practices, and vice versa.
- H4: The combined adoption of servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies effects the level of CE reporting practices.

1.9. Research Methodology

The researcher has adopted following three steps to conduct the study:

1.9.1. First Step: Establishing Relationship between Latent Variables

The researcher has presented a thorough literature review about the latent variables (CE, servitisation, I4.0 and CV) and established the affiliation among them. This section aims to contribute to the need for more CE-related literature that evaluates servitisation and I4.0 as an enabler towards circularity which is the first objective (RO1: To explore and explain the interconnectedness of CE, servitisation, and I4.0 by analysing the adoption of I4.0 technologies and implementation of servitisation as a CE strategy.) of the current study. Thus, this research has analysed the use of I4.0-enabled shared platforms leveraging the servitisation approach to generalise the innovative value propositions associated with the transition. The research also identified the interconnection between the latent variables (CE, servitisation, I4.0 and CV) to understand the implication of CE transformation strategies adopted by the selected firms.

1.9.2. Second Step: Development of CE Disclosure Index and Content Analysis

The second step in analysing the transition towards circularity through the lenses of servitisation and I4.0 involves creating a self-constructed disclosure index. Prior studies have overlooked the development of a CE-disclosure index to evaluate whether companies are leveraging servitisation and I4.0 as strategies within their CE initiatives. Thus, the current study aims to fill this void by creating a CE-disclosure index based on previous studies and utilises multiple components of each key variable, including the CE, servitisation, and I4.0. The disclosure index includes various elements that help to understand the paradigm shift in a firm's operational and financial performance. The content analysis was performed manually on secondary sources like company websites and annual/sustainability reports of 100 manufacturing companies listed on the Global Fortune 500 list for a five-years (2018-2022) period. The sample comprised five hundred observations in total. This step is crucial for the current study as it provides the researcher with a comprehensive path to evaluate the research objectives, especially RO2: To investigate the frequency and depth of CE, servitisation and I4.0's reporting practices by Global Fortune 500 listed companies, and Research Objective 3 (RO3): To investigate the extent of CE reporting practices related to using servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategy by Global Fortune 500 listed companies.

1.9.3. Third Step: Measurement and Statistical Analysis

The researcher has conducted a statistical analysis using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) to test hypotheses, developed to achieve RO4: *To explore the implications of CE reporting practices, specifically examining the use and impact of servitisation and I4.0 as integral components of CE strategy in disclosure activities.* Before conducting the statistical analysis, it is crucial to specify the measurement model as it affects the validity and reliability of the research outcomes. The researcher designed the measurement procedures carefully to ensure accuracy and impartiality. Four latent variables were used in the CE-disclosure index², including CE as a dependent variable (with ten indicators), servitisation (four indicators), and I4.0 (seven indicators) as independent variables, and control variables (five indicators) to evaluate the relationship among them through the structural model. In the later chapter (Chapter 5: Findings and Discussion), the researcher discussed the measurement model in detail, including a thorough discussion of the outcomes derived from assessing the reliability and validity of the measurement model, collinearity test, and normality test.

1.10. Contribution of the Research

This research will help in filling the gaps identified by previous scholars regarding the reporting of CE strategies, servitisation approach and I4.0 technologies by the businesses. An extensive discussion of the gaps in the existing literature is provided and discussed in detail in Chapter 2 (section 2.11) which motivates the researcher to gain insight knowledge about the key variables and their reporting practices by the companies.

1.10.1. Environmental Domain

The CE paradigm has received remarkable attention from practitioners and academics during the last decade. Hence, the present research builds upon prior suggestions regarding the principles of the CE (Sihvonen & Partanen, 2017; Yang et al., 2019; Scarpellini et al., 2019; Dagiliene et al., 2020; D'Amato et al., 2019; Roberts, Georgiou, et al., 2022; Scarpellini, 2022). The majority of previous studies have concentrated on implementing the principles of the CE (Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020; D'Amato et al., 2019; Gunarathne et al., 2021). However, a few studies focused on the reporting of specific CE practices like eco-design (Sihvonen & Partanen, 2017); supply chain practices (Doni et al., 2019; M. P. Singh et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2019); management practices (Dagiliene et al., 2020; Gunarathne et al., 2021). Additionally, few studies have utilised the 4R-strategy of CE (Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020; Dagiliene et al., 2020) This study is among the few that utilised the 10R strategy to assess the extent of CE disclosure that provides a holistic approach to how companies are adopting and reporting 10R-

² Self-developed CE-disclosure index is available in Chapter 2

strategy at different stages of business. The current research has divided the 10R-strategy into three stages, i.e., the circular design stage that includes R1: refuse, R2: rethink and R3: reduce; the second stage is the responsible consumption and production phase that includes R4: reuse, R5: repair, R6: refurbish, R7: remanufacture and R8: repurpose; Lastly the third phase is called connected platform approach which includes R9: recycle and R10: recover (Bag, Gupta, and Kumar, 2021).

1.10.2. Social Domain

This research adds to the body of literature on CE by classifying servitisation and I4.0 as its enablers and evaluating their influence on CE disclosure in selected listed companies. According to Walker et al. (2021), CE networks have been exemplary in many aspects, but several companies have overlooked the reporting of the social dimension. Addressing this gap, the research highlights the importance of incorporating social assessment into CE reporting practices. Through the involvement of stakeholders in the assessment process and promoting transparency, companies can ensure the legitimacy of their social assessments (Sharma et al., 2023). Additionally, the study emphasises the positive impact of reporting social aspects on profitability and their contribution to sustainability. Therefore, the research outcomes foster companies to invest in reporting the social assessment to enhance their sustainability efforts and profitability, aiding in the creation of a more sustainable and socially responsible business ecosystem.

1.10.3. Governance Domain

Maroun (2019) emphasised the pressing need for a contemporary understanding and measurement of assurance within corporate reporting. This sentiment is also echoed by Walker et al. (2022), who suggests developing impact assessment approaches to support CE strategies. Despite companies' efforts to enhance reporting quality through various systems and processes, the definition and measurement of assurance still need to be improved (Moroun, 2022). This highlights the importance of investigating how reporting practices can be effectively defined, measured, and implemented within corporate reporting frameworks (Borgato & Marchini, 2021; A. Hassan et al., 2020; Quick & Inwinkl, 2020). Thus, the findings of this study hold significance for government, society, and academia, particularly in contemplating the transition from a linear economy (LE) to a CE. Legislative bodies and policymakers benefit from leveraging this research to gain insights into CE-compliance policies, facilitating the development of effective policy frameworks to support and advance the CE paradigm among stakeholders.

1.10.4. Contribution to Policy Development

Although, the affiliation between CE and servitisation and between CE and I4.0 has been well developed. There is still a need to bridge the gap regarding the characteristic of a synergic consolidative assessment of the CE principles with the Servitisation approach and I4.0. There is not a single disclosure-based study that has evaluated this trio-combination using a disclosure index. Therefore, a self-developed CE disclosure index has been developed to explore the extent of the servitisation approach being used as a CE strategy to return the used product into the production cycle leveraging the I4.0-enabled collaborative platform and emphasising the significance of material visibility from stakeholders' engagement perspective. Moreover, the current study will take a broader approach to explore the 10R- strategy of CE by advancing the understanding of the essence of shared platform perspective using servitisation and I4.0 lenses to understand about the managerial commitments within a firm that plays a vital role to unlock the maximum potential across ESG dimensions. A self-constructed disclosure index is developed based on academic literature used to measure the disclosure of CE principles and indicators for servitisation approach when used as CE strategy with the help of I4.0-enabled shared platforms conducting a content analysis from company websites and their sustainability and annual reports. Most of the CE-related index was primarily based upon 306-waste related GRI-2021 framework published in October 2021. Following index has been previously employed by Gunarathne et al. (2021); Roberts et al. (2022); Opferkuch et al. (2022). This study extended the CE-index and used 10R strategy of CE dividing them into three phases according to product's lifecycle: 1- circular design: This stage focuses on minimising of inputs and outputs of waste at design stage; 2-responsible production & consumption: This stage discussed about maintenance of resource value within the system for as long as possible; 3-return of used product and bring it back to production cycle: finally, this stage focus on reintegration of used/discarded products into the system by closing the supply chain loop. A few studies have employed some of 10R strategies of CE principles like R1: refuse; R2: rethink; R3: reduce; R4: reuse; R5: repair; R6: Refurbish; R7: Remanufacture; R8: Repurpose; R9 recycle and finally R10: recover suggested by (Gunarathne et al., 2021; Roberts et al., 2022; Opferkuch et al., 2022; Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020). However, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, there is no index previously constructed that cover all 10Rs of CE strategies.

1.10.5. Managerial Contributions

The current study may guide executives and practitioners to comprehend the orientation of the CE, servitisation and I4.0 technologies. The study results can aid managers in decision-making by reviewing collaborative and augmented partnerships. Opferkuch et al. (2023), proposed a study to explore the

impact of increased CE implementation on managerial processes by linking sustainability trade-off research with due diligence processes. The study conducted a content analysis of company's sustainability reports to determine the extent to which the circularity paradigm is adopted. The analysis also identified the challenges manufacturers face in transitioning their BM to a service-based one while providing circular products to their customers.

1.10.6. Industrial Contributions

Addressing notable research gaps, the current study is poised to significantly contribute to CE and industrial practices. Firstly, prior research, as identified by Puglieri et al. (2022), has highlighted the burgeoning potential for CE development in the forthcoming years, emphasising the imperative for companies to adopt diverse strategies to remain competitive in their respective markets. Furthermore, as highlighted by Tiscini et al. (2022), there is a pressing need exists for a more holistic and integrated approach to sustainability reporting. Additionally, Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, (2020) have emphasised the criticality of bridging the gap between CE theory and practice, emphasising organisations' need to collaborate effectively with stakeholders to actualise CE and sustainability goals. Considering these research gaps, the current study aims to delve into the intricacies of CE phenomena, examining the resources and operations pivotal to servitisation and elucidating how I4.0 technologies catalyse this transformation, bolstering firm performance. Moreover, by exploring the performance dynamics of service systems within the CE framework, the study seeks to identify novel dimensions of servitisation performance, offering empirical evidence and strategic recommendations to enhance economic and environmental performance. Additionally, the study envisions the formulation of new policies and guidelines to bolster industries' economic, environmental, and human capital competencies, thereby paving the way for the industrial revolution of the future. By filling the identified research gaps and offering actionable insights, the study aspires to advance CE theory and practice, ultimately fostering sustainability and innovation across industrial domains.

1.11. Structure of Thesis

The structure of the analysis presented in this research is as follow:

Chapter 1: Introduction: The following section provides brief background information about the key variables (CE, servitisation, and I4.0 technologies) used in the current study. Following that is a problem statement highlighting the misstatement of CE-related reporting practices and the absence of disclosing of using I4.0 technologies and servitisation as the CE strategy in a specific reporting framework. Moreover, the research aims, objectives, and questions were designed to analyse the

answers to the problem statement. A summary of the adopted methodology and research contribution is also provided in this section, and finally, the structure of this thesis is presented.

Chapter 2: Literature Review: Chapter 2 includes a thorough Literature Review that explores the relationship between the current study's key variables (CE, servitisation, and I4.0). It explains the evolution and integration of CE into sustainability reports. The section begins with a literature review on the shift towards CE, emphasising the role of servitisation and I4.0 in facilitating CE, which is relevant to RQ2. The latter part of this chapter provides insights into how CE-related reporting practices are integrated into sustainability reporting and discusses the integration of servitisation and I4.0 into CE reporting practices. This comprehensive literature review leads the researcher to develop a self-developed CE disclosure index.

Chapter 3: Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses Development: In this section, three essential theories are introduced: the Resource-Based View (RBV), Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCT), and Stakeholder Theory (ST), which form the theoretical framework of the current study. These theories explain how organisations can develop comprehensive sustainability strategies to meet ESG goals. RBV is used to clarify the reporting practices related to the circular design phase of the 10R strategy of CE, aiming to understand how firms report on gaining competitive advantages. DCT is utilised to assess the reporting practices of the sample companies that disclose adapting their dynamic capabilities in creating circular products and processes. Lastly, ST emphasises the importance of addressing stakeholders' concerns and needs by incorporating transparency and accountability in reporting responsible returns of used products. Later, based on this theoretical framework, the researcher formulated four hypotheses (H1-H4) to test these theories.

Chapter 4: Methodology: This section thoroughly discusses the reasons behind selection of a specific methodology and the justification. The researcher has provided a rationale for selecting a positivist research philosophy, a deductive research approach, a quantitative method using a case study strategy, and the time horizon of the current study. Additionally, a detailed discussion about the development of the CE disclosure index was included to illustrate the surety of impartial and reliable results that future researchers can easily replicate. Therefore, this section explains the steps to conduct content analysis, including sample selection, population distribution, data collection techniques, and pilot study specifications.

Chapter 5: Findings and Discussion: This chapter presents the results of the measurement and statistical analyses and discusses the findings from the current study. The chapter addresses RQ2-RQ4 and their objectives. **(RQ2)** focuses on the extent and frequencies of reporting practices of CE, servitisation, I4.0, and CV. **(RQ3)** examines the descriptive analysis of these reporting practices. **(RQ4)** involves hypothesis testing (H1-H4) to investigate the impact of combining CE, servitisation, and I4.0

on companies' reporting practices, particularly regarding the effects and transition practices related to this trio-combination. This chapter concludes with a concise summary of the statistical findings and a thorough discussion of the research outcomes.

Chapter 6- Conclusion: This chapter summarises the findings of the research, followed by implications of the research, conclusion and research recommendations for future researchers and finally the limitations that researcher faced in the process.

1.12. Chapter Summary

This chapter presents the research background and focuses on integrating CE, servitisation, and I4.0 technologies and how they can enhance business sustainability and competitiveness. However, prior research has left a gap in understanding the relationship between these concepts and their disclosure practices. Thus, this chapter presents the aim of the study, which is to bridge the gap by investigating the synergies and implications of integrating CE, servitisation, and I4.0 technologies and their impact of reporting these on business sustainability and competitiveness. The study strives to contribute valuable insights to academic literature and offer practical guidance for businesses navigating modern economic landscapes. The researcher presented the motivation for clearer sustainability reporting integrating CE with servitisation and I4.0 technologies. This complexity often overwhelms firms, leading to a need for effective tools to discern genuine CE practices from greenwashing claims. Firms must embed a robust reporting practise about their environmental responsibilities and servitisation strategies to address this challenge. This will ensure a transparency in their material sourcing, waste reduction, and product lifecycle management to all the stakeholders. Recognising the need for such tools, the study aims to develop a CE disclosure index that empowers stakeholders to make informed and environmentally conscious decisions. To achieve this aim, the study has formulated four research objectives (RO1-RO4), addressing the integration and execution of I4.0 technologies and servitisation, the extent of disclosure practices by Global Fortune 500 listed companies, and the impact of combining CE, servitisation, and I4.0. Corresponding research questions (RQ1-RQ4) and hypotheses (H1-H4) have been devised to provide insight into latent variables and evaluate the effect of this combination. The study's methodology encompasses three steps detailing the approach taken to conduct the research.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1. Introduction of the Chapter

Chapter 2 presents a comprehensive literature review, setting the theoretical and empirical foundation for the main variables (CE, servitisation and I4.0) and their reporting practices. The roadmap for the first part of this chapter is as follows: section (2) will provide a broad overview of the existing literature, summarises the main areas to focus and highlights the relevance of each section to the overall research; section (3) discusses the transition from traditional LEBM to CEBM; section (4) provides an in-depth examination of the CE paradigm, including its principles and practices; section (5) explores how servitisation acts as a strategy for implementing CE principles; section (6) analyses how I4.0 technologies support CE strategies; section (7) provides a discussion on the interconnections among CE, servitisation, and I4.0 and section (8) details an exploration of specific features of CE (which are used as CV in current study). The second part of this chapter is as follows: section (9) provides an overview of how CE is integrated into sustainability reporting, examining the existing frameworks and their limitations; section (10) details a discussion on incorporating servitisation and I4.0 into CE reporting practices; section (11) provides a review of previous empirical studies related to CE, servitisation, and I4.0 reporting, highlights the key findings and insights; section (12) provides a discussion on identification of gaps in the existing literature and finally section (13) provides the self-developed CE disclosure index, including its components and relevance.

2.2. Overview of Literature Review

In the current study the key variables (CE, servitisation, and I4.0) are multidisciplinary concepts. Therefore, it is crucial to establish a solid theoretical framework to explore their interrelationships before examining the significance of CE reporting practices and integrating servitisation and I4.0 within sustainability reporting frameworks.

Figure 2. 1: Trajectory of Chapter 2: Literature Review

Figure 2.1 presents a flow chart of Chapter 2: Literature Review, explaining the progression and facilitation of CE in business framework and the integration of the CE-related reporting practices into company’s sustainability reports. The left-hand side (left handle) of the flowchart presents the roadmap for exploring the evolution from LEBM to CEBM and the role of servitisation and I4.0 in facilitating CE, which will help the researcher achieve answers for RQ1. This research question delves into the potential of using servitisation and I4.0 technologies to implement CE principles in smart manufacturing. Before examining reporting practices, it was essential to establish the connection between CE, service, and I4.0, considering their diverse and multidisciplinary nature and identifying how their synergy can steer the shift towards a more circular and sustainable manufacturing industry, leading to decreased environmental impact and improved economic performance. Additionally, the specific features of CE have been explored in detail, as they are used as control variables in the current study. Businesses must change several key areas to incorporate CE principles when they opt for CE implementation fully. For example, CEBM, which involves redesigning traditional business models to prioritise sustainability and resource efficiency; the Value Domain, which focuses on creating value

through circular practices; SCM, which requires rethinking supply chains to enhance circularity; Circular Investment Prospects, which involves identifying and investing in opportunities that support circular practices; and the Sustainable Development Strategy Statement, which outlines a company's long-term commitment to sustainable development and CE principles.

The right-side (right handle) of the flowchart represents the second section of Chapter 2: Literature Review. This section provides an overview of how CE is integrated into sustainability reporting, including examining existing frameworks and their limitations. The researcher then discusses the incorporation of servitisation and I4.0 into CE reporting practices. Additionally, a research matrix is presented, highlighting the key findings and insights of previous empirical studies used as a basis for the current study. This matrix also assisted to identify gaps in the existing literature and setting the research aim, objectives, and questions accordingly. The literature review helped the researcher to identify common themes from the existing literature, which were then used to construct a self-developed CE disclosure index, including servitisation and I4.0 constructs for the current study.

2.3. From Linear business model to CEBM

Historically, businesses have operated under a Linear Business Model (LBM) called the "take-make-use-dispose of" model to create economic value (Michelini et al., 2017). This supply chain pipeline model consisted of distinct manufacturing processes that consumed raw materials and disposed of waste upon the completion of manufacturing (Garza-Reyes et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2019). However, this model is no longer sustainable in today's business environment, where companies are under increasing pressure to operate sustainably and minimize their environmental impact (Atif et al., 2021). As a result, businesses are now exploring CBMs that prioritize the reduction, reuse, and recycling of resources to create economic value (Opferkuch et al., 2023). By adopting a CBM, companies can reduce waste and inefficiencies, save money on raw materials, and create new revenue streams from reusing materials (Scarpellini, 2022). In addition, circular models promote a more sustainable and responsible approach to business that aligns with the values of modern consumers and stakeholders (EMF, 2015; Puglieri et al., 2022).

2.4. Circular Economy (CE)

Despite the evolution of the LBM, the industrial economy has remained rooted in its original characteristics established during the early days of industrialism (Mendoza et al., 2022). Under the LBM, companies harvest, extract, manufacture, and sell products, discarding them once they are no longer used (Garza-Reyes et al., 2019; Ghisetti & Montresor, 2019). This model heavily relies on the abundant availability of resources, necessitating a fundamental shift in its operations (Lewandowski,

2016; Scheel et al., 2020). Economic uncertainty and the adverse effects of the traditional LE, characterized by the take-make-dispose approach, have highlighted the need to transition to a more innovative and sustainable BM (Atif, 2023a; Frank, Mendes, et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2021). Thus, CE is designed to contribute to the growing need for sustainable BM. CE emerged in the 1990s as a collection of holistic perspectives to attain a society that is sustainable and free of waste (Atif et al., 2021; Turner, 1990). Given the global economic uncertainties, there has been increasing attention on the CE paradigm to mitigate the adverse impacts of the traditional LEBM (take-make-dispose). Consequently, businesses are increasingly adopting CBMs, aligning their value propositions that offer sustainable economic advantages and promote environmental well-being (Ünal et al., 2019; Lüdeke-Freund et al., 2019a; Dragomir & Dumitru, 2022).

Figure 2. 2: Transition from Linear Economy to Circular Economy

Source: (Atif, 2023a)

Figure 2.2 illustrates the functioning of two contrasting BMs: the LBM and the CBM. The LBM depicts a linear approach where products are manufactured from extracted resources and ultimately disposed of after a single use, contributing to environmental degradation. In contrast, the CBM emphasises decoupling revenues from product disposal through the implementation of reverse logistics, thereby recovering and maximising the value of products (Garza-Reyes et al., 2019; Atif, 2023a). This involves closing the loop in the supply network to curtail waste and promote sustainability (Jum'a et al., 2022). Inspired by non-linear systems, particularly biological ones, the CE notion posits the simultaneous pursuit of commercial perks and ecological returns which can generate work prospects within

industries (Horbach & Rammer, 2019). By aligning economic goals with sustainable practices, businesses can contribute directly to job creation by providing related services (Horbach & Rammer, 2019; Obeidat et al., 2023). The CE represents a novel paradigm from various philosophical perspectives, including Cradle-to-Cradle (Linder et al., 2017), Green Economy (Zahraee et al., 2018; D'Amato et al., 2019; Hariadi et al., 2023; S. A. R. Khan et al., 2022), Biomimicry and biodiversity (Roberts et al., 2021; Roberts, Georgiou, et al., 2022), Environmental Sustainability (Bogdan et al., 2022; Javeed et al., 2022; Zheng et al., 2022), and Industrial Ecology (Roberts, Nandy, et al., 2022; Scavarda et al., 2020; Stock et al., 2018). This interdisciplinary approach has garnered substantial traction among practitioners and policymakers because it does not only meet their sustainability and environmental goals, but it is also a viable business concept. This approach involves extending the life of products, recovering resources, adopting reverse logistics, and implementing closed-loop supply chains (CLSC) and shared platforms for reverse logistics through intermediaries. These characteristics provide opportunities for businesses to improve their models. Additionally, firms can adopt a hybrid approach by incorporating these features to suit their needs and contexts (Atif, 2023a; Atif et al., 2021). The CE paradigm revolves around designing out waste, promoting responsible production and consumption, and facilitating the return of used products to reintegrate them into the cycle.

2.4.1. Designing out Waste

There are two critical dimensions of the CE that warrant consideration. Firstly, the green economy (D'Amato et al., 2019; Shrivastava & Tamvada, 2019; Zhao et al., 2021), biodiversity (Roberts et al., 2021; Roberts, Georgiou, et al., 2022), and biomimicry (Scavarda et al., 2020; Stock et al., 2018; Xing et al., 2022) paradigm highlight the efficient utilisation of material flows, prioritising the use of consumable products made with the least toxic biological components (Alkaraan et al., 2024). It is broadly acknowledged that the green economy serves as a foundational element for CE (D'Amato et al., 2019, 2020). Secondly, from a technical perspective, CE encompasses operations that involve recycling, refurbishing, resale, or related services. These operations aim to design circular products that use minimal resources and provide superior efficacy through shared platforms (Aggarwal & Saxena, 2022; Al-Shaer et al., 2022; Atif, 2023b). Consequently, the CE paradigm has emerged as a pivotal concept among experts and legislators, addressing the negative impacts that human actions have on the natural world. These impacts include the dwindling of natural resource abundance, the loss of biodiversity, and the negative effects on human societies' well-being and quality of life (Al Mahameed et al., 2020; Bui & Tseng, 2021; Tykkyläinen, 2019). It facilitates the creation of innovative revenue streams, enhances competitive advantage, and enables financial savings through practical initiatives (Alvarez-Aros & Bernal-Torres, 2021; Martín et al., 2021).

The Ellen MacArthur Foundation advocates for the introduction of new designs and advanced procedures focusing on reusing discarded products instead of bringing virgin resources into the loop repeatedly (EMF, 2015). For instance, Daou et al. (2020) and De Pádua Pieroni et al. (2018) discuss the principles of the 3Rs – reusing used products, rethinking BMs, and plummeting the usage of pristine materials to enhance competence. Referring to Chiappetta Jabbour et al. (2020), these 3R imperatives are tangible means for influencing substantial usage in the CE, contributing to the commercial value of businesses after adopting CBMs. Additionally, D’Amato et al. (2019) suggest CE as a resilient strategy, exemplified through case studies within the fashion sector to demonstrate sustainability. Anastasiades et al. (2020) associate reusing with outsourcing, while the addition of "recover" to the 3R framework expands it to the 4R concept, and subsequent additions of "redesign" and "remanufacture" further evolve it into the 6R and eventually the 9R framework (Moktadir et al., 2019; Okorie et al., 2018). Additionally, Micheline et al. (2017) suggest the Ellen MacArthur Foundation's design principles as part of the 9R strategy to minimise waste and adverse ecological impacts. Although the 9R strategy is not commonly discussed in the literature, Nazir & Doni (2024) recent study on integrated reporting using multiple case studies has brought it to attention. Furthermore, Ibáñez-Forés et al. (2022) propose CE principles are an evolving concept that promotes sustainability through remanufacturing and repurposing redundant products for enhanced functionality. Bag et al. (2021) emphasise that the CE encourages innovative practices for organisations to generate value for both customers and the organisations themselves. The principle of 10R outlines various conducts for value creation, such as reusing used products, rethinking BMs, minimising the virgin resource consumption, outsourcing, repair, refurbishment, remanufacturing, repurposing, and recycling (Lopes de Sousa Jabbour et al., 2020; Bag et al., 2021).

2.4.2. Responsible Production and Consumption

The CE paradigm has garnered widespread attention to foster more resilient economic prosperity Rossi et al. (2020). CE is conceptualised as an industrial economy striving for restoration, relying on alternative energy sources, minimising, or eliminating the utilisation of harmful chemicals and reducing waste through thoughtful design processes (Bressanelli et al., 2019a; Nag et al., 2022; Nandi et al., 2021). This paradigm transcends traditional notions of consumption and production, particularly in areas requiring redefinition, such as the reconstruction of natural and social capital and the shift from clienteles to handlers (Bag & Rahman, 2023; Gupta et al., 2021; Li et al., 2024). Thus, to promote new socioeconomic consumption patterns aimed at reducing overconsumption, businesses must embrace circular supply practices and minimise waste through the adoption of the CE BM (CEBM) (Kohtamäki et al., 2022; Puglieri et al., 2022; Rossi et al., 2020; Scarpellini, 2022). CE represents a

fundamental shift in manufacturers' approach to production and consumption, aimed at curbing resource depletion and improving resource and energy efficiency to promote sustainable development at micro (businesses and consumers), meso (economic entities fostering symbiotic connections), and macro (cities, regions, governments) levels (Neligan et al., 2022; Schröder et al., 2020). Consequently, various CE approaches advocate for resource and energy conservation through innovative product designs, emphasizing the reuse of discarded products instead of continuously introducing new resources into the cycle (EMF, 2015). In the evolution of SCM, organisations' competitiveness and effectiveness have become paramount (Chari et al., 2022). In contrast to the LE where products often end up in landfills after one use, Closed-Loop Circular Systems (CLCS) play a crucial role in realizing CE and sustainability goals (Garza-Reyes et al., 2019; Michelini et al., 2017).

2.4.3. Return of Used Product and Bringing it Back to Production Cycle

It is commonly believed that the CE paradigm represents a harmonious integration of environmental resilience, achieved through resource and energy recirculation, retrieval of valuable materials from discarded constructs, and minimal resource convention, all while delivering social and economic benefits (Opferkuch et al., 2023; Tseng et al., 2020). CE endeavors to extend the lifecycle of products via refurbishment and renewal, employing competent design and enhancing process quality through servicing, mending, recycling, and reassembling (Gonella et al., 2023; Howard et al., 2019; Morseletto, 2020). A key distinguishing feature of CE principles is the emphasis on cost minimisation, paving the way for the gradual creation of additional value (Li et al., 2019; Yan et al., 2022). CE aims to revitalize and reclaim the products, harnessing useful waste flows through extended lifecycles (Kjaer et al., 2019; Schroeder et al., 2019; Shihundla et al., 2019). This necessitates significant shifts in firms' managerial practices. Concurrently, servitisation encourages firms to optimise resource utilisation by providing shared platforms at various levels (Adel & Wiesner, 2015; Atif, 2023b; Kühl et al., 2020; Reim et al., 2019; Rymaszewska et al., 2017). By maintaining product/service value within the economy through functional/resource efficiency and enhanced productivity, the product's ownership stays intact with the manufacturer throughout its lifecycle (Cherry & Pidgeon, 2018; Isaksson et al., 2018; Kristensen & Remmen, 2019; Azcarate-Aguerre et al., 2022). Shared platforms serve as a primary catalyst for manufacturing firms to adopt servitisation approaches, facilitating the development of innovative revenue streams (Atif, 2023b; Baines et al., 2017). This shift enables product-based organisations to produce circular goods, while service-providing businesses achieve competitive differentiation strategies (Alvarez-Aros & Bernal-Torres, 2021; Corboş et al., 2023).

2.5. Servitisation as a CE Strategy

Industries and manufacturing organisations have experienced significant transformations in recent decades. Servitisation is closely associated with the demand-pull innovation trajectory (Frank, Mendes, et al., 2019; Liu, et al., 2019). Consumers seek additional services for a better experience as demand shifts from products to outcomes (Cela et al., 2024; Rymaszewska et al., 2017). In some cases, consumers prefer to access the value inherent in products as services, rather than owning the products themselves (Li et al., 2022). This shift has led manufacturing organisations to adopt a servitisation approach that moves away from the product-focused strategy to a Product-Service Systems (PSS) (Kühl et al., 2018; Li et al., 2022; Tukker, 2015; Tukker & Tischner, 2006), with servitisation and PSS often used interchangeably (Reim et al., 2019; Xing et al., 2022). This approach involves an alteration process from a product-focused to a service-focused BM, with servitisation defining the efficacy of this transformation (Kiel et al., 2017). Servitisation integrates goods and services to provide additional features to stakeholders and consumers offering environmental advantages (Adel & Wiesner, 2015). According to Teece et al. (2009) and Witell et al. (2016), this change of approach towards the PSS should be deeply entrenched in the organisational value creation model that refers to the process of creating value for the company. This involves various aspects such as identifying mechanisms for creating and capturing value, delivering value to customers, taking necessary actions to maintain the value created, and identifying complementary strategies to enhance the overall value creation process, collectively referred to as Business Model Innovation (BMI). It has been observed that servitisation is frequently described as an alteration from product-focused manufacturing to an arrangement that offers a blend of products and associated services for creating distinctive strategy (Nudurupati et al., 2016). Manufacturers are progressively integrating strategies focused on services to revitalise commercial approaches that increase the alleged value throughout the entire product's lifespan, ensuring a lasting competitive edge in the market (Atif et al., 2021; Mishra et al., 2020; Nag et al., 2022). The term "servitisation" was first introduced by Vandermerwe and Rada (1988). According to them, it refers to the increasing trend of corporations to offer a complete package or bundle of client-centric amalgamations of goods, services, assistance, self-support, and expertise. This approach aims to provide a full range of services to customers and increase the value of the product (Atif, 2023b).

Figure 2. 3: Value Proposition for Servitisation

Source: (Atif, 2023b)

Figure 2.3 illustrates how servitisation enhances value by transitioning from a product-focused to a product-service system which have been developed from literature adopted from Ejsmont et al. (2020) and Kowalkowski et al. (2017). Studies suggest that servitisation encourages firms to augment resource utilization (Shen et al., 2021; Zheng et al., 2019), necessitating significant changes organisation needs to change its organisational framework, tactics, ethos, procedures and personnel to adjust to the changing business landscape effectively (Azcarate-Aguerre et al., 2022; Baik et al., 2019; Zighan et al., 2021). This transformation presents an opportunity for firms to evolve their BMs, offering a blend of PSS to meet the changing demands of customers and enhance their competitive advantage in the market (Abdelkafi et al., 2022).

A comprehensive analysis of current research indicates that the CE strives to detach income generated from material input through the integration of biological and technical systems to advance material flow efficiency (Werning & Spinler, 2020). This transformative approach necessitates businesses to utilise minimal resources, particularly non-toxic physical components, in producing premium products that can be safely returned to the biosphere (Morseletto, 2020; Nanayakkara et al., 2022). The technical components involve related services and procedures designed to optimise product usage by reintegrating it into the economy (Fagnoli et al., 2022; Marc et al., 2022; Sehnem et al., 2019). Both segments aim to utilise and optimise waste from discarded products (Lieder et al., 2017; Oviedo-Ocaña et al., 2023; Salesa et al., 2023).

According to Kjaer et al. (2019), a two-step usage-focused framework entails shared platforms or cooperation among business entities to forecast customer requirements and develop servitisation approaches. Integrating new remanufacturing with upgraded BMs is poised to elevate remanufacturing as a primary driver of businesses' creation of value, facilitating enhanced management of technology lifecycles and product obsolescence (Ramsheva et al., 2020). Combining remanufacturing with PSS influences the market value of products based on consumer attitudes, behaviours, and values (Kjaer et al., 2019; Rizvi et al., 2023). However, an attitude-behaviour gap exists

among consumers, as Sousa-Zomer et al. (2018) highlighted, indicating that consumer actions may only sometimes align despite favourable attitudes towards PSS. Nonetheless, the perceived value of PSS encourages consumer adoption, underscoring the importance of social and psychological factors (Reim et al., 2019). Lately, industries and consumers have shown increasing interest in adopting sustainable consumption practices aligned with the CE paradigm (Tseng et al., 2020; van Stijn & Gruis, 2019). While society embraces this responsibility, there are challenges in executing this move (Ziaee Bigdeli et al., 2021). To be deemed efficacious, a PSS should provide circular products with integrated EPR and practical functional effectiveness (Azcarate-Aguerre et al., 2022). Customer satisfaction is critical, particularly regarding product ownership and usage (Atif, 2023b).

Various studies have investigated different aspects of servitisation, including theoretical frameworks to ensure product durability via PSS and reconfigurations of operations in accordance with sustainable design principles (Bressanelli et al., 2019a; Kühl et al., 2020). Moreover, research has identified risks and challenges associated with servitisation, such as inconsistencies, subpar product performance, and significant initial costs (Azcarate-Aguerre et al., 2022; Reim et al., 2019; L. Smith et al., 2014). Addressing these challenges requires investments in human and physical capital, innovation in products and processes, and development of new solutions through a shared-value approach (Abdel-Basst et al., 2020a; Kristensen & Remmen, 2019a; Schenkl et al., 2014). Servitisation approaches have been proposed to retain EPR successfully, highlighting the interconnectedness of sustainable business practices. An I4.0 enables shared platforms that have been emphasised to improve utilisation, and maintenance services (Atif, 2023b; Bai et al., 2021; Cenamor et al., 2017).

2.6. Industry 4.0 (I4.0) as CE Strategy

The term "Industry 4.0," introduced as a component of the German industrial approach in 2016 by Klaus Schwab, has emerged as a platform supporting flexible management, operational decision formulations, and automated transformation, ultimately improving customer satisfaction and financial return on investment (Alvarez-Aros & Bernal-Torres, 2021; Atif, 2023a, 2023b). Consequently, data has become integral to business strategy, driving insights into production efficiency, service quality improvement, and infrastructure operations analysis through I4.0 (Rizvi et al., 2023; Yu, et al., 2022). Automation facilitated by I4.0 technologies enables firms to achieve operational efficiency and these technologies are garnering increased attention for their role in automation (Atif et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2022). I4.0 have been widely discussed for their potential to democratize data, enhance operational agility, involve customers throughout the product lifecycle, and improve decision-making (Alkaraan et al., 2024; Atif, 2023b; Bai et al., 2021; Kohtamäki & Partanen, 2016). Several key I4.0 technologies are noteworthy:

- **Big data analytics:** Leveraging massive datasets collected throughout a product's lifecycle, big data analytics transforms unstructured data into actionable business insights, enhancing production, cost efficiency, and SCM (Côte-Real et al., 2019; G. Wang et al., 2016).
- **Cloud computing:** It expedites the process of big data analytics and business intelligence, restructuring business applications and improving market orientation (He & He, 2021; Mourtzis et al., 2020).
- **Artificial intelligence (AI):** AI technologies interpret extensive quantities of data originating from different phases of manufacturing, categorising it to identify patterns and correlations for real-time decision-making (Agrawal et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2022; Dhar Dwivedi et al., 2021).
- **Blockchain:** Integral to the I4.0, blockchain decentralises control and decision-making in intelligent factories, enhancing resource utilization and production viability (Bellucci et al., 2022; Bhatt et al., 2021; Saberi et al., 2019; Teisserenc & Sepasgozar, 2021).
- **Digital twinning:** It creates interactive virtual prototypes that mirror physical systems, enabling performance monitoring and optimization throughout the product lifecycle (Teisserenc & Sepasgozar, 2021; Ulmer et al., 2022).

It has been observed from the review that I4.0 promises to redefine a company's value proposition, improving operational procedures and contributing to consumer satisfaction (Ivanov et al., 2021; Kiel et al., 2017; Piyathanavong et al., 2022). This transformation presents many opportunities and supports firms in enhancing their performance across various domains (Kohtamäki & Partanen, 2016). Adopting I4.0 technologies improves internal infrastructure, business operations models, and customer relationship management (Kohtamäki & Partanen, 2016; Siddik et al., 2023). Moreover, integrating CE principles with I4.0 technologies can positively impact eco-innovation and overall company performance (Bag et al., 2021; Cainelli et al., 2020). Service-based operating models within I4.0 companies emphasise the integration of manufacturing assets including analytics services, comprehensive operations and streamlined mass customisation (Chaudhuri et al., 2022; Lyons et al., 2020; Rymaszewska et al., 2017). I4.0 fosters collaborative communities among connected equipment in factories (Pinheiro et al., 2019).

2.6.1. Smart Manufacturing

I4.0 revolutionises manufacturing operations, transforming them into smart manufacturing environments where data and information, facilitated by sensors, applications, and processes, optimise processes across the supply chain, enhancing system and product efficacy (Atif, 2023b; Cela et al., 2024; Lightfoot et al., 2013; Majeed et al., 2021). Despite the global evolution of I4.0 technologies, its disruptive nature highlights the emphasis on collecting and analysing data for decision-making (Karuppiah et al., 2023; Marc et al., 2022). Literature on I4.0 explores various aspects, including customer acquisition decisions (Gao & Meng, 2021; Sun & Zhang, 2022), incessant upgrading of business procedures (Ivanov et al., 2021; P. Mishra & Yadav, 2021; Okorie et al., 2022), and timely quality delivery at a low price (Marc et al., 2022). While studies delve into the motivators and facilitators of I4.0 capabilities, some highlight feebleness and intimidations linked to this shift (Bag et al., 2021; Bag, Gupta, et al., 2020; Ozkan-ozen et al., 2020). Founded on intelligent, vertical, horizontal, and real-time connection principles, I4.0 utilising machinery, individuals, data, and communication networks to oversee intricate systems dynamically (Atif, 2023a; Jafari et al., 2022; Okorie et al., 2018). Analysis of I4.0 literature accentuates the growing organisational interest in its technical foundations and broader business implications (Kohtamäki et al., 2020; Beier et al., 2021; Majeed et al., 2021). While studies often address challenges faced by organisations transitioning to I4.0, limited attention is given to its critical influence on BMs (Bag, Wood, et al., 2020). Research exploring the ways in which I4.0 can improve organisations' effectiveness to provide, acquire and produce value within BMs remains relatively sparse (Martín et al., 2021; Weking et al., 2020).

Figure 2. 4: A Conceptual framework for I4.0 Technologies Industry

Source: (Atif, 2023a)

It is apparent from Figure 2.4 that I4.0 technologies are categorized into two groups based on their objectives: Front-end Technologies, which aim to facilitate the shift towards intelligent manufacturing, products, supply chains, and work practices that improve material and labor efficiency and Base Technologies, which serve to interconnect or bridge the front-end technologies with intelligence. This activity level is driven by operational and market requirements, providing an additional impetus that distinguishes this revolution from its predecessors. This evolutionary path supports advanced predictive tools (Abdel-Basst et al., 2020; Mourtzis et al., 2020; Shihundla et al., 2019). The data collected systematically can be utilised to recognise uncertainties and formulate informed strategies to surmount challenges, fostering a cooperative, sustainable, and robust supply chain channels (Peker et al., 2020; Shihundla et al., 2019). Consequently, Information Technology (IT) drives manufacturing operations and systems transformations through I4.0 (Beier et al., 2021; Osterrieder et al., 2020). Experts concur that I4.0 heralds technological advancements and entails versatile organisational repercussions (Bag et al., 2021; Kohtamäki & Partanen, 2016; Stock & Seliger, 2016).

2.6.2. I4.0-enabled Platform Approach

I4.0-enabled shared platforms are collaborative digital environments where multiple stakeholders, including manufacturers, suppliers, and customers, interact and exchange data and resources in real time (Cenamor et al., 2017). These platforms leverage advanced technologies to enable seamless communication and collaboration across the value network (Bai et al., 2021). One key feature of I4.0-enabled shared platforms is their ability to facilitate sharing of resources and capabilities among different ecosystem participants. For example, manufacturers can share production capacity or equipment with other companies to optimise resource utilisation and reduce costs. Similarly, suppliers can collaborate with manufacturers to streamline inventory management and logistics processes (Atif, 2023b).

These shared platforms also enable greater visibility and transparency across the supply chain by providing real-time access to data and insights. This allows stakeholders to make more informed decisions and responding promptly to any changes in demand or disruptions in the supply chain. Overall, I4.0-enabled shared platforms play a crucial role in driving collaboration, innovation, and efficiency in manufacturing and supply chain operations, ultimately aiding to the advancement of the smart manufacturing (Cenamor et al., 2017; Senna et al., 2020).

I4.0 technologies provide an intricately interconnected platform merging hardware and software, garnering increased attention from practitioners and researchers (Mourtzis et al., 2020). A prevailing consensus among scholars and researchers is that I4.0 facilitates the convergence of the physical and digital realms (Bressanelli et al., 2018a). IoT technologies aid in digitalising the industrial

manufacturing these systems (Camacho-Otero et al., 2018), thereby contributing to value creation (Frank, Mendes, et al., 2019).

2.7. Linking CE, Servitisation and I4.0³

The CE strategy emerged in today's highly interconnected world to meet increasing demand by providing high-quality products at accessible prices (Okorie et al., 2022). Businesses are increasingly aligning factors that support both economic growth and environmental well-being to establish a sustainable long-term business framework (van Stijn & Gruis, 2019; Rossi et al., 2020; Werning & Spinler, 2020). The EPR approach has been intricately allied with CE strategies, as it incorporates the comprehensive value network (Compagnoni, 2022). For a PSS to effectively augment the practical efficiency of a circular merchandise, it must be aligned with CE principles (Azcarate-Aguerre et al., 2022; A. Q. Li & Found, 2017). According to Okorie et al. (2018), the Europe 2020 initiative has embraced the Ellen MacArthur Foundation's 9Rs design philosophy as a cornerstone of their resource efficiency strategy. This framework embodies circularity principles by retrieving used or discarded constructs or their components as by-products for new products. It also reevaluates BMs, reduces the utilisation of raw resources while improving product efficacy, repurposes used constructs through subcontracting, handles and upkeeps defective products, and repairs and reinforces them through refurbishment. Additionally, this framework involves remanufacturing by using parts or components of used or discarded products to create new ones with the same features and upcycling and reutilising excess products for alternative purposes (Atif, 2023b, 2023a; Atif et al., 2021).

2.7.1. System-based Concept

CE is a system-oriented perception aimed at decoupling revenue generation from material input by integrating organic and mechanical arrangements to optimise material stream (Werning & Spinler, 2020). The CE archetype is extensively pragmatic to condense energy ingestion and promote environmentally friendly developments across the production cycle (Xia et al., 2022). End-to-end SCM can leverage smart devices, sensors, and smart meter data to identify waste patterns and implement real-time waste reduction strategies (Majeed et al., 2021). It operates as a well-structured, interconnected, malleable loop that identifies and abolishes the non-value-added intricacies and waste throughout the production cycle. EPR legislation reshapes waste collection and recycling responsibilities, placing them primarily on the producer/provider (Compagnoni, 2022). Moreover, Azcarate-Aguerre et al. (2022) advocate adopting a servitisation approach to achieve CE objectives,

³ A detailed literature review is available in the Appendix 3: A Detailed Review Linking Servitisation and I4.0 with CE.

encompassing ESG goals related to circular product and service offerings (Campbell-Johnston et al., 2020).

Firms can harness I4.0 technologies across various stages of the manufacturing cycle, augmenting their circular product portfolios with complementary service provisions and advancing their offerings. Servitisation fosters an interconnected value chain through diverse simultaneous customer arrangements. Data placid on shared platforms provided by I4.0 can help firms identify market prospects through comprehensive market evaluations, while SCM can be progressively aligned accordingly. Evaluating the reception and viability of circular products and services is crucial to ensure optimal customer satisfaction. EPR connects CE concepts, enhancing manufacturer liability and proprietorship of raw materials and final products (Azcarate-Aguerre et al., 2022; Compagnoni, 2022). Thus, a flexible, agile, and interconnected mechanism is indispensable for delivering end-to-end customer services (Atif, 2023b; Mathieu, 2001). Change management is imperative to help managers anticipate project viability, allocate resources, and proactively plan projects (Amani & Fadlalla, 2017). Enterprises should educate their leadership teams to identify unbiased trends to mitigate unexpected revenue fluctuations. Companies that strategically align themselves at this juncture will be primed for evolution. Leadership must harness the analytical prowess of I4.0 technologies to formulate business strategies that optimise customer value via servitisation while mitigating costs and waste linked to circular product development. This shift presents compelling prospects by delivering heightened perceived value to customers. Through ongoing interaction with the developmental framework, conventional machinery evolves into precise and self-learning systems, bolstering overall efficiency and upkeep (Shihundla et al., 2019). Case study research by Campbell-Johnston et al. (2021) sheds light on fundamental variations in EPR guidelines and recommends integrating eco-design early in developing circular products to enhance recycling effectiveness and quality at the final stage of the value chain.

2.7.2. Servitisation and I4.0 as a CE strategy⁴

The expanding body of literature on servitisation examines an organisation's ability to respond promptly and effectively to crises (N. Wang et al., 2020). Organisation management identifies various threats including financial, economic, operational, and strategic hazzards, aligning them with company policy (Hock-Doepgen et al., 2020). As businesses propose an assorted array of services, management must comprehend internal and external influences affecting strategic objectives, evaluate risk magnitude and likelihood, and understand risk dimensions such as associations amid menaces and

⁴ The Appendix 1: Definitions of Servitisation and Appendix 2: Types of Services details a detailed discussion of establishing the relationship between CE, Servitisation, and I4.0.

emergency response times. Increased risk lenience enhances an organisation's keenness to reconnoitre uncertain commercial ventures (Smith et al., 2014). Although research presents discrepancies, suggesting that it forecasts potential challenges in unemployment due to innovative technologies enhancing stakeholder transparency and possibly replacing human roles with robots. Hence, all involved parties must improve their competencies and focus on acquiring the latest technical competencies (Mourtzis et al., 2020). Advancements in I4.0 technologies primarily aim to align organisations' integrated value chains by delivering high-quality products and effective customer service (Rehman et al., 2016). This study examines previous research to identify obstacles and methods to mitigate negative effects, highlighting the prospects of I4.0 as a leverage of CE through servitisation.

Emerging real-time product development tools are supplanting conventional ones. The executive team could collaborate to create a tailored dashboard showcasing individual product attributes, competitive standing, revenue sources, and potential customer segments. Circular design guidelines align with the reiterating rotations, encompassing organising, conceptualising, and transmuted into a detailed circular design. Reprocessing focuses on material separation and reuse (Okorie et al., 2022). The challenge with CE lies in managing second and third markets recurrently. For which, businesses are adopting digital twins, AI-powered simulations that integrate circular products with services through PSS (Fagnoli et al., 2022; A. Q. Li & Found, 2017). These progresses lead to improved-intended circular products, efficient systems, and smart services, aiding manufacturers in real-time decision-making, potentially more efficient resource use, and improved ability to predict future demand. An I4.0-enabled PSS assists in developing effective circular products and predicts and mitigates future disruptions by linking the strategy and execution continuum, positioning the entire network from initial stage through to the ultimate outcome with comprehensive data integration (Atif, 2023a).

2.7.3. I4.0-enabled shared platform for Circular product and Services Package

The information generated throughout the industrial process, with the incessant involvement of intelligent gadgets, gauges and detectors, can serve various purposes, such as assessing associated costs and overheads (Majeed et al., 2021), identifying cost drivers, improving operational efficiency, and making pricing or other decisions (Cagliano et al., 2017; Hao et al., 2020). Data mining of this collected information is employed to uncover crucial insights that directly impact PSS design (Rymaszewska et al., 2017). I4.0 represent a significant shift in engineering towards a socially specialized focus, transitioning, for instance, shifting expertise from mechanical engineering to info-tech (Chen et al., 2022). Mechanisation expands the potential for tumbling the industry overheads

across various stages, including design, development, and production cycles (C. Zhang et al., 2021). Information acquired throughout the entirety of a product’s production phase to consumption, is utilised to extract valuable insights for managing operations at different production phases (Prieto-Sandoval et al., 2019).

Figure 2. 5: I4.0-driven Shared Platform for Circular Product and Service Package

Source: (Atif, 2023b)

Figure 2.5 depicts an I4.0-driven shared platform. In the era of I4.0, businesses are grappling with the production, collection, storage, and processing of vast amounts of data, posing challenges for management to extract valuable insights from it (Weking et al., 2020). Consequently, the adoption of I4.0 technologies aids in uncovering treasured intuitions about the merchandise lifecycle from production cycle information. Numerous researchers have advocated for outspreading lifespan of the product and closing loops within the CE (Okorie et al., 2022; Zheng et al., 2019). Operations redesign has been explored across various disciplines, including textiles, architecture, and agriculture (Kjaer et al., 2019; Zucchella & Previtali, 2019; Lieder et al., 2017). Managers can utilise this organised data to achieve accurate insights into their client’s consumption patterns through a joint podium, enabling more informed decision-making (A. Gupta & Singh, 2021). It's crucial to assess enterprises' readiness to adopt these cutting-edge digital trends, substantial change in operational capabilities is necessary. Once the services included in the circular product consortium are defined, the next step is to put them into operation by specifying the data that will be input, output, and utilised by the resource allocation. Considering the essence of PSS, providers must establish performance metrics such as efficiency and

effectiveness. Due to the framework's complexity, the growing utilisation of digital functionalities and contemporary information economics requires reconsidering order concepts, individual responsibilities, and the design and implementation of measures (Isaksson et al., 2018; Kohtamäki et al., 2020; Shen et al., 2021). Digital technology applied in engineering design presents challenges and tests the organisation's competences (Mourtzis et al., 2020).

Arrangements are equipped with standards that facilitate real-time scrutiny after carefully selecting and reviewing statistics from large corporations, and patrons (Kohtamäki et al., 2020; Martín et al., 2021). According to Forrester, big data comprises four variables: data volume, diversity of data, speed of acquiring and analysing fresh data, and data significance (Jabbour et al., 2019; Cardoso de Oliveira et al., 2019). The business milieu is branded by amorphous statistics introducing high uncertainty and risk into executive decisions. Therefore, analysing newly recorded data is crucial for detecting risks encountered in diverse manufacturing operations and evaluating new questions and answers to prevent their recurrence (Bag, Yadav, et al., 2020). Officialdoms need to comfort major data obstacles in today's global milieu to enhance productivity (Ejsmont et al., 2020). Despite the presence of smart devices, numerous production systems struggle to leverage the full ability of big data (Dalenogare et al., 2018; Frank, Dalenogare, et al., 2019).

Given its consideration of an organisation's assorted resources, the PSS emphasises comprehending the success and failure of firms at the organisational level to promote innovation in business operations through the inclusion of value-enhancing services (Bustinza, Lafuente, et al., 2019; Romero & Rossi, 2017). A connected and coordinated infrastructure enables the identifying innovation requirements and effectual diffusion of technological advancements (Stock & Seliger, 2016). Zhao et al. (2021) demonstrated assessing the efficacy of the EPS system in advancing green technology development. The complexity of markets and customer demands makes it challenging to meet EPR requirements (Compagnoni, 2022). Bag & Rahman (2023) discovered the challenges linked to raw material costs and the configuration of the networks. A resilient value chain, guaranteeing the accessibility of PSS resolutions, must accompany the amalgamation towards circularity with enhanced features and effective service offerings (Peker et al., 2020; Lyons et al., 2020). Data analytics help minimize wasteful material flow by streamlining supply chain processes, yielding superior pecuniary aids. Consequently, innovative product design facilitates the re-claim, refurbishment, upgrading and maintenance of products in the production for a prolonged passé (Lexutt, 2020).

Servitisation in the manufacturing sector has positively impacted revenue (Bressanelli et al., 2018a; D'Agostin et al., 2020). Organisations are incentivized to revolutionise circular products to enhance robustness, allowing them to remain in the cycle longer while delivering effective functionality to users (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017; Lüdeke-Freund et al., 2019b). Conventional growth characteristics, future

growth opportunities, and innovation through I4.0 technologies influence growth and differentiated sources of value (Cherry & Pidgeon, 2018; Weking et al., 2020).

2.7.4. End-of-Life Practices/Reverse Logistics

The literature examined in this study highlights the significance of servitisation and CE, with a particular emphasis on servitisation as a key driver for resource reduction (Brown & Lee, 2019; Scheel et al., 2020; Stock & Seliger, 2016). Manufacturers and users consistently make decisions regarding investments and enhancements in the industry, considering various factors in the dynamic global landscape (Cainelli et al., 2020). The servitisation literature aligns closely with the trends observed in I4.0 and CE. Many view CE as a critical concept that substantially enhances servitisation by encouraging prolonged product lifespan, CLSCs, resource and functional effectiveness (Kühl et al., 2019; Reim et al., 2016). Rymaszewska et al. (2017) elucidate how multi-stakeholder partnerships can enhance business operations, leading to competitive advantages, efficient supply chain systems, and cost reduction through stakeholders shared digital solutions.

A CEBM, as proposed by Bressanelli et al. (2018b), shapes how organisations create, gather, and produce value using recycled or reused resources within the organisation's system (Witell et al., 2016). This model encompasses maintenance, repair redistribution, disposal, recycling, refurbishment, energy reclamation, and enhancement (Ghisetti & Montresor, 2019). The concept of CE extends the product lifecycle, and servitisation enables this evolution throughout the product's lifespan (Adel & Wiesner, 2015; Bressanelli et al., 2018b; Kristensen & Remmen, 2019; Kühl et al., 2020; Witell et al., 2016). Servitisation is also a solution for reducing environmental risks (D'Agostin et al., 2020; Ik & Azeez, 2020). Additionally, the product life extension model aims to capture the potential circular value of goods manufacturing (Bustinza, Gomes, et al., 2019), while the sharing platform model links products with interested parties to keep them in the market as long as possible (Atif, 2023b; Cardoso de Oliveira et al., 2019).

2.8. Features of CE⁵

The intersection of CE, I4.0, and servitisation significantly influences organisational performance, enhancing production efficiency and the effectiveness of business systems. Advanced technologies like the IoT facilitates the integration information from conceptualisation to product improvement stages (Lightfoot et al., 2013; Tavera Romero et al., 2021). Through digitisation and servitisation, companies position I4.0 as a key player in supporting future global competitiveness (Atif, 2023b; Kiel et al., 2017). However, uncertainties persist regarding the implications of IoT, with conflicting views

⁵ The features of CE are being used as control variables in the current study.

on its possible drawbacks and advantages among academics and policymakers (Hartley et al., 2020). Evaluating the cost administration of this affiliation is essential for extenuating superfluous expenditures throughout and after the transformation, with a focus on revenue impact, growth, and profitability, as indicated by financial measures (Hartley et al., 2020; Li et al., 2019).

While many studies have examined operational stream redesign, operational efficacy variations, or disparities in performance post-transformation, few have delved into economic parameters and governing perspectives (Govindan et al., 2018; Velte et al., 2020). Businesses embracing servitisation within the context of the fourth industrial revolution and sustainability through the CE paradigm do so in diverse ways, with I4.0 technologies primarily being data-driven analytics offering enhanced flexibility (Bressanelli et al., 2018a; Frank, Dalenogare, et al., 2019; Rosa et al., 2020). However, numerous barriers exist along this path, underscoring the need for further exploration and resolution (Atif, 2023a). Overall, the literature anticipates significant development and exploration of latent variables such as I4.0, servitisation, and CE, elucidating their interplay and expected evolution (Atif, 2023b; Atif et al., 2021; Dev, Shankar, & Qaiser, 2020).

2.8.1. Circular Business Model (CBM)

Business Model (BM) stands as a foundational element in management sciences, essential for addressing global competitive dynamics and ensuring organisational adaptability (Atif, 2023b; Chiappetta Jabbour et al., 2020). It facilitates the delivery of flexible and transparent processes for developing premium products and service packages at competitive prices (Heyes et al., 2018; Kristensen & Remmen, 2019a; Lüdeke-Freund et al., 2019). I4.0 aids in value creation by minimising operational expenses through comprehensive integration, while servitisation enhances efficiency, particularly in reclamation, refurbishment, and resource recovery systems, supported by diagnostic algorithms processing big data (Nazir & Doni, 2024). Conversely, CE signifies a shift towards sustainable economic systems, focusing on material/resource recirculation to achieve ESG benefits (Kirchherr & Piscicelli, 2019; Morea et al., 2022).

Within this framework, understanding value propositions is crucial for identifying why customers prefer one firm over others, driving the analysis of potential prospects within combined BMs (Ivanov et al., 2021). Servitisation strategies, advocated by Kohtamäki et al. (2020), aim to minimise costs and enhance customer services, while Reim et al. (2019) propose a contingency model accommodating various servitisation strategies. This body of literature frequently merges a procedural outlook with an inter-organisational viewpoint, underscoring manufacturing firms' endeavors to integrate CE principles to develop and deliver value propositions collaboratively (Fernandes et al., 2019; Li & Found, 2017; Muller et al., 2022).

Additionally, many studies suggest that manufacturing firms integrate CE principles into their BMs to support product functionality and efficiency and maximise customer value (Bressanelli et al., 2018b; Kühl et al., 2020; Raja et al., 2020). However, while theoretical guidelines exist, empirical case studies investigating the interdependencies between CE and servitisation remain limited, highlighting the need for further practical research in this area (Nudurupati et al., 2016).

2.8.2. Circular Value Domain

The reconfiguration of traditional BM has emerged as a fundamental strategy for reshaping value grids (Ibarra et al., 2018; Ruff & Woschank, 2022). Businesses now aim to provide enhanced value propositions to facilitate effective functionalities for circular products (Garza-Reyes et al., 2019; Man & Strandhagen, 2017; Scarpellini, 2022). These circular value propositions constitute unified rudiments of a BM, enabling businesses to expand a competitive edge in the market (Côte-Real et al., 2019). Unlike the traditional focus on financial value creation, the revised value drivers now encompass value seizing and prospects crucial for a business's market survival (Bressanelli et al., 2019b; Scheel et al., 2020).

The updated value drivers highlight the importance of resource efficiency, material consumption reduction, product lifespan extension with enhanced residual value, and closing the loop (Ghisetti & Montesor, 2019; Kristensen & Remmen, 2019; Lyons et al., 2020; Puglieri et al., 2022). I4.0 is instrumental in improving product design and enticing new clientele, providing technical and maintenance support, and upholding existing customer segments (Heyes et al., 2018; Kohtamäki & Partanen, 2016; Mathieu, 2001; W. Zhang & Banerji, 2017). Various authors have highlighted the possible assistances of integrating I4.0 technologies into BMs through servitisation across different sectors (Rehman et al., 2016; Bag, Yadav, et al., 2020; Rosa et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2022). The analysis highlights the significance of value propositions in delineating drivers of differentiated customer value (Kristensen & Remmen, 2019; Cardoso de Oliveira et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2022). Effective relationship establishment with all value chain actors is crucial for leveraging shared value and achieving collective goals. In servitisation, services play a central role in creating additional value (Fernandes et al., 2019; Raja et al., 2020). Circular value creation revolves around reducing production (Cela et al., 2024; Chen et al., 2022; Werning & Spinler, 2020), material consumption (Tseng et al., 2020; Choudhary et al., 2022), and waste (Di Vaio et al., 2022; D. Rossi et al., 2024; Salesa et al., 2023). It has been observed from the review that CE has catalysed the evolutionary journey of conventional manufacturing firms, whereas servitisation is seen as a tactic or remedy for collaborative value creation in ecosystem restructuring (Isaksson et al., 2018; Agyemang et al., 2019; Prieto-Sandoval et al., 2019; Frederico, 2021). Although value proposition is just one element of BM, researchers have accorded exclusive

importance to the value domain, exploring it through various morphologies including value propositions, delivery, generation, and acquisition (Bustinza, Gomes, et al., 2019; Fernandes et al., 2019; Ik & Azeez, 2020; Mirzaei & Shokouhyar, 2022)

2.8.3. Circular Supply chain management

Supply chain management (SCM) bolsters a firm's competitiveness (Lüdeke-Freund et al., 2019a). In the contemporary dynamic global marketplace, firms need to reassess their supply chains to remain competitive (Rymaszewska et al., 2017). SCM orchestrates the coordination of services provided by autonomous firms across various phases, including manufacture, logistics, and sales, fostering transparency and suppleness through the digitalisation enabled by I4.0 (Beier et al., 2021; Parhi et al., 2022; Jafari et al., 2022). By facilitating the measurement and monitoring of performance parameters, SCM establishes benchmarks to regulate value-added operations (Sajjad et al., 2015; W. Liu, Wang, et al., 2019; Pal et al., 2019; Fernando et al., 2023). Consequently, it has become imperative for firms to incorporate cutting-edge, eco-friendly, and economical solutions within their supply chain networks (Bag, Yadav, et al., 2020).

Establishing a resilient supply network throughout the manufacturing process is still in its early stages (Gupta & Singh, 2021). Consequently, there need to be more managerial research focusing on the movement of materials through flexible reverse and forward logistics (Dev, Shankar, & Swami, 2020; Werning & Spinler, 2020). Implementing the CE notion in servitisation BMs necessitates dynamic competencies through collaboration with various stakeholders (Chiu & Tsai, 2020). Integrating smart goods with enhanced functionality and supplementary services within closed-loop operations in the competitive landscape allows parsimonies to dissociate pecuniary gains from resource value volatility, ensuring a sustainable competitive advantage (Kühl et al., 2020).

This shift highlights the potential benefits of imbuing the CE principles into sustainable products by implementing servitisation to generate value (Sajjad et al., 2015; de Morais et al., 2022; Seuring et al., 2022). However, the literature reveals a gap in determining the preservation of value for used or returned products and the related challenges and expenses of reverse logistics (Kühl et al., 2020). Ramsheva et al. (2020) suggest that restructuring requires enlargement and cooperation throughout the complete supply chain network to bolster resilience and minimise waste. Furthermore, evaluating the efficacy of I4.0 technologies and their aptitude to tackle mechanical, commercial, regulatory, and logistical hurdles is essential. Findings specify that I4.0 will offer premeditated insight into a product's sustainability and operational effectiveness, which can be disseminated throughout a company's supply chain infrastructure (Dalenogare et al., 2018; Frank, Dalenogare, et al., 2019).

2.8.4. Circular Investment Prospects

CE has emerged as a global imperative for fostering sustainable production and consumption. Concurrently, integrating I4.0 technologies into this transition is anticipated to have a reflective impact. Consequently, ensuring that the CE paradigm fulfils its sustainability objectives is crucial. To achieve this, firm management must evaluate the feasibility of adopting the CE paradigm within their BM while embracing servitisation with the aid of I4.0 technologies in an integrated manner. Manufacturers should conduct a comprehensive financial assessment, examining the combined impact of latent variables (CE, Servitisation and I4.0) on revenue streams, monetary recital, and market evolution before embarking on the transition. Studies in this area often highlight the phased transformation of firms from linear to circular models. As per the directives of the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, firms are advised to appraise their revenue streams, considering potential short-term and long-term profit variations (EMF, 2015; Michelini et al., 2017; Puglieri et al., 2022).

The transition towards circularity in the manufacturing sector has positively impacted revenue streams (Sajjad et al., 2015). Businesses are incentivised to enhance product durability, utilising I4.0 technologies to extend product lifespans and deliver efficient functionality (Oghazi & Mostaghel, 2018; Zhao et al., 2021). This shift in strategy influences the Return on Assets (ROA), with variations depending on the payback period. Additionally, market share has been linked to higher revenue streams (Chang et al., 2016; Jin et al., 2015), and firms serving larger markets are expected to capture a broader customer base (Rehman et al., 2016). Strengthening customer relationships enhances a firm's market visibility (Kohtamäki et al., 2020), although academic research has focused less on customer relationships than other elements of BM (Sassanelli et al., 2016).

CE, defined as an economic system focused on recirculating materials/ assets within the supply chain for sustainable development highlight the significance of organisational integration and change management for optimal operational effectiveness (Kohtamäki et al., 2020; Zighan et al., 2021). Servitisation strategies are recommended for companies to reduce expenses while improving customer services (Atif, 2023b), with studies proposing various servitisation strategies such as expansion of services, comparison to standards, digitisation, and collaborative customer involvement (Reim et al., 2019). The literature on servitisation frequently integrates a procedural outlook with an inter-organisational viewpoint. It explores how manufacturing enterprises adopt CE principles to develop and incorporate circular value propositions collaboratively (Hedvall et al., 2019).

2.8.5. Sustainable Development Strategy Statement

Organisations rely on managing investment flows to sustain their growth trajectory (Beier et al., 2021). Size, age, obligations, future growth prospects, and innovation significantly influence their

development (Cainelli et al., 2020). Business growth is intricately linked to acquiring assets and securing financing for them. The trend observed indicates that firms are embracing servitisation BMs to attract new customer segments by providing innovative value-added services (Bustinza, Lafuente et al., 2019) coupled with circular products (Bag et al., 2021; Kühl et al., 2020).

Executives and senior manager must carefully select a sustainable approach that maximises customer satisfaction, as customers are more concerned with a product's benefits than owning it (Bressanelli et al., 2018a; Reim et al., 2019). The integration of CE principles into servitisation is widely cited as aligning growth objectives with environmental responsibility and delivering perceived value to customers (Li & Found, 2017; Kjaer et al., 2019; Peker et al., 2020). Furthermore, the transition towards a CE ensures sustained financial evolution across Expanded market reach through the provision of sustainable PSS (Bhatti et al., 2023).

2.9. CE Integration: A Sustainability Report Overview

The aim of the current study is to assess CE disclosure by examining the utilisation of the servitisation and the I4.0 as integral components of CE strategy. Thus, the researcher has incorporated the 10R strategy of CE to investigate the extent of CE-disclosure practices and its correlation with various constructs of I4.0 disclosure and various constructs of servitisation disclosure practices in the context of selected 100 companies from fortune global 500 listed companies. Therefore, it is viable to investigate a few prior studies that investigated the CE content elements. Krippendorff, (1980) advised presenting a precise and unambiguous description of the phenomenon before conducting a content analysis. Therefore, the research has thoroughly reviewed the extant literature on CE disclosure practices before developing the disclosure index for the current study.

2.9.1. The Emergence of CE Reporting

The CE has emerged as a critical component of sustainability reporting (Ivic et al., 2021; Opferkuch et al., 2022; Tiscini et al., 2022). However, companies often need more systematic reporting of their commitments towards using servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies within their disclosure practices. CE disclosure refers to the information that companies provide about their CE practices in their sustainability reports. This includes details on the company's efforts to reduce waste, enhance resource efficiency, and promote closed-loop systems within their operations, supply chains, and products (Roberts, Georgiou, et al., 2022). The CE can be presented in multiple formats, including quantitative indicators, narrative descriptions, case studies, and visual representations (Sihvonen & Partanen, 2017; Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020). Typical CE indicators encompass metrics such as waste generation and diversion rates, the utilization of recycled or reused materials, and the proportion of

products engineered for longevity (Dagiliene et al., 2020). It has been observed that by reporting details about their CE practices, companies can showcase their dedication to sustainability while fostering transparency and accountability (Scarpellini et al., 2020). CE disclosure assists companies in pinpointing areas for enhancement and directing their initiatives towards adopting a more sustainable CE framework. It also empowers stakeholders to make informed decisions regarding their interactions with companies, informed by their sustainability practices (Yang et al., 2019). Thus, this research builds upon earlier suggestions in the literature concerning the principles of the CE (Sihvonen & Partanen, 2017; Scarpellini et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2019; D'Amato et al., 2019; Dagiliene et al., 2020; Roberts et al., 2022; Scarpellini, 2022). Majority of the previous studies are focused on the integration and implementation of CE principles (D'Amato et al., 2019; Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020; Gunarathne et al., 2021). However, a few scholars specific CE practices like eco-design (Sihvonen & Partanen, 2017); supply chain practices (Doni et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2019; M. P. Singh et al., 2021); management practices (Dagiliene et al., 2020; Gunarathne et al., 2021). Furthermore, only a limited number of studies have employed the 4R strategy of the CE (Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020; Dagiliene et al., 2020).

2.9.2. CE Frameworks and their Limitations

Several organisations and research institutions have developed CE disclosure indexes and other frameworks to compare companies' performance and transparency towards CE practices (Barnabè & Nazir, 2021; Gunarathne et al., 2021; Opferkuch et al., 2022, 2023; Roberts, Georgiou, et al., 2022; Tiscini et al., 2022). Most of these indexes aim to evaluate the effectiveness of company's disclosure of information about the implementation and impacts of CE principles in the business, with the aim of showcasing better transparency and accountability towards circular transition. The current study emphasises developing a comprehensive and robust disclosure index using servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies; academics and industrial practitioners must combine different metrics into composite indicators. These indicators must be technically feasible and provide measures that can be used for strategic decision-making. Thus, the researchers of this study analysed various CE-related tools based on stakeholder perspectives and value propositions:

2.9.2.1. Lifecycle Assessment (LCA)

This circularity tool assesses a product's environmental impact from extraction to disposal. It helps to identify the connection between economic activities and the environment (Ali et al., 2023; Oviedo-Ocaña et al., 2023). However, LCA has some limitations. It requires consistent and accurate data, which can restrict the exploration of new materials. (Karuppiyah et al., 2023). Extensive literature exists on LCA with a product focus, emphasising material input/output analysis (Romagnoli et al., 2023; C. Zhang et al., 2023). Xing et al. (2022) proposed a full lifecycle-based sustainability evaluation model for

remanufacturing ecosystem services (ESs) from a novel perspective of technology-ecology synergy. The aim of the current study is to assess CE disclosure by examining the utilisation of the servitisation and the I4.0 as integral components of CE strategy. By exploring the potential of these approaches, this study seeks to identify the benefits and opportunities that can be leveraged to develop an integrated and comprehensive disclosure index to drive business growth and competitiveness.

2.9.2.2. Circulytics

It is a highly impactful tool presented by EMF to evaluate CE strategies (Łękańska-andrinopoulou et al., 2021). It covers six indicator categories divided into themes. The first theme assesses the organisational commitment towards circularity; the second theme focuses on technology and digitalisation; the third theme emphasises internal and external communication (stakeholder engagement); the fourth theme discusses R&D in circularity with an emphasis on open innovation; the fifth theme talks about circular design and societal values, and the sixth theme concentrates on production, focusing on circular assets (the concept of leasing and sharing economy) (Valls-Val et al., 2023). However, it is important to note that Circulytics may have limitations or drawbacks despite offering valuable insights into an organisation's circularity. Circulytics relies on data provided by organisations to assess their CE performance (Valls-Val et al., 2022). The researchers of the present study argue that the accuracy and completeness of the data are heavily reliant on the management's capacity to gather and report relevant information. Thus, there is a high chance of biased data being recorded that may affect the reliability and accuracy of the CE assessment. Additionally, Circulytics uses standardised indicators to assess CE performance for all companies, and it may only partially capture sector-specific challenges or nuances. Certain industries may face unique CE challenges that need to be adequately addressed by a standardised tool. Thus, the current study's authors believe that the self-developed CE disclosure index shall be used to assess CE performance as it covers the 10Rs of CE and doesn't miss out on any CE strategy. Therefore, organisations in various sectors/industries may use our developed disclosure index to assess their performance accurately.

2.9.3.3. Global Reporting Initiatives (GRI)

The Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) is a widely used tool that standardises sustainability reporting and measures organisations sustainability impacts (Narula et al., 2021). It helps them manage waste, address material issues, and improve production design to increase usage and reduce disposal (Roberts, Georgiou, et al., 2022). However, voluntary GRI reporting limits comparability and transparency (Zheng et al., 2022). Consequently, Dwivedi et al. (2021) suggested that GRI aims to develop a new economic standard-based CE and indicates that governments must address the challenge of insufficient regulations towards sustainability, which may penalise current and future

development. Similarly, Opferkuch et al. (2022) have identified a pressing need to improve the reporting standards for evaluating circularity performance from ESG perspective. Furthermore, Roberts et al. (2022) also indicated the need for research assessing CE disclosure as a pathway to meet sustainability. One limitation of using the GRI standard is its neglect of the social dimension of CE. At the same time, Narula et al. (2021) suggested that adopting I4.0 minimally impacts the social dimension of the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) and highlighted that further investigation on this interface is needed. Sometimes, GRI reporting can encourage companies to focus more on reporting a large quantity of information rather than ensuring the quality and materiality of the disclosed information, which can result in information overload for stakeholders. As a solution, the researchers in the current study utilize I4.0 technologies to adopt the I4.0-enabled shared platform paradigm that leverages the CE implementation.

2.10.2. Embracing Servitisation and I4.0 within CE Reporting

2.10.2.1. Circular- Servitisation: Disclosure Practices

The existing literature highlights the presence of various CE disclosure indexes spanning different sectors and industries, encompassing services as well (Opferkuch et al., 2023). These indexes evaluate and promote CE practices and services across diverse businesses, given the significant role services play in the economy (Atif, 2023b; Atif et al., 2021). However, despite these efforts, there remains a need for an enhanced index or framework tailored to assess the utilization of services as a CE strategy comprehensively. Servitisation disclosure emerges as a pivotal component within this context, referring to the information companies share in their financial or sustainability reports regarding their transition towards offering value-added services that complement or replace traditional product-centric models. This strategic shift, known as servitisation, can be elucidated through various means such as narrative descriptions, quantitative indicators, case studies, or visual representations. Key indicators within servitisation disclosure include revenue or profits generated from services, the types of services offered, and metrics about customer satisfaction or loyalty rates. By disclosing their servitisation strategy and performance, companies aim to provide stakeholders—including investors, customers, employees, and regulators—with insights into their strategic direction and capacity to create value through services. However, the extent and quality of servitisation disclosure in corporate reports have not been extensively explored. Developing and implementing a servitisation disclosure index tailored to the CE context can be a valuable tool in assessing the integration of servitisation within CE strategies. Such an index can facilitate a more comprehensive evaluation of the adoption and impact of servitisation in advancing circularity and sustainability within various industries.

2.10.2.2. Circular I4.0: Disclosure Practices

Sustainability reports can include various disclosure forms regarding I4.0. Companies commonly disclose I4.0 indicators, such as the amount of energy or materials saved through digital process optimization, the types of I4.0 technologies used, and the impact of digitalization on workforce skills and jobs. By disclosing their I4.0 strategy and performance in sustainability reports, companies provide stakeholders, such as investors, customers, employees, and regulators, with valuable information about their efforts to adopt I4.0 technologies and practices. This transparency can demonstrate a company's commitment to sustainability and innovation, promoting accountability in its operations. Additionally, I4.0 disclosure in sustainability reports can assist companies in pinpointing areas needing improvement and steering their efforts to enhance their digital transformation.

2.11. Evidence from Prior Studies on CE, Servitisation and I4.0 Reporting

Several papers propose a review of literature incorporating CE, servitisation, and I4.0 (exploring the intersections of these concepts and proposing frameworks or methodologies that incorporate them). However, there needs to be specific research that integrates CE, servitisation, and I4.0 into a single disclosure index. Thus, the current study has reviewed prior studies focusing on CE, servitisation and I4.0 disclosure practices to gather valuable insights. These will be used to develop a tailored CE disclosure index, including constructs to assess sensitisation and I4.0 being used as CE strategies. Table 2.1 presents the details of prominent studies related to CE, servitisation, and the I4.0-Related studies, which helped the researcher establish the relationship among the latent variables and develop the CE-disclosure index for the current study.

Table 2. 1: Prior Empirical Studies CE, Servitisation and I4.0⁶

Ref.	Method	Country	Sample Size	Ind.	Research Gap	Results
(Doni et al., 2019)	Content Analysis	EU	208	Manufacturing	<p>1: How servitisation supports the tackling of environmental issues and delivering business strategies.</p> <p>2: To understand whether and to what extent the level of servitisation can change the BM and drive possible improvements in environmental performance</p>	<p>-The findings suggest that servitisation improves energy consumption and enhances environmental performance.</p> <p>-Servitisation did not affect corporate sustainability disclosure and other environmental policies such as environmental assurance, emissions-reduction policies, and environmental SCM.</p>
(M. P. Singh et al., 2021)	Content analysis	India	29	Manufacturing	<p>1: By involving stakeholders in the materiality analysis, it can be improved.</p> <p>2: Listed service-based SMEs can also be included in future research to compare and demonstrate the SR practices.</p> <p>3: To understand the position of SR practices in each sector, a comparative study can be done between large sector enterprises (LSE) and MSMEs.</p>	<p>-Large firms need to pay due diligence by engaging their supply chain partners (SMEs) and motivating them to address green practices and social aspects for a sustainable supply chain.</p> <p>-These actions will result in direct and indirect economic impacts on large firms, SMEs, and society through the socio-economic development of the local community.</p> <p>-Strategic tie-ups with investors, lending agencies and higher education institutions should be promoted to leverage SMEs' social and environmental responsibility.</p>
(Gunarathne et al., 2021)	Literature Review	Sri Lanka.	20 companies	Various	<p>1: Investigate how the organisations practice the CE principles from “practice-reporting portrayal gap”.</p> <p>2: More research on CE related disclosures by analysing the sustainability and integrated reports of companies in different</p>	<p>-The Sri Lankan companies’ strong interest to follow the environmental management principles to improve the organisational sustainability performance.</p> <p>-The environmental management actions do not directly embody the principles of the CE, strong macro-level support and guidance could change firm-</p>

⁶ A detailed discussion of key previous studies used in the current study is provided in the Appendix 4: Prior Studies on CE, Servitisation and I4.0 Disclosure.

Ref.	Method	Country	Sample Size	Ind.	Research Gap	Results
					countries, industries, or regions over the years.	level motivation towards circularity.
(Barr eiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020)	Survey	Global	256	Vario us	1: Further research could be focused on the micro level, to analyse how organisations are understanding and implementing CE.	-The results show that organisations focus on reducing and recycling more than repairing and remanufacturing. -Some organisations that engage with the 4Rs do not do it under the CE umbrella, whereas some that claim to apply CE have low levels of engagement with the 4Rs. -CE also must be implemented outside the organisations, in a more holistic way, for example, through better collaboration with stakeholders on CE efforts and activities.
(E. Zhen g et al., 2022)	Case study and quantitative	Global	3 case study and 263 reports	Vario us	1: Future research should expand the time frame of digital disclosure/reporting in context of their communication with stakeholders about their commitment 2: Future research should evaluate the shifting from voluntary to mandatory disclosure likely will impact both the narratives and behaviours of companies.	we find that these companies learned to define the CSR term and adjust their disclosing behaviours gradually, from ad hoc mentioning of idiosyncratic themes to disclosing proliferating themes, often in the dedicated separate website section. Accompanying this change was the growth of global initiatives such as Global Compact and Global Reporting Initiatives and their disclosure guidelines
(Rob erts et al., 2022)	Content Analysis	Global	28 companies from 3 sectors	1: Aero spac e & Défe nse 2: Mot or vehic le	1: More studies are needed to investigate both biodiversity and CE in more sectors. 2: More attention is required to increase the awareness about biodiversity & CE 3: How biodiversity and CE can add value to the companies. 4: How accounting can affect the CE- transition	- The main research outcomes indicate that disclosure scores are generally low, with companies offering minimal and vague information. Many companies received a score of zero across all our disclosure categories, suggesting a lack of understanding of biodiversity and the circular

Ref.	Method	Country	Sample Size	Ind.	Research Gap	Results
				and parts 3: Transportation	and how accounting barriers for the CE can be mitigated.	economy concept among these companies. -There is an increase in the level of disclosures on both biodiversity and CE between 2012, 2014, and 2016 and there is a small decrease for the 2018. -The Motor industry is providing more disclosure on both biodiversity and CE, followed by Aerospace & Défense and Transportation industry was the lowest in providing disclosure on both biodiversity and CE.
(Opferkuch et al., 2022)	Content Analysis	EU	94		1: The transition towards a CE requires transparency. Therefore, further research and engagement is needed to better define the value of CE within external corporate communication.	-Results showed that nearly all companies are explicitly referencing CE, however, only 7% of them integrate CE within all five SR elements. -Less than one third of companies were found to include both targets and indicators for CE suggesting that overall, the content related to the CE in sustainability reports tends to be superficial and lacks consistency
(Dagliene et al., 2020)	Qualitative content analysis and statistical methods	EU	226 companies	Manufacturing	1: The subjective interpretation of 4R is the primary qualitative constraint. This paper used the 4R framework, which the EU has endorsed. However, there may be knowledge gaps between businesses (who generate the reports) and researchers. Therefore, more research is required to provide useful insight for policy implications	-Companies still do not report very much information about the CE. -The most expressed closed loop is R1 (i.e., reduce), as most companies focus on reducing materials. -The resource efficiency approach implemented through the minimization of raw materials and creation of shorter loops and closed loops is weakly disclosed in environmental reporting. -Disclosures of reuse, recycle and recover information in the reports of manufacturing companies are not sufficient.

Ref.	Method	Country	Sample Size	Ind.	Research Gap	Results
(D'A mato et al., 2019)	Content analysis	Global	123 reports		<p>1: Investigate the connection between corporate sustainability management and the way it feeds into public discussion through multi-dimensional CE, GE, and BE concepts.</p> <p>2: Trends in sustainability concepts adopted by firms (considering disclosure practices also in non-DJSI companies)</p> <p>3: The evolving conceptualisation of sustainability and how such disclosure is perceived among external stakeholder groups.</p> <p>4: The correlation between the financial results and the extent of sustainability reporting concerning CE, GE, and BE policies.</p>	<p>-Results suggest CE to be omnipresent and homogeneous across all companies and sectors.</p> <p>-GE was the second most frequent concept, especially in forest and mining.</p> <p>-BE was under-represented in all reports, with the exception of the forest sector. Interlinkages between concepts were few.</p> <p>-The CE-BE connection appeared to be the strongest, concerning efficiency and recycling of bio-based resources.</p>
(Scar pelli ni et al., 2020)	Quantitative: PLS-PM	Spain	87 Questionnaires		<p>1: Investigate the dynamic capabilities specifically needed for the adoption of the CE</p> <p>2: Research the changes in the BM and the monitoring and measurement of flows of raw materials and resources in collaborative models.</p>	<p>-The results suggest a significant affiliation among the CS of organisational, their environmental accounting practices, and their level of CSR and accountability. - Stakeholders' pressure – which has a mediating effect on the CS of firms – is also analysed, adding new insights to recent studies of this topic at the micro-level.</p>
(Sihv onen & Parta nen, 2017)	Content analysis	Global	43 companies	ICT sector	<p>We also draw attention to the fact that reuse alternatives, which are uncommonly published or reported by the businesses in this sample, require greater explanation.</p>	<p>-The publishing of quantitative environmental targets for products is positively associated with lifecycle thinking, considering the durability of products, and remanufacture.</p> <p>-This exploratory study reveals that the quantitative environmental targets for</p>

Ref.	Method	Country	Sample Size	Ind.	Research Gap	Results
						products are positively associated with environmental performance measures. -This includes capability to report quantitatively onflows of reclaimed products, and positions in external ranking.
(Yan g et al., 2019)	regression analysis	China	293 firms	Manufacturing	1: Further studies could take the cost into consideration. to explore more internal factors for a company to enhance the complementarity's effects on CSR performance, such as the organisational structure, process reengineering, or the role of advanced IT technologies in implementing the CE practices	-More studies are needed to extend this topic to Supply Chains and analyse the complementarity between the forward and reverse SC practices. -Following study only consider the two main CE practices (front (eco-design, ECO) and back ends (reverse activities, RA), which may not provide a full picture of CE. -Future research could extend the test of complementarity to other CE practices, such as green procurement, cleaner production, and consumer responsibilities.

2.12. Research Gaps

Based on the above discussion, there is a need for more studies to investigate the influence of CE, servitisation and I4.0 (Frank, Mendes, et al., 2019a; Shihundla et al., 2019; de Moura Leite et al., 2020; Dev, Shankar, & Swami, 2020; Atif et al., 2021; Ruff & Woschank, 2022). Previous studies have suggested that the manufacturers are rooting for a fundamental and dynamic structural change to the ecosystem that was previously lying on the LE BM that succumbed to long-term prosperity and sustainability of the industry. To avoid the environmental catastrophe, manufacturers are adopting service-based strategies to create additional value by offering a circular product with enhanced efficacy. This transition gaits upon the path that is embedded in CE principles and the servitisation approach combined with I4.0 technologies that serve as a facilitator.

Table 2. 2: Research Gaps

Reference	Research Gap Suggested by Previous Studies	Covered in Current Research
(Doni et al., 2019)	1: How servitisation can help address environmental issues and support business strategies.	✓
	2: To determine how much servitisation can alter the BM and drive environmental performance improvements.	✓
(M. P. Singh et al., 2021)	1: How can involving stakeholders improve materiality?	✓
	2: Future research can include listed service-based SMEs to demonstrate and compare SR practices.	✓
	3: To understand the position of SR practices in different sectors, a comparative study can be conducted between large sector enterprises (LSEs) and micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs).	✓
(Gunarathne et al., 2021)	1: It is recommended to investigate how organisations practice CE principles, focusing on the “practice-reporting portrayal gap”.	✓
	2: More research is needed to analyse CE-related disclosures in sustainability and companies' integrated reports across industries, regions, and countries over the years.	✓
(Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020)	1: Instead of focusing on the macro level, further research could concentrate on the micro level to analyse how organisations perceive and implement CE.	✓
(Zheng et al., 2022)	1: In the context of their communication with stakeholders regarding their commitment, future research should expand the time frame of digital disclosure/reporting.	✓
	2: Investigating the impact of shifting from voluntary to mandatory disclosure on companies' narratives and behaviours should be evaluated in future research.	✓
(Roberts et al., 2022)	1: Additional investigation is required to thoroughly scrutinise the affiliation among biodiversity and CE across various industries.	Partly
	2. Future researchers must pay more consideration to raising awareness about the importance of biodiversity and CE.	Partly
	3. Examining how biodiversity and CE can bring value to companies is important.	Partly
	4: The study of how accounting practices can impact the transition to CE and how accounting barriers for CE can be resolved is crucial.	✓
(Opferkuch et al., 2022)	1: More research is necessary to comprehend the extent of transparency in CE's external corporate engagements.	✓
(Dagiliene et al., 2020)	1: The subjective interpretation of 4R is the primary qualitative constraint. This paper used the 4R framework, which the EU has endorsed. However, there may be knowledge gaps between businesses (who generate the reports) and researchers. Therefore, more research is required to provide useful insight for policy implications	✓
(D'Amato et al., 2019)	1: Investigate the connection between corporate sustainability management and its impact on public discourse through multidimensional CE, GE, and BE concepts.	Partly

Reference	Research Gap Suggested by Previous Studies	Covered in Current Research
	2. Analyse the trends in sustainability concepts adopted by firms, considering disclosure practices even in non-DJSI companies.	Partly
	3. Explore the evolving conceptualisation of sustainability and how external stakeholder groups perceive such disclosure.	✓
	4: The affiliation among the financial performance and company levels of sustainability disclosure for CE, GE, and BE policies.	✓
(Scarpellini et al., 2020)	1. Please investigate the dynamic capabilities that are specifically required for the adoption of the CE.	✓
	2. Please research the changes in the BM and the monitoring and measurement of flows of raw materials and resources in collaborative models.	✓
(Sihvonen & Partanen, 2017)	1: We would also like to highlight that reuse alternatives require greater explanation as businesses rarely publish or report them.	✓
(Yang et al., 2019)	1: It is important for further studies to consider the cost and internal factors such as organisational structure, process reengineering, and the role of advanced IT technologies when implementing CE practices.	Partly

Table 2.2 presents the research gaps identified from the key studies. The researcher has indicated in the table what research gaps the current study fills. Most of the research, including studies like Frank, Mendes, et al. (2019a); Shihundla et al. (2019); de Moura Leite et al. (2020); Dev, Shankar, & Swami (2020); Atif et al. (2021) and Ruff & Woschank (2022) continuously stressed the significance of methodically integrating I4.0 technologies within enterprises. This alignment with the CE framework facilitates value generation through the adoption of servitisation approaches. Nevertheless, there remains a deficiency in tangible ramifications that could substantiate the theoretical understanding (Reim et al., 2016; Ibarra et al., 2018; Rosa et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020). Thus, more empirical evidences are required about reconfiguration of the BM (Adel and Wiesner, 2015; Geissdoerfer et al., 2017; Conference, Etienne and Siadat, 2018; Kohtamäki et al., 2020), mainly concerning the capture of value via open innovation (Witell et al., 2016; Rizos et al., 2016; Ghisetti & Montresor, 2019; Fernandes et al., 2019), establishing the CE-strategy grounded on sustainability stance (Michellini et al., 2017; Zucchella & Previtali, 2019; Cainelli et al., 2020; Scheel et al., 2020), providing smart circular products via intelligent services and overseeing the distribution network (Surajit & Christiaan, 2020a; Giovanni, 2020; Ünal et al., 2019; Gupta et al., 2019).

Moreover, companies are often compelled to explore novel BMs (Adel & Wiesner, 2015) to seize distinctive value propositions while mitigating operational expenses (Rehman et al., 2016; Shihundla, Mporfu and Adenuga, 2019; Dev, Shankar and Qaiser, 2020a; Nakata and Bahadir, 2020). It is evident that the majority of servitisation literature addresses the operational perspective (Adel & Wiesner,

2015; Rehman et al., 2016) and it has been viewed as a route that amplifies downstream possibilities by delivering independent services to their clientele (Bustinza, Gomes, et al., 2019; Rymaszewska et al., 2017). Notwithstanding the uncertainties and risks encountered during the transition period (Ejsmont et al., 2020; Reim et al., 2016; Rymaszewska et al., 2017), majority of the previous literature reach agreement that the transition towards circularity brings substantial benefits to any firm. A few researchers like (Adhikari parajuli et al., 2021; Hassan et al., 2021, 2022; Yu, et al., 2022) have suggested to embed the economic, social, and environmental business reporting in corporate reports includes metrics for monitoring waste, waste management practices, end-of-life pathways, material inflows and outflows, and other key performance indicators (KPIs) related to the CE. It is noted that there are two main issues that needs to be highlighted from this study, which are:

Reason 1: The CE has mostly been viewed as a vital catalyst for economic growth and development spectrum in both developed and developing economies (Brown and Lee, 2019; Tykkyläinen, 2019). However, few studies have been conducted to specifically comprehend how businesses are implementing CE principles within their BM and how they are disclosing the impacts and practice of CE-transition (Roberts et al., 2022). Most of the disclosure-based research have focused prominently on Corporate social responsibility (Adhikari parajuli et al., 2021; Al-Shaer et al., 2022; Quick & Inwinkl, 2020; Yu, et al., 2022) and have not focused extensively on CE strategies. Besides some earlier research that has used CE have focused on specific country like India (M. P. Singh et al., 2021), China (Yang et al., 2019; Yu, et al., 2022); Sri Lanka (Gunarathne et al., 2021) using case studies (Opferkuch et al., 2022; Zheng et al., 2022). Therefore, the conclusion that can be drawn from the discussion above is that there has been lack of a holistic disclosure index that measure and report the circularity metric (circular design: resource use; responsible production and consumption and progress in the transition towards CE) in a credible manner.

Reason 2: Prior research demonstrates unequivocally the advantages of adding service provision to product consortium (Michelini et al., 2017; Bressanelli et al., 2018b; Heyes et al., 2018; Chiappetta Jabbour et al., 2020; Nag et al., 2022), sustainable supply chain perspective (Cardoso de Oliveira et al., 2019; A. Gupta & Singh, 2021; Piyathanavong et al., 2022; Bag et al., 2022) CE capabilities, eco-innovation and digitalisation (Rosa et al., 2020; Bag et al., 2020; Atif et al., 2021; H. Gupta et al., 2021; Romero et al., 2021; L. J. Zheng et al., 2022) or using I4.0 technologies in designing the product-service system/servitisation approach (Shihundla et al., 2019; Frank, Mendes, et al., 2019a; de Moura Leite et al., 2020; Dev, Shankar, & Swami, 2020; Ramsheva et al., 2020). It has been noted that the descriptive research conducted by previous researchers are mainly extending the idea of design and development of innovative product (Nudurupati et al., 2016; Isaksson et al., 2018; Azcarate-Aguerre, Klein, et al., 2022), smart manufacturing (Zheng et al., 2019; Abdel-Basst et al., 2020a; de Moura Leite et al., 2020;

Majeed et al., 2021; Jafari et al., 2022), reconfiguration of BM (Davies & Doherty, 2019; Garza-Reyes et al., 2019; J. Han et al., 2020; Kohtamäki et al., 2022; Scarpellini, 2022), experimenting with smart services and smart contracts (Peker et al., 2020; Rupa et al., 2021). Nevertheless, research assessing CE principles employing a servitisation strategy and a connected platform supported by I4.0 still need to be included. Thus, the researcher has created a comprehensive CE disclosure index to examine how the 10R strategies of the CE align with servitisation and I4.0. This analysis uses multiple constructs where servitisation illustrates its role as a medium for reintegrating used products into the cycle via I4.0-enabled platforms, addressing a gap in existing research on the intersection of CE, servitisation, and I4.0.

2.13. Development of CE Disclosure Index

As outlined in the literature review, a pressing need exists for an enhanced disclosure index to support manufacturers in developing circular products and leveraging servitisation and I4.0 as integral components of a CE strategy. This Phase followed a 2-step analysis for self-development of the CE-disclosure index. In the first phase, the researchers categorized the variables into three groups: dependent variable, independent variables, and control variables. This approach aims to provide clarity and precision in assessing the adoption of servitisation and I4.0 within CE practices, facilitating informed decision-making and strategic planning among manufacturers and stakeholders. The researchers developed a comprehensive CE disclosure index⁷ (presented in Table 2.3: CE Disclosure Index) which is as follows:

⁷ The CE-disclosure index was developed after a thorough literature review and identification of research gaps. In Appendix 5: Constructs of the CE Disclosure Index, the researcher explained how to measure each construct of the CE, servitisation, and I4.0 constructs and provided a rigorous and standardised framework for assessing companies' CE-related disclosure practices.

Table 2. 3: Circular Economy Disclosure Index

Var	Phase	Code	Constraints	Measurement Metric	References	Keywords
Dependent Variable: Circular Economy (CE) Components	CE- Phase 3: Circular Design R1: Refuse R2: Rethink R3: Reduce	CER1	R1: Refuse	Co. reporting about making an unsustainable product redundant, which aims to stop producing or supporting a development that is difficult and expensive to bring back to the production cycle after use.	(Opferkuch et al., 2022)	Refuse Replace Reject Substitute
		CER2	R2: Rethink:	Co. reporting about designing a circular product making it more intensive through design	(Gunarathne et al., 2021; Roberts et al., 2022); (Opferkuch et al., 2022) GRI, 2021	Rethink Redesign Transform
		CER3	R3: Reduce	Increase efficiency in product use or manufacture by consuming fewer natural resources. the total environmental consumption burden and reducing the resource use	(Gunarathne et al., 2021; Roberts et al., 2022) (Opferkuch et al., 2022) GRI, 2021	Reduce
	CE- Phase 2: Responsible Production & Consumption R4: Reuse R5: Repair R6: Refurbish R7: Remanufacture R8: Repurpose	CER4	Reuse	The weight of waste generated directed to recovery or disposal i.e., the waste streams, relevant to its sector or activities (e.g., tailings for the mining sector, electronic waste for electronics sector, or food waste for agriculture or in the hospitality sector). Another consumer utilising a discarded product that remains in good condition and serves its intended purpose.	(Gunarathne et al., 2021; Roberts et al., 2022) (Opferkuch et al., 2022); (Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020) GRI, 2021	Reuse second-hand
		CER5	Repair	Co. reporting about repairing and regular maintenance of a product to extend the lifespan of a product and minimize the need for costly replacements.	(Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020); (Opferkuch et al., 2022)	repair, maintenance
		CER6	Refurbish	Co. reporting about scalable refurbishing and restorative initiatives, which aims to embrace efficiency via upgrades while reducing waste.	(Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020); (Opferkuch et al., 2022)	Refurbish Upgrade
		CER7	Remanufacturing:	Co. reporting about using components from a castoff product in a novel product, which aims to reduce waste and save resources.	(Gunarathne et al., 2021; Roberts et al., 2022) (Opferkuch et al., 2022); (Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020) GRI, 2021	Remanufacture
		CER8	Repurpose	Co. reporting about using discarded products for their parts that might otherwise have discarded in a novel product with a distinct function which aims to repurpose materials and reduce waste.	(Opferkuch et al., 2022)	Repurpose Upcycle
	CE- Phase 3: Return of Used	CER9	Recycle	Co. reporting about recycling a used product, which aims to process materials to obtain the same (high grade) or lower (low grade) quality	(Opferkuch et al., 2022) GRI, 2021	Recycle

Var	Phase	Code	Constraints	Measurement Metric	References	Keywords
	Product and Bringing it Back to Production Cycle R9: Recycle R10: Recover	CER10	Recover	Co. reporting about total weight of waste (hazardous and non-hazardous) diverted to/from disposal in metric tons, and a breakdown of this total by composition of the waste.	(Gunarathne et al., 2021; Roberts et al., 2022) (Opferkuch et al., 2022) (Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020) GRI, 2021	Recover
First Independent Variables	Servitisation as a CE Strategy	SER11	Servitisation as a CE strategy	Co. reports on adding service-provision into their Product consortium, which aim to Bring back used constructs from the customers back to the production cycle	(Li et al., 2015) (Doni et al., 2019)	Sharing Economy Renting Leasing Product-Service System PSS PAAS
		SER12	Waste recovery for servitisation	Co. reporting whether the mixed recycling is sorted and separated into different types of materials by hand or machine (or both) before being sent to manufacturers who make it into new products	(Scarpellini et al., 2020)	Waste recovery Waste Management
		SER13	Minimise usage of virgin material	Co. reporting about making their products or packages from waste. This generates demand for recycled content, which, along with recycling, creates a recycling-based CE	(Scarpellini et al., 2020)	Minimum Use Resource Reduction
		SER14	End-of-Life Practices/ Reverse Logistics	Co. reporting about “tightening the circle” by moving from recycling to reuse through Loop, which aim to develop a global reuse platform that allows the customers to easily return the used construct.	(Mirzaei & Shokouhyar, 2022)	Reverse Takeback
Second Independent Variable	Industry 4.0 as a CE Strategy	IND15	Transparency and Accountability	Co. reporting on successfully enabling a low-cost data-driven management system, providing an eco-friendly product with high sustainability, which can rapidly reconfigure and remanufacture itself with reusable/recyclable materials and components.	(Cenamor et al., 2017)	Transparency Accountability Data sharing
		IND16	I4.0-enabled shared platform	Co. reporting of successfully implementing Data-driven remanufacturing/replacing initiatives to measure the feasibility of accelerating the supply chain transition towards CE.	(Cenamor et al., 2017)	Digital Platform Data-driven Digital ecosystem Smart Platform
		IND17	Resource Efficiency	Co. reporting about innovating/experimenting with product’s design or services, which aims to develop a resource efficient product	(Scarpellini et al., 2020)	Smart Manufacturing Resource Optimisation
		IND18	Extended lifecycle	Co. reporting about product’s design or services modification, i.e., implementing product design strategies and providing repair services that prioritise the sharing or renting to extend product life which aims to reduce waste.	(Scarpellini et al., 2020)	Product life Lifecycle extension

Var	Phase	Code	Constraints	Measurement Metric	References	Keywords
		IND19	Functional Efficacy	Co. reporting about processes and operating procedures replaced or improved to reduce energy consumption or exploit renewables, aiming to improve energy efficiency and transition to renewable energy sources.	(Scarpellini et al., 2020)	Functional Efficacy Sustainable Function Smart Product
		IND20	Innovation through I4.0	Co. reports about components of products or services replaced with innovative features to comply with environmental regulations, which aims to become more environmentally conscious that comply with regulations.	(Scarpellini et al., 2020)	Human-machine Robotics Automation Connected
		IND21	Monitoring Resource Use	Co. reporting about transition to smart services and upgrade contracts using I4.0 technologies	(D'Amato et al., 2019)	Collaboration Digital Transform Monitoring Stakeholder Engagement
Control Variable	Features of CE	CBM2 2	Circular business model	Co. reporting about adoption and implementation of CE principles within their business model, which aims to decouple the economic activities from resources, material, and carbon intensity.	(Opferkuch et al., 2022)	Circular Business Model Business Model Sustainable Business Model
		SCM2 3	Supply Chain Management: Reverse activities/logistics	Co. reporting about specialised service-design, ensuring the CE principles are successfully adopted across the multi-layered, distributed supply chain as well as reuse data platform enabling flexible, robust, and low-cost data sharing across the supply chain, which aims to generate revenues from undervalued waste stream through smarter and resilient reverse logistics and less waste.	(Yang et al., 2019); (Doni et al., 2019)	Regenerative economic system Circular supply chain Sustainable supply chain Reverse logistics Closed loop Green logistics
		CVP24	Circular Value Proposition	Co. reporting about eco-design, eco-label legislation requiring QR code labelling to accelerate and de-risk the Co.'s transition towards "remanufacture not replace"	(Yang et al., 2019)	Circular value Innovative value
		IED25	Investment in Eco-design	Co. reports about the company's profitability achieved from circular projects relative to its equity which aims to document how the impact of CE principles improved their financial performance.	(Bogdan et al., 2022)	Circular Innovation Eco-investment Green-investment Circular Project
		SDS26	Statement on sustainable development strategy	Co. reporting about strategies to manage data sharing among customers and suppliers, which aims to de-risk and streamline the remanufacturing process and strengthening stakeholders' confidence in adopting CE business model.	GRI, 2021	Sustainable development

Later using the self-developed CE disclosure index, the researcher conducted a manual content analysis using that disclosure index to quantitatively measure the association between adoption of

10R strategy of CE paradigm and the extent of various constructs of I4.0 disclosures and the extent of various constructs of servitisation disclosures on leveraging the transition towards circularity.

In the second step of the research process, definition of scores (presented in Table 2.4) was set and then utilised to measure the existence, frequency, and practical implications of the 10R-strategy of CE, I4.0, and servitisation disclosure practices. This was done through content analysis, where the researchers inferred the awareness of these practices by assigning scores on a 0-3 scale. Constructing a scorecard for disclosures can be achieved through the weighted approach (subjective judgment based on the specific objectives) and the unweighted approach where same score is used irrespective of a construct’s objectivity (Valls-Val et al., 2022). Both methods have unique advantages and can be used to evaluate and measure disclosure performance effectively (Alvarez-Aros & Bernal-Torres, 2021). For example, Singh et al. (2021), Zampone et al. (2022) and Raimo et al. (2022) used binary coding of 0 for no disclosure and 1 for presence of disclosure. These studies did not have a specific focus on their constructs (Singh et al., 2021) and selected an easy comparison method to avoid bias by not using subjective weights (Zampone et al., 2022). However, Bogdan et al. (2022) and Roberts et al. (2022) used a weighted approach as both studies attempted to fully comprehend the relevant disclosure practices.

Table 2. 4: Definition of Scores

Score	Definition of Scoring
0	No disclosure.
1	General disclosure.
2	Objective and verifiable disclosure.
3	Objective and verifiable disclosure with monetary value, program details, future strategies, targets etc.

The aim of the current study is to assess CE disclosure by examining the utilisation of the servitisation and the I4.0 as integral components of CE strategy. Thus, the researcher applied the weighted index approach for constructing a definition of scoring (presented in Table 2.4). The scores were as follows: 0 meant no disclosure, 1 indicated general or partial disclosure, 2 represented verifiable and objective disclosure, and 3 represented objective, verifiable disclosure with monetary value, program details, future strategies, and targets mentioned. The scoring definition followed the guidelines presented by Roberts et al. (2022). Once the disclosure index and scoring definitions were finalised, the data collection for content analysis began. The researcher drew inspiration from established methodologies. A list of sub-sets of CE disclosures (10 constructs) was generated, including servitisation (4 constructs) and I4.0 (7 constructs) as CE strategies with inclusive control variables (5 constructs) to analyse the extent of disclosures by considering the difference among latent variables. The list was coded using main variables and indicators, resulting in a CE disclosure index with 26

constructs grouped under various themes. The lowest disclosure scores for each variable would be *10*0=0 for CE, 4*0=0 for SER, 7*0=0 for I4.0 and 5*0=0 for CV* and the highest disclosure scores will be *10*3=30 for CE, 4*3=12 for SER, 7*3=21 for I4.0 and 5*3=15 for CV.*

2.14. Chapter Summary

This chapter discusses the existing literature related to integrating I4.0 and implementing servitisation as a CE strategy, aiding the researcher in achieving the RO1. By establishing the relationships among the latent variables (CE, servitisation, and I4.0) with the help of previous research and existing theories, this chapter highlights the potential of servitisation and I4.0 in leveraging CE principles by promoting resource efficiency, sustainable BMs, and fostering innovation in various industries. The findings demonstrate the transformative power of digital technologies in optimising resource utilisation, improving operational efficiency, and promoting environmental stewardship within manufacturing contexts. This chapter emphasises how servitisation enables companies to reduce waste, extend product longevity, and promote resource efficiency by providing maintenance, repair, refurbishment, and product upgrades. By doing so, businesses enhance a product's useful life, reducing the need for novel engineering and minimising waste generation. Servitisation encourages a shift towards more sustainable consumption patterns, where customers pay for the use of products rather than ownership. While I4.0 technologies are not just tools but enablers of a sustainable future. I4.0 facilitates the implementation of CE practices by optimising resource utilisation, reducing waste, and enabling closed-loop production systems. This data-driven approach, powered by I4.0 technologies, is the key to making more informed decisions that align with CE principles. Furthermore, I4.0 technologies enable the development of innovative BMs, such as asset-sharing platforms, where companies can offer access to products and services based on usage rather than ownership. These models promote resource efficiency, reduce overconsumption, and support the circular economy transition. This chapter also highlights the importance of transparent and comprehensive sustainability reporting regarding CE-related reporting and disclosure practices. Companies must adopt clear approaches to reporting on the integration of CE, servitisation, and I4.0 technologies. This includes disclosing information about material sourcing, product lifecycle management, waste reduction, and product efficacy enhancement. Effective reporting practices help prevent greenwashing and ensure that stakeholders can verify companies' genuine commitment to CE principles. This chapter concludes that integrating reverse-logistics perspectives within servitisation and utilising the potential of I4.0 are essential components of a comprehensive CE strategy. Additionally, transparent and accountable CE reporting practices are crucial for fostering stakeholder trust and supporting the broader adoption of sustainable and circular business practices.

Chapter 3: Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses

Development

3.1. Introduction of the Chapter

The main objective of this study is to investigate the disclosure practices related to CE, Servitisation, and I4.0 in manufacturing companies. This chapter is outlined as follows: section (2) presents the theoretical framework, discussing and justifying the existing theories; Section (3) demonstrates the overview of triangulation of theories; section (4) discusses the three phases of CE constructs from CE disclosure index and Section (5) will present a thorough discussion on hypothesis development based on theoretical framework (triangulation of theories)

3.2. Theoretical Framework

This section will demonstrate the three foundational theories used in the literature: Resource-Based View (RBV), Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCT), and Stakeholder Theory (ST). These theories underpin the theoretical framework of the current study, depicting how organisations can develop a comprehensive sustainability strategy that covers all phases of their operations and product consortium. These theories address environmental sustainability, social responsibility, and economic growth strategies.

3.2.1. Resource-based view (RBV)

RBV theoretical framework is considered as the basic principle in strategic management research that involves a comprehensive inspection of the resources used to detect a firm's competitive position in the market (Lee et al., 2020). RBV originated from "The theory of the firm" that was initially presented by Penrose in 1959 (Kozlenkova et al., 2014). RBV distinguished between the two types of resources involved in any business. i.e. human resources and physical resources. It implies on emphasising the value of resources that enhance the productive purpose of a firm. Later, Wernerfelt, 1984 protracted the types of resources as tangible and intangible (C. M. J. Lee et al., 2020; Kozlenkova et al., 2014; Zahra, 2021). This was further improvised by Barney (Jay, 1991) with an assumption that resources have diversified portfolio. In the CE context, RBV is used to highlight the importance of evaluating and understanding the value creation process, which is fundamental to CE strategies. This understanding is crucial for managing resources effectively and ensuring the availability of the right amount and quality of resources necessary for the execution of the value creation process. By managing resources efficiently, firms can enhance their ability to create value through sustainable practices, reduce waste,

and improve resource efficiency. The RBV, deeply rooted in strategic management literature aids in analysing the impact of transition strategies on company performance (Carnahan et al., 2010). Despite its significance, much of the CE-related literature lacks an understanding of antecedents of resource value, and the subjective nature of individual CE strategies (10Rs) means their implementation involves varying resources (Gueler & Schneider, 2021). Tukker (2015) highlights the role of servitisation in effective resource management and advocates that servitisation can intensify material usage, thereby reducing the need for new materials, however; this process may require radical strategic changes. Supporting this narrative, Khanra et al. (2022) suggest that businesses should innovate strategic resources for reverse-logistic servitisation using advanced technologies (I4.0), sustainability expertise, and connected platforms to reintegrate raw materials, components, and used goods into the production cycle. RBV theory views a firm as a bundle of diverse resources, enabling it to identify its strengths and capabilities, which are essential for strategy formulation (Paper et al., 2020). As rightly observed by Zahra (2021), allocating the resources efficiently help businesses to expand their market and sustain in a dynamic environment as they are being more progressive in translating their strengths into competitive advancement through I4.0 technologies (Dev, Shankar and Qaiser, 2020a). Therefore, RBV is considered to be most relevant theory that assist the researcher of this study to understand that how a company can attain a competitive edge in the marketplace by adapting, integrating, and reconfiguring its resources within a digital landscape, linking clienteles in the process of value co-creation (Davies & Doherty, 2019).

3.2.2. Dynamic capabilities (DCT)

The concept of dynamic capabilities (DCT) was introduced by (Teece et al., 2009b). The theory comprises of two key terms dynamic and capabilities. Dynamic in the context of this theory means the ability of an organisation to rejuvenate its competences in order to achieve a harmonic change in its business. While, capabilities emphasises on strategic management's critical role in adapting, integrating, and restructuring resources and competencies to meet changing environment. Thus, reconciling RBV and DCT seems a promising path to expand the knowledge about favourable management practices during the transition from LE to CE. (Teece et al., 2009b) later expands their prior work by exploring the micro elements of dynamic capabilities, and suggests three distinct forms: **Sensing capabilities:** It refers to sensing a firm's capacity to explore new markets and possibilities based on the business' expertise and learning skills. This study applies the DCT's sensing capability as a theoretical framework for investigating a combination of circular product with servitisation and suggests that I4.0 technologies facilitate a firm to adopt a robust technical approach that enhances the internal organisational and management environment while creating value/wealth (C. M. J. Lee et

al., 2020). To be more precise, value creation is contingent on identifying innovative opportunities and availing them to enhance a firm's operations in an efficient and effective manner (Teece, Pisano and Shuen, 2009a; Chiappetta Jabbour et al., 2020a).

Seizing capabilities: When a new opportunity is identified, it must be handled by investing in the development of innovative goods, services, or processes. Firms must then alter or deploy their current resources to respond to such possibilities. Therefore, it is advised for firms to implement innovative methods to cut operational expenses and increase economic advantages (Gunday et al., 2011). The shift towards CE is characterized by the innovative vigour of the servitisation approach, representing the culmination of the "New green market" (Hafezi & Zolfagharinia, 2018; Rizos et al., 2016; Zahraee et al., 2018). According to (Sivarajah et al., 2017), adopting intellectual resource capabilities can have a major influence on financial performance. (Bianchi et al., 2022) went on to say that this may be accomplished by actively monitoring environmental viewpoints and leveraging new possibilities in the market.

Transforming capabilities: Innovation only sometimes delivers growth prospects directly, which can be done by raising its production capabilities. Businesses are opting for introducing innovative ideas by redesigning and customising services-provision to gain a competitive advantage. That helps sustain existing customers' loyalty and attracts new segments of customers (S. Gupta et al., 2019). R&D activities (I4.0 technologies) are considered significant at the origin or commencement phase of any product's life cycle or service package (Bustinza, Gomes, et al., 2019). It is believed that by implementing the CEBM and redesigning its servitisation approach, the management pledges to minimise wastage and reduce environmental pollution (Mathew et al., 2020). Hence, the key to sustainable development is correlated with its green innovation and green sustainable capabilities (S. K. Singh et al., 2022).

Sustainability reports present information regarding ESG concerns and disclosures on environmental management activities as these subside CE transformation (Scarpellini et al., 2019). It provides insights into investments in circular-design-innovation, usage of renewable energy, and focusing on reverse-logistic servitisation that require specific capabilities of businesses (Scarpellini et al., 2019). This correspondences with the study by Soomro et al. (2022) which suggests that business should modify their resource bases into new competencies based on the environment, as RBV is employed in this study to understand the theoretical basis for redesigning company models that supply circular products and added value utilising I4.0 technology. While, DCT will help the researcher to get holistic insights about on a firm's ability to continually rearrange and reconfigure its resources to identify and achieve a competitive edge in the market. Therefore, in this study, an evaluation of fortune 500 listed

companies' ability to sense, seize and reconfiguration resource allocation together with managerial approaches will be undertaken to help them embed the CE principles in their practices.

3.2.3. Stakeholder Theory (ST)

A recent increase in demand by the stakeholders from the large companies and public institutions has been noted to make their CE practices transparent and visible. As noted in the literature review, the CE is crucial for corporate expansion, and sustainability reporting now plays a pivotal role in documenting ESG impacts and the degree of transition towards circular practices. According to Al-Shaer et al., (2022), businesses must engage in ecological sustainability and pursue CE strategies to achieve stakeholder-oriented outcomes. Relationships with stakeholders built on mutual trust and cooperation to act morally and honestly (Freeman et al., 2021). Due to growing pressure from the stakeholders, businesses are embracing servitisation (reverse logistics) to reintegrate used products into the production cycle, alongside utilising I4.0 technologies to create transformative opportunities through shared platforms for transparent stakeholder engagement. Hence, the research shows that a significant number of researchers have employed servitisation to illustrate the consistent affiliations among all the stakeholders of any business. The ST also suggest that all the stakeholders including the government, businesses, academia, and society must play their role in the circular transition. The government must regulate the compliance of sustainability goals to influence businesses (Kuo & Chang, 2021). Based on research conducted by Kuo & Chang, (2021), highlighting that regulations, tax incentives, and subsidies puts a significant impact on corporate strategies. Therefore, ST seems to an appropriate theory to elaborate on importance of compliance with GRI reporting standards and assessment of performance goals so the companies can constantly manage their performance and report their ESG impact against other companies and industries.

It is worth mentioning that a company's ability to survive depends on positive relationships between internal and external stakeholders (Lüdeke-Freund, Gold and Bocken, 2019) that leads to the success of the company' BM. Singh et al., (2022) explored the impending influences of stakeholder involvement and identified stakeholder pressure as a primary motivator for implementing CE and sustainability initiatives in businesses. Maximising shareholder interests is a company's principal objective, but to achieve this, the company must also consider the interests of other stakeholders (D. Lee & Hess, 2022). According to ST, all stakeholders should be treated equally, regardless of their level of power. In line with this, Mazzucchelli et al., (2022) emphasised the importance of using 3R (reduce, reuse, recycle) practices of CE to establish and reinforce relationships, thereby enhancing firm performance. This research aligns with the broader investigation of CE-related reporting practices, highlighting the critical role of stakeholder engagement in driving sustainability efforts

Moreover, the current study highlights that market orientation and stakeholder orientation share a common foundation. Management must adjust their policies to meet the demands of various stakeholders, not just a single stockholder. To mitigate the risk of power abuse, ST suggests that organisations should implement effective monitoring systems (Freeman et al., 2021) to maintain long-term, positive relationships with all stakeholders (Singh et al., 2022). This theory is particularly relevant to the current study, as companies adopting CE practices must recognise and disclose about employees' contributions and the collective efforts of numerous economic and social stakeholders. Integrating servitisation approaches with Industry 4.0 technologies plays a crucial role in successfully transitioning to CE, promoting the circular movement of materials and enhancing revenue efficiency (Raza et al., 2020). From the ST's perspective, transparency in sustainability reporting can be achieved only when businesses provide reliable assessments and credible data on their performance towards circularity (Simmou et al., 2022). Therefore, sustainability reports should disclose a comprehensive set of circularity indicators, detailing how the business has embedded CE strategies, integrated reverse-logistic services into organisational processes, managed waste-related impacts, and maintained transparency to keep all stakeholders informed.

3.3. Triangulation of Theories: Circular Product Development and their Reporting

The researcher employed a triangulation method using RBV, DCT, and ST to examine how sample manufacturing businesses from the Global Fortune 500 list integrate servitisation and I4.0 technologies into their CE reporting practices. RBV helps identify the strengths and capabilities that firms utilise for strategic advantage. DCT provides insights into how firms adapt and evolve their technical and digital capabilities for sustainable growth. ST emphasises the significance of addressing the concerns and needs of all stakeholders, ensuring that CE strategies are implemented responsibly and transparently. This theoretical triangulation enables a thorough analysis of the extent and impact of CE, I4.0, and servitisation disclosure practices, leading to a detailed understanding of how these elements contribute to sustainable business models and transparent reporting. Figure 3.1 illustrates the theoretical framework constructed by triangulation of theories and its connection with three phases of a circular product.

Figure 3. 1: Overview of Theoretical Framework

Figure 3.1 illustrates the major impact of strategy development and setting of an action plan using “Resource-based View (RBV)” and “Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCT)” to elaborate the implementation of CE principles through the lifecycle of a product. The CE disclosure index has been categorised into three phases i.e., Phase 1: Circular Design that includes R1: refuse, R2: rethink and R3: reduce; Phase 2: The responsible consumption and production includes R4: reuse, R5: repair, R6: refurbish, R7: remanufacture and R8: repurpose; Phase 3: Return of Used Product includes R9: recycle and R10: recover. The CE disclosure index is significant for the effective operationalisation of transformation towards circularity in the manufacturing industry.

CE-related reporting practices are crucial for presenting a business’s sustainability reporting and compliance where each stakeholder (investors, consumers, employees, and others) plays a vital role in implementation of CE initiatives. The stakeholders demand transparency and clarity in ESG reporting. Therefore, this section will also use “Stakeholder Theory (ST)” to support the strategic scope of resource management concerning the company's capacity and commitment (H3). This theory mainly focuses on how companies identify key stakeholders and align their value propositions and

expectations. Accordingly, the researcher advocates for transparency, emphasising that implementing servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategy requires stakeholder collaboration and transparency in CE-related reporting practices. Thus, the fourth hypothesis arise from a sophisticated integration of RBV, DCT and ST, highlighting the strategic, adaptive, and socially responsible dimensions of businesses moving towards circularity. This approach is expected to satisfy the stakeholders and significantly contribute to CEBM's reconfiguring in alignment with a sustainable development strategy.

3.4. Three Phases of Circular Product Cycle

3.4.1. Phase 1: Circular Design

The researcher employs the RBV to elaborate on the first phase of the 10R strategy of the CE, specifically focusing on the circular design phase. RBV emphasises that a firm's sustainable competitive advantage is derived from its unique resources and capabilities. By assessing various constructs of I4.0 and servitisation disclosure practices, the study investigates the extent and impact of circular design disclosures on implementing CE principles within business models. This includes examining how effectively firms utilise their resources to achieve circular productivity, which positively influences firm performance (Chuang & Lin, 2015) and integrates with both internal and external environments (Edh Mirzaei et al., 2021). In this phase, the RBV helps researchers understand how organisations can develop sustainable products and processes that efficiently use resources, minimise waste, and leverage their core competencies for sustainable growth.

3.4.2. Phase 2: Responsible Consumption and Production

Manufacturers are advised to leverage DCT to develop circular products, emphasising the need to cultivate efficient and intelligent processes. These processes should enhance their capacity to fulfil demand by effectively utilising post-manufacturing resources and minimising waste, thereby adding value through servitisation is advised (Bressanelli et al., 2018a). (Bressanelli et al., 2018a). The study explores how organisations integrate DCT principles, such as sensing, seizing, and transforming, into their operations to align with the CE paradigm and reporting practices. According to DCT, manufacturers are not just urged, but empowered to enhance their technical and digital capabilities through I4.0 technologies within the circular product consortium and implementing servitisation strategies. These sustainable technological advancements, encompassing product and service enhancements as well as infrastructure improvements, when integrated into strategic planning and operational frameworks, can significantly impact organisational outcomes, offering a new level of control and efficiency in manufacturing processes. The current study investigates the relationship between the "responsible consumption and production" phase of the 10R strategy of the CE and

different aspects of I4.0 and servitisation-related disclosure practices. It aims to understand an organisation's adaptive capacity to navigate evolving environmental and social dynamics in the context of responsible consumption and production. This includes formulating strategies to mitigate environmental impact and foster social responsibility that aligns with sustainable development and circularity goals.

3.4.3. Phase 3: Return of Used Product

This study will assess the effective controls related to the role of I4.0 technologies in the manufacturer's adoption of the servitisation BM in the shadow of environmental and economic perception from the lens of ST. The third phase of the CE 10R strategy called the “connected platform approach,” will investigate the changes brought in service providers' operations where resources are processed with sustainability, waste minimization and efficiency. This study will cover the initial production phase of designing circular products by utilizing I4.0 technologies to enhance optimal resource utilization. Until the stage of reverse logistics, the servitisation BM persuades the clients or end-users to return the used product to the manufacturer. This phase will promote incorporating the used/returned product in developing a circular product with high functionality at a reasonable cost. Finally, ST emphasises the importance of considering the concerns and requirements of all stakeholders, encompassing clients, staff, suppliers, and ecological aspects. In the servitisation phase, this theory can help organisations develop strategies for returning used products to the economy sustainably and responsibly.

3.5. Hypotheses Development

Formulating hypotheses appeared to be the best course of action for evaluating the research objectives of this study.

3.5.1. Servitisation as a CE Strategy

Adding service provision has been seen as a key enabler for enhancing the perceived value of circular products and smart-service packages. RBV considers a firm as an assortment or a bundle of diverse resources. Hence, manufacturers must identify their strengths and abilities of their resources to embrace servitisation, which helps them shape their strategy. Integrating servitisation allows companies to improve resource efficiency, prolong product lifecycles, and build stronger customer relationships (Paper et al., 2020). This strategic shift not only maximises the firm's tangible and intangible assets but also aligns with the principles of the circular economy. It involves deploying unique resources to support servitisation, that also enhance its competitive advantage and sustainability reporting, especially in CE disclosures. As rightly observed by Zahra (2021), allocating resources according to the VRIO framework helps businesses expand their market and sustain in a dynamic environment. Therefore, recently, firms have been more progressive in translating their resource strengths into competitive advancement through digitalisation (Dev, Shankar and Qaiser, 2020). A firm's management is responsible for setting a strategy that helps the firm sustain in the market while consolidating its growth and profitability. In contrast, the operational level ensures the development of a sustainable relationship with suppliers to promptly deliver goods and services at a reasonable production cost. Most studies establish that manufacturers must evaluate their resources to adopt CE principles with the servitisation BM. As a result, RBV is regarded as the most appropriate theoretical lens within the strategic management literature to support the current study's research agenda. RBV suggests that firms with strong resource bases are better equipped to adopt servitisation and enhance their ability to disclose CE-related information effectively. This improved disclosure satisfies regulatory, and stakeholder demands and reinforces the firm's commitment to sustainable practices and transparency, driving long-term competitive advantage. Based on the above discussion, the following hypothesis has been developed:

Hypothesis 1

- ***H1: The adoption of servitisation positively effects the level of CE disclosures.***

3.5.2. I4.0 as a CE Strategy

The dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCT) paved an expanded paradigm for RBV as a competitive strategy. Developing and delivering a circular product are considered major drivers for revolutionising companies' manufacturing. Rossi et al. (2020) suggested that developing innovative capabilities by applying I4.0 technologies to circular products will not only improve products quality but will help in real-time monitoring of the product life cycle and add agile responses to changing market condition. Moreover, Chari et al. (2022) suggested that manufacturers should experiment with innovative technologies to enhance their value proposition and gain a competitive edge in the market. At the same time, (Scarpellini et al., 2019) insist on adopting digitization to measure and quantify the circularity of designed and implemented initiatives that will help manufacturers identify improvement areas and further develop innovative capabilities. Thus, it won't be wrong to suggest that in the Fourth Industrial Revolution, technologies played a pivotal role in driving the transformation of conventional manufacturing companies. It will be feasible for the current study to assess the development of dynamic capabilities within a firm that would leverage this transition phase. Consequently, firms will be obliged to continually refresh their resource functionality and regularly change segments of the organisation, resulting in firms gaining a competitive advantage or new positions. Innovative processes and techniques can help eliminate non-value-added activities within the supply chain network. In addition, the advancement of technologies is amplifying the awareness about environmental and sustainability issues in the public, resulting in increased demand on social and ecological aspects of the products, such as decreased waste and energy consumption during the production (Govindan et al., 2018). Based on the discussion above, the following hypothesis has been put forth:

Hypothesis 2

- **H2: The adoption of I4.0 positively effects the level of CE disclosures.**

3.5.3. Digital Transformation: Developing Smart and Circular Product and Services

In the current study, a disclosure index is made to evaluate the standard reporting on selected firms from global fortune 500 listed companies' waste-related impact and how they manage servitisation and I4.0 technologies towards circularity. Therefore, this study aim to draw upon the view point of ST to illustrate the importance and influence of different stakeholders because this theory argues that the firm should generate value for all stakeholders not solely for shareholders (Gupta et al., 2019). Freeman et al. (2021) and Freeman & Dmytriyev (2020) assert that a firm's performance cannot be judged simply by shareholder wealth but must be assessed in light of the value provided to all stakeholders. The qualitative study by Baah et al. (2022) investigated the adoption of CE concepts, stakeholder satisfaction, and green legitimacy using the ST perspective. The results showed that satisfying stakeholders fosters loyalty, trust, and strong ties, leading to competitive advantages and enhanced value. Choudhary et al., (2022) emphasised the significance of senior management's environmental commitment to ensure that businesses are CE-compatible. Therefore, one of the key theoretical pillars of this research is to shed light on how manufacturing firms are adopting an I4.0-enabled platform approach to leverage circularity targets (resource efficiency and extending product lifecycles) with advanced reverse-logistic services. The results of this (servitisation and I4.0) integration seem aligned with the ST stance. Thus, the researcher wanted to assess their synergic effect, evaluating how they contribute to comprehensive reporting on ESG impacts in the CE disclosure index. Based on the following discussion, the following hypothesis has been formulated:

Hypothesis 3

- ***H3: The adoption of I4.0 technologies positively effects the level of servitisation in the disclosure practices, and vice versa.***

3.5.4. Trio-Combination of CE, Servitisation and I4.0

The overall perception of servitisation within the manufacturing sector has demonstrated a positive impact on revenue (Bressanelli et al., 2018a) aligns with the RBV principles. At the same time, firms are incentivised through government grants and funding to innovate circular products, resonating with DCT, emphasising a firm's ability to innovate and adapt to changes, making an organisation more attractive for investment (D'Agostin et al., 2020). Thus, it would not be incorrect to say that servitisation, influenced by incentives and I4.0 technologies, not only aligns with DCT but also reflects the firm's commitment to responsible consumption and production, a key principle of ST. I4.0 technologies aid in evaluating the firm's circularity readiness, associated risks, performance monitoring, and, most importantly, residual value stewardship. Therefore, understanding the profound impact of CE on business performance is of utmost importance. Previous research has primarily emphasised the economic advantages of CE (Prieto-Sandoval et al., 2019). For example, Schröder, Lemille and Desmond (2020a) introduced a three-tiered integrated design tool to facilitate a cohesive circular design approach. Additionally, Van Stijn and Gruis (2019) introduced a three-tiered integrated design tool aimed at facilitating a cohesive circular design approach. Additionally, Ünal et al. (2019) analysed managerial practices for CE using an Italian SME, suggesting the need for broader experimentation with the theory. Similarly, Tykkyläinen (2019) identified both challenges and prospects for social enterprises, concluding that firms consider organisational and financial performance as their main growth orientation. Notably, no empirical study has previously examined CE's innovative 10R strategy with a servitisation approach and I4.0 technologies. The transition towards circularity is believed to intensify the sharing platform culture by adopting the servitisation approach and connecting different stakeholders by leveraging the value of I4.0 technologies (Cenamor et al., 2017). Therefore, the researcher decided to explore this relationship (combining CE, servitisation and I4.0 constructs to detect CE reporting practices), the researcher conducted a content analysis to gather comprehensive statistics on the 10R strategy of CE, servitisation approach, and I4.0 disclosures from selected companies' sustainability reports, exemplifying a stakeholder-oriented approach to understanding the relationships between latent variables (CE, servitisation, I4.0 and CV). The fourth hypothesis stems from a nuanced integration of RBV, DCT, and ST perspectives, emphasising the strategic, dynamic, and socially responsible aspects of businesses transitioning towards circularity. Based on the above discussion, the following hypothesis has been formulated:

Hypothesis 4

- ***The combined adoption of servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies effects the level of CE reporting practices.***

3.5. Model Formulation

After careful consideration, the researcher has developed the following research model that presents a pictorial representation of the latent variables and the hypotheses development:

Figure 3. 2: Research Model

Source: Author's Creation

Figure 3.2 illustrates the research model developed by the researcher based on significant variables reviewed in Chapter 2: Literature Review. This model identifies CE as the primary dependent variable. Servitisation and I4.0 are designated as independent variables. H1 represents the first hypothesis: H1: The adoption of servitisation positively affects CE disclosures. H2 indicates H2: The adoption of I4.0 positively affects the level of CE disclosures. H3 represents the third hypothesis: H3: The adoption of I4.0 technologies positively affects the level of servitisation in disclosure practices, and vice versa. Finally, H4 indicates the fourth hypothesis: H4: The combined adoption of servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies affects the level of CE reporting practices. Furthermore, the study incorporates five control variables to manage the transition from LEBM to CEBM, reflected in a firm's reporting practices. The researcher conducted assessments of various features of CE (these are used as CV in the current study), identified circular value propositions, and evaluated circular supply chain management (SCM). Additionally, the study examined investments in eco-design as growth catalysts and an assessment of statements on sustainable development strategies to understand their influence on transitioning towards circular practices.

3.6. Chapter Summary

This chapter employs a triangulation technique to elucidate the theoretical framework of the current study by integrating RBV, DCT, and ST to explore CE implementation and reporting practices. RBV guides examining the first phase of circular product development, i.e., circular design, linking it to hypothesis H1. This theory and H1 propose that firms with robust resource bases are better positioned to adopt servitisation and effectively disclose CE-related information to gain competitive advantage. DCT is pivotal in the second hypothesis (H2), addressing the second phase of circular product development i.e., responsible consumption and production. It highlights the role of I4.0 technologies in driving the transformation of smart manufacturing. DCT emphasises the development of dynamic capabilities within firms to leverage these advancements, enhancing resource efficiency and promoting competitive advantage through innovative processes and reduced environmental impact. ST underpins the third hypothesis (H3) concerning the third phase of circular product development, i.e., the return of used products where manufacturing firms adopt I4.0-enabled platforms to optimise circularity goals. This theory highlights the crucial role of stakeholder engagement and comprehensive reporting on ESG impacts in CE disclosure indices. The fourth hypothesis (H4) merges CE, servitisation, and I4.0 concepts throughout the circular product development. This hypothesis reflects on stakeholder-oriented viewpoint by exploring businesses' strategic, dynamic, and socially responsible aspects as they transition to circular practices and their reporting practices in the CE context.

Chapter 4: Methodology

4.1. Introduction of the Chapter

In this chapter, the research methodology used in the current study is outlined in Figure 4.1, illustrating the processes, procedures, and techniques employed to achieve the research objectives (RO1-RO4). The current study has utilised the sub-layers of the "research onion", presented by Saunders et al. (2019) to comprehend the rationale behind the methodological selections. The chapter is divided into seven sections, each representing a layer of the "research onion": Section (2) explains the adopted research philosophy; Section (3) describes the research approach; Section (4) outlines the research methods; Section (5) discusses the research strategy and Section (6) summarizes the data collection and analysis procedures followed in the current study.

Figure 4 1: Overview of Research Design

4.2. Research Philosophy: Positivism

According to Saunders et al. (2019), a research philosophy is a collection of ideas and assumptions regarding the acquisition of knowledge. It is the insight of the paradigm from researcher's perspective (Collis and Hussey, 2003). It is based on set on beliefs or assumptions about human knowledge that articulates the researcher's viewpoint about a particular topic (Saunders et al., 2019). According to the research onion, here are five sub-categories of a research philosophy which includes Pragmatism,

post-modernism, inter-pretivism, critical realism and positivism. Each of these philosophies offers a unique perspective for understanding and developing a phenomenon.

The positivism philosophy refers to the existence of the outer world. It conducts an analysis founded on the positive stance that can be quantified through scientific means like testing and observation that eventually accentuates the formulation of a constructive conclusion (Saunders et al., 2019). A positivist thinks that human knowledge is gained via observation of real-life circumstances and analysis of causal relationships between statistics generated from theories or law (James & Patterson, 2013). Thus, the positivism philosophy seems to be the most appropriate philosophy for the current study where a self-constructed disclosure index is being used to investigate the extent of CE, I4.0 and servitisation disclosure practices in selected companies from fortune global 500 list.

The researcher initiated the following research on positivism stance by formulating hypotheses (H1 to H4) to test the relationship between the latent variables (CE, servitisation and I4.0 technologies) based on quantifiable facts. The manual content analysis led the author to understand the prevailing realities regarding the CE transition of selected companies and the role of I4.0 and servitisation as an enabler towards circularity. It ensures a non-bias, credible and convincing conclusion on the relationship between various constructs of CE, I4.0, and servitisation disclosure from the perspective of the Global Fortune 500 listed companies.

4.3. Research Approaches: Deductive

Different scholars adopt a different research approach as a path that leads them to study or examine a phenomenon. Hence, this difference in perception compels them to choose a path. For example, the concept of “A paradigm” can be rummaged from different viewpoints that characterise different meanings (Melnikovas, 2018). For this reason, the researcher needs to decide which research approach would be suitable for the current study. There are three types of research approaches, inductive, abductive and deductive approach. The abductive method enables the use of vision and perception to steer theoretical development and comprehend both the fundamental and specialised aspects of observable phenomena (Saunders et al., 2019). Inductive approach on the contrary is built on the analysis of data and forming theories and hypothesis based on the observation and patterns noted in the data (Bryman and Bell, 2015). On the other hand, deductive approach is a scientific principle that relies on testing a theory by analysing the collected data. This is an exceedingly structured method that is most suitable where the relationship between variables is scrutinised.

A positivism approach is selected to investigate the organisational arrangements as this study aims to grasp the universally applicable truth about CE transition and the support provided by I4.0 and servitisation. The researcher has then tested the existing relevant theories (RBV, DCT and ST) on

business strategies. This process is carried out in few steps. First, by collecting the applicable data from large samples of an appropriate size (100 companies from the fortune global 500 list). In this step the researcher carried out a manual content analysis with the help of self-constructed disclosure index. In the final step the data was analysed to conclude the validity of the chosen theory and testing the hypothesis. In the current study, the researcher has used the deductive research approach and formulated hypotheses (H1-H4) from the literature review to achieve the research objectives (RO1-RO4). The hypothesis were then subjected to experimental testing to provide reliable answers to the research questions RQ1-4. This testing involved investigating the presence of any relationship between servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies by assessing CE-related disclosure practices.

4.4. Research Method: Quantitative

Data is not knowledge, instead the differences between research methodologies are founded on a philosophical and theoretical vision of research that leads social science researchers in their work (Saunders et al., 2019). There are three types of methodological choices, i.e., quantitative, qualitative and mixed (combination of quantitative and qualitative method) method. The following thesis investigates the extent of CE disclosure elements of 10R strategy from selected companies's websites and sustainability/annual reports using quantitative method. Particularly, this study sought to measure the aid of I4.0-enables shared platform to leverage the servitisation approach in fortune global 500 companies over the study period. As previously established in chapter 2: Literature review, the impact of implementation of CE is not readily quantifiable in the short-term basis whereas it leaves a strong influence on firm's performance in the long-term. For this reason, the researcher has adopted a quantitative approach and collected the data from the selected manufacturing companies sustainability reports over a five-year period. The researcher then conducted manual content analysis on this data through a self-constructed disclosure index to measure the extent of various constructs of CE, I4.0 and servitisation disclosures. The data is further assessed with the help of statistical software i.e., SPSS software (IBM SPSS Statistics 29.0) and Smart PLS. Quantitative method is considered as traditional and positivist, experimental paradigm, that can be subjected to non-parametric or predictable statistical capacity inspection (Al-Ababneh, 2020). As this study is constructed on positivism philosophy and relies on logical validations only, so quantitative research method seems the most appropriate research method. It helped the researcher to measure the extent of social phenomena of 10R strategy of CE in relation with I4.0 and servitisation disclosures practices through quantifiable data extracted from sustainability reports of selected companies from Global Fortune 500 list.

4.5. Research Strategy: Case Study

A research strategy is simply a predetermined plan for achieving the research goals and each researcher devises a plan before conducting research (Saunders et al., 2019). The researcher has selected to conduct a case study research to gather a clear and holistic insight into a CE's contemporary phenomenon through the collected data. Research strategy can use either a single case study or a multi-case study approach (E. Zheng et al., 2022), but the main concern is to select a case or cases from a particular industry or sector.

A case study is useful as an exploratory tool as it unveils real-life situations, problems or issues. However, it is a time-consuming research process involving various methods. Therefore, the researcher has selected this research strategy to conduct the current study because it is considered rigorous and inflexible (Al-Ababneh, 2020). There is a high chance that a single case study represents a single perspective or opinion at a particular moment that cannot be verified over time with different settings. Hence, there are chances of misrepresentation and risk of misinterpretation. Therefore, the researcher uses a case study strategy for conducting manual content analysis using a self-constructed disclosure index to observe the implementation of the 10R strategy of CE disclosure practices in the sample. Moreover, the case study will also investigate the impact of CE concerning various constructs of I4.0 disclosure practices and various constructs of servitisation disclosure practices among the selected companies from the fortune global 500 list accumulating to 500 observations in totality.

4.6. Time Horizon: Longitudinal

According to time horizon, there are two types of research, i.e., the cross-sectional study and longitudinal study. The cross-sectional study helps a researcher to observe data collected at a single point of time where instead of manipulating variables to test for correlation, researchers just find and record information that already exists. Adopting CE is a paradigm is evolving over time so understanding how practices change can provide valuable insights. A longitudinal study on the other hand helps a researcher to identify strategy trends, challenges, and improvements over an extended period. The researcher has therefore selected longitudinal study to examine the extent of CE disclosure practice over a five-year period. The longitudinal study allows the businesses to monitor and record their progress towards sustainability by keeping track of changes, modifications, and challenges and whether implementation of servitisation and I4.0 can be effective strategies for achieving this goal. The current study is conducted to investigate the relationship of 10R-strategy of CE disclosure practices with various constructs of I4.0 and servitisation disclosure practices. Therefore, the selection of longitudinal study is considered to be the best approach to evaluate the extent of 10R-strategy of CE, I4.0 and servitisation disclosure practices and investigate the impact of the transition

towards circularity ***over a 5-year period span, i.e., 2018-2022 cumulating to a total of five hundred observations***. Many of the earlier studies have employed cross-sectional research collecting the data in a single year (Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020; Opferkuch et al., 2022; Scarpellini et al., 2019; Sihvonen & Partanen, 2017; Zheng et al., 2022); or observations conducted on alternative years (2012, 2014, 2016 and 2018) for a period of four-years' time (Roberts et al., 2022); or observations for three-years (2013-15) (Yang et al., 2019). Thus, the longitudinal research seems suitable for this aspect as well as it allows the researcher to construct and evaluate a timeline about transition of selected sample towards circularity and to situate the I4.0 and servitisation disclosure practices through a comparative lens. Therefore, the researcher plan to gather the data where the companies must have published their website and sustainability/annual reports in English language for the period of 2018-2022. English is a commonly used language for business communications. This makes comparing and analysing data across companies from different regions easier.

4.7. Data Collection and Technique

The researcher conducted a comprehensive literature review of previous studies to ensure that the developed CE disclosure index is robust and is based on a solid groundwork of knowledge and insights. This is critical because it provides the framework for addressing real-world issues and capitalising on business prospects (Saunders et al., 2019). The elements of data collection and techniques are mentioned in the subsections below.

4.7.1. The Content Analysis

According to Krippendorff (1980), the qualitative statements from sustainability reports are best analysed through content analysis systematically by coding and describing them using quantitative measures. Quantifying qualitative data for research is a well-established practice furnishing a comprehensive understanding of the qualitative statements. Few prior studies have used surveys (Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020) and case studies (Opferkuch et al., 2022; Zheng et al., 2022) to evaluate the disclosure practices. However, company websites, annual reports and sustainability reports seems the most reliable and suitable source of documents that are widely used within disclosure related studies (Sihvonen & Partanen, 2017; Scarpellini et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2019; Roberts et al., 2022). Hence, during the second phase, the researcher has conducted a manual content analysis using a self-constructed disclosure index collecting the quantifiable data from selected company's websites and their sustainability/annual reports. Content analysis has been significantly used as it is the methodology that has been mostly adopted in CE-disclosure-related literature (Bogdan et al., 2022; Roberts, Georgiou, et al., 2022; Zheng et al., 2022). However, most of the previous studies have used

data extracted from large financial databases such as Bloomberg data base (Doni et al., 2019; Raimo et al., 2022); Thomson Reuters Institutional Holdings(s34) database (Cao et al., 2021); Eikon database (Al-Shaer et al., 2022); NRDS database, Shanghai and Shenzhen stock exchange (Yang et al., 2019); GRI Database (Dagiliene et al., 2020; Roberts, Georgiou, et al., 2022). However, the researcher considers that using these large financial databases may not comprehensively represent the full impact of CE-related initiatives and policies in the companies. As a result, the findings and conclusions drawn from these studies may need to fully capture the extent and nuances of the effects of CE practices on various ESG outcomes. Thus, the researcher of the current study followed an approach practised by Hassan et al. (2020) and conducted a manual content analysis to maintain the data's robustness, reliability, and validity.

4.7.2. Definition of Variables

In the current study, a theoretical framework was developed, consisting of structural variables (“I4.0 and servitisation as independent variables”; “10R-strategy of CE as dependent variable” and “circular business model, SCM, circular value proposition, investment of eco-design and Statement on sustainable development strategy” as Control variables” of observed data. To bridge this gap, the current study endeavours to comprehensively understand each construct of the latent variables (CE, servitisation, and I4.0) by offering detailed definitions and elucidating the measurement metrics associated with each construct. The definition of variables are as follows:

4.7.2.1. Dependent Variable: CE

In the current study, the dependent variable is CE, and the researcher will explore the adoption and implementation of practices within the sample. This variable aims to measure the degree to which companies promote sustainable production and responsible consumption, which ultimately leads to a more sustainable use of resources. The dependent variable CE is used to explore the extent of emphasis in the sample companies on reducing waste and promoting the efficient usage of resources by adopting a CLSC within their business model. The CE practices listed include circular design, reuse, mend, rejuvenate, reconstruct, adapt, salvage and recycle. Therefore, the dependent variable CE would measure the extent to which companies adopt and implement the CE practices in their business model. This measurement of CE practises will be conducted through various metrics such as the amount of waste diverted from disposal, the percentage of products designed for circularity, or the number of recycled materials used in production.

4.7.2.2. Independent Variable: Servitisation and I4.0

The current study has developed a CE disclosure index comprising two independent variables: servitisation (SER11-SER14 as constructs of servitisation) and I4.0 (IND15- IND21 as constructs of I4.0). A brief description for each construct of the independent variable is provided below:

Doni et al. (2019) suggests that *servitisation* allows businesses to diversify their revenue streams and reduce their dependence on circular product sales. In their research, Doni et al. (2019) examine companies' ESG communication related to servitisation, highlighting the need for a thorough analysis of the infusion of services. Thus, the researcher evaluates if sample companies are reporting the integration of servitisation with their product consortium this will facilitate the return of used constructs for recycling or reuse (SER11). Scarpellini et al. (2020) highlight the role of waste recovery in managing CEBM and improving environmental disclosure, prompting an assessment of companies' recycling practices (SER12). This issue can also be addressed by integrating servitisation with CE, as it assists in the dematerialisation process and the use of recycled materials to develop a circular product and improve environmental strategy (Scarpellini et al., 2020). This integrating of servitisation with CE makes reporting on recycled materials and dematerialisation suitable for CE disclosure (SER13). Mirzaei & Shokouhyar (2022) Moreover, Mirzaei and Shokouhyar (2022) advocate for the incorporation of CEBM to maximise resource value, motivating an assessment of companies' end-of-life practices through reuse platforms (SER14).

As for *I4.0 constructs*, the researcher evaluated I4.0 disclosure practices across seven constructs (IND15-21), drawing from studies by Cenamor et al. (2017); D'Amato et al. (2019) and Scarpellini et al. (2020). Cenamor et al. (2017) advocate for a platform approach to achieve circular economy (CE) through digitalisation, prompting the evaluation of firms employing low-cost data-driven management systems (IND15). They also emphasise the importance of I4.0-enabled shared platforms (IND16) and data-driven platforms (IND17) as key to leveraging the CE paradigm. This approach extends a product's lifecycle, guiding the assessment of firms' efforts in creating eco-friendly products (IND19). Additionally, Scarpellini et al. (2020) stress the significance of eco-innovation and CE objectives, which inform evaluations of firms' eco-innovation practices (IND20). Lastly, D'Amato et al. (2019) highlight the importance of firms' environmental compliance efforts (IND21).

4.7.2.3. Control Variable

The study's outcome depends on the CE, which is the dependent variable. The independent variables include Servitisation and I4.0, while various features of the firm's performance are classified as the control variable. The study includes five essential control variables (CBM22, SCM23, CVP24, IED25 and SDS26) that act as steering features to accelerate the transition towards circularity in businesses. The first control variable focuses on reconfiguring the business model, known as the Circular Business

Model (CBM22). This variable is tailored to support circular economy efforts and has generated significant interest in sustainable business models such as rental, sharing, and sufficiency models (Opferkuch et al., 2022). The second control variable emphasises adapting a robust supply chain management to support circular practices, referred to as Supply Chain Management (SCM23) (Doni et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2019). The third control variable assesses the circular value proposition (CVP24) to determine if the circular product's quality and accessibility align with its durability and affordability (Yang et al., 2019). The fourth control variable evaluates resource availability, including investments in eco-design (IED25) (Bogdan et al., 2022). Finally, the fifth control variable encourages companies to shift their mission and vision towards sustainable development, known as the Statement on Sustainable Development Strategy (SDS26) (GRI, 2021).

4.7.3. Sample Selection

The study analysed 100 manufacturing companies from the Global Fortune 500 list, adapting a very similar approach as the studies from Roberts et al. (2022). The criteria for selecting the sample companies for the current study is mentioned in detail below:

Source of Data: The company must be included in the Fortune Global 500 companies list that is compiled and published in 2021 by Fortune magazine [Global 500 | Fortune](#). The reason for using the companies from this list as a sample is that they are the large size and most influential companies globally. (M. P. Singh et al., 2021) also suggested that for a comparative study the companies operating in large sectors and various industries should be selected. These companies have a significant global impact and extensive resources, which enable them to implement and report on their CE transformation including their sustainability initiatives and ESG impacts. By studying these companies, the researcher gets a sample from a diverse representation of industries and an opportunity to examine their corporate sustainability practices.

Industry/Sector Wise: The company must be a *manufacturing company* and have data on CE and firm-specific variables in reported in their website and sustainability/annual reports. Due to their sustainability challenges and the need for resource efficiency, manufacturing companies are an interesting area for exploring the use of servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies. Therefore, the authors of this study decided to focus on these companies because they are often engage in resource-intensive activities, making their CE practices particularly relevant for this study specifically their material flows and waste reduction practices. Additionally, manufacturing companies provide detailed and specific data on their production processes and sustainability initiatives, which enables the researcher for a

thorough analysis of their CE practices. Companies operating in various sectors of manufacturing industries have diverse operations, resource usage, and environmental impact, which vary significantly. Therefore, the researchers believe that conducting industry-wide analysis can provide valuable insights into the distinct challenges and opportunities specific to different sectors. This study analyses how different sectors use servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies. This allows for targeted recommendations and tailored CE strategies to be formulated. Thus, after careful consideration, the author finalised a list of 100 manufacturing companies operating in manufacturing sector from the fortune global 500 list.

4.7.4. Data Collection

The researcher used the online search engine Google to collect sustainability reports for content analysis. The search process involved entering keywords such as [company name], [Year], and [sustainability report/annual report]. When sustainability reports were found, they were saved in separate folders for each Year from 2018 to 2022. If sustainability reports were unavailable for a particular company or Year, “sustainability report” was replaced with “Integrated report.” Although not many companies publish integrated reports, their inclusion would have been advantageous as these reports typically address climate issues and monetary values with specific scoring. Combining these methodologies provides a comprehensive approach to data collection, allowing researchers to gain a deeper understanding of the research subject and identify the underlying causes and effects. Each report was meticulously reviewed to identify CE disclosures, specifically focusing on whether the companies reported utilising servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies.

4.7.5. Data Analysis: SPSS and SmartPLS

The researcher used two statistical software for data analysis. Initially SPSS version 26.0 was used to evaluate the reliability and validity tests. A descriptive analysis was carried using SPSS to assess CE disclosures in the data extracted from the sustainability reports. This was done by examining the utilisation of the reverse-logistics perspective within servitisation and the I4.0-enabled perspective as integral components of CE strategy. The extent and frequencies of CE, servitisation, I4.0 and CV were also explored from the data through SPSS that revealed the preliminary links between the latent variables. Later Smart PLS-SEM software was used for structural Equation Modelling (SEM) analysis. The rationale for selecting PLS-SEM over SPSS for SEM analysis for this analysis is mentioned below.

Suitable for Complex Models: The researcher found that three latent variables, Servitisation, I4.0, and CV, do not follow a normal distribution pattern. Despite trying various transformations in SPSS, the

researcher was unable to standardize or normalize these datasets. For this reason, the researcher has decided to use Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) as it is a more flexible statistical technique that can handle non-normal data (Palmer, 2008). To achieve this, a multivariate transformation was performed based on the "central limit theorem" which states that as the sample size increases, the distribution of sample means tends to become normal, regardless of the population distribution from which the samples are drawn (Hair et al., 2014).

Focus on Prediction and Exploratory Analysis: According to Schreiber (2008), SEM is suitable for studies that simultaneously assess the causal relationships between one or more predictor variables and one or more outcome variables. The decision to employ PLS-SEM aligns well with the objectives and structure of the current study. Given the complexity of the model, which involves multiple variables, a dependent variable (CER comprising of ten constructs), two independent variables (SER with four constructs and IND with seven constructs) and a control variable (comprising five constructs), PLS-SEM is suitable for analysing the relationships among multiple variables (Raza et al., 2020). Additionally, PLS-SEM is adept at handling predictive studies that identify causal relationships, making it a fitting choice for the current research. With twenty-six constructs distributed across the variables, PLS-SEM can effectively capture the relationships within the sample data.

4.8. Chapter Summary

This chapter outlines the research methodology, detailing the selection of a positivist philosophy, a deductive approach, and quantitative research methods to establish a robust foundation for the current study. The primary aim is to investigate the extent of CE, servitisation and I4.0 disclosure practices among selected Global Fortune 500 companies. By adopting a positivist approach, the researcher utilised a logical validation of quantitative data to effectively measure ESG phenomena related to the 10R strategy of CE alongside I4.0 and servitisation disclosures. The methodology included a three-step analysis. The first step involved developing the CE disclosure index and defining scoring criteria to assess the presence and practical implications of the constructs. The second step entailed a thorough content analysis to determine the extent and frequency of reporting practices. A pilot study⁸ was conducted to ensure consistency in scoring. The data analysis was conducted using SPSS and SmartPLS as part of the third step. SPSS was initially used to check the reliability and validity of the datasets and to conduct descriptive analysis to assess CE disclosure. Subsequently, SmartPLS was utilised to analyse the statistical model.

⁸ Please find details about pilot study in Appendix 6: Pilot Study.

Chapter 5: Findings and Discussion

5.1. Introduction of the Chapter

This chapter demonstrates the findings and discussion of the current study. This section is designed as follows: section (2) presents the model overview, outlining the measurement and statistical model specifications; section (3) explains the data screen and cleaning procedure; section (4 and 5) includes a detailed analysis of depth of disclosure practices of the latent variables (CE, servitisation, I4.0 and CV) conducted to achieve answers for RQ2 and RQ3: for example section (4) illustrates the extent, trends and frequency distribution of the reporting practices of the latent variables; section (5) presents the descriptive analysis, interpreting how sample companies utilise servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies and use CV in controlling these CE transitions; section (6 and 7) presents the results for reliability and validity tests; section (8- 11) presents the outlier, normality, factor analysis and goodness of fit tests; section (12 and 13) aims to achieve answers for RQ4 by uncovering the findings from the statistical analysis, for example: section (12) demonstrate the results and interpretation for statistical results of main model and section (13) illustrates the statistical results and interpretation for robust models.

5.2. Model Overview

The model overview visually represents the study's framework, outlining the statistical and measurement models utilised. This section explains how data was collected and analysed in the current study.

Figure 5. 1: Overview of Measurement and Statistical Model

Source: Author's Creation

The structure of Chapter 5: Findings and Discussion is illustrated in Figure 5.1. It provides a comprehensive discussion on the relationships between the latent variables (CE, servitisation, I4.0, and CV) and their corresponding observed indicators (CER1-CER10 for CE; SER11-SER14 for servitisation; IND15-IND21 for I4.0, and CBM22, SCM23, CVP24, IED25, and SDS26 for CV). The red box highlighted in Figure 5.1 displays the results of the measurement analysis of the outer model. This analysis includes outlier detection, collinearity tests, normality tests, reliability tests, and validity tests. The measurement model has helped the researcher understand the dataset's characteristics, identify any issues requiring attention, and make informed decisions about the appropriate statistical techniques for further analysis. Additionally, the green highlighted box in Figure 5.1 presents the findings of the structural analysis, which tests the correlation of latent variables through hypotheses. The main objective of this section is to accomplish RO4, which aims to analyse the impact of disclosure practices incorporating servitisation and I4.0 as a CE strategy within the sustainability reports of the sample. The results will help to determine the effects and transition practices related to this

combination. Ultimately, this section will answer RQ4: What are the implications of incorporating servitisation and I4.0 into CE reporting practices, and how do these integrations impact the transparency, accountability, and overall sustainability performance of Global Fortune 500 companies.

5.3. Data Screening and Cleaning

The first step in data screening is preparation of the data for subsequent analysis. The researcher has therefore prepared an excel sheet which is essential for converting raw data into a meaningful form for the screening. Once the data has been organised into workable order, a content analysis was carried out to determine the thoroughness of latent variables and its constructs, such as CE as the dependent variable, servitisation and I4.0 as independent variables, and control variables. For the content analysis, initially the subsets of each latent variable were constructed i.e., ten constructs in CE, four constructs in servitisation, seven constructs in I4.0, and five constructs as control variables, reflecting the CE disclosure index's domain. As the missing data can significantly impact the research goals and objectives (Hodges et al., 2023), so it is essential to check for this issue. Thus, before data cleaning, all 500 observations were reviewed for missing data to confirm the accuracy of the data. According to Jobst et al. (2022), up to 5% of missing data is allowed. The statistical software SPSS (V.26.0) was used for this purpose. It was found that all missing data was randomly distributed and fell below the 5% threshold. The researcher then analysed the sustainability reports where data was missing and made the necessary rectification in the data sheet. As a result, the final data set includes all the data without any missing values.

5.4. The Extent and Trend in Disclosure Practices

A comprehensive assessment of the extent, trends, and frequency distribution of CE reporting practices in Global Fortune 500 companies provides a valuable insight into the transparency and accountability of disclosures related to CE, Servitisation, I4.0, and CV in these companies. The researcher has therefore conducted an analysis using four levels of data profiling: Level 1: The overall extent of CE, Servitisation, I4.0, and CV; Level 2: The overall frequency distribution of CE, Servitisation, I4.0, and CV; Level 3: The frequency distribution of CE, Servitisation, I4.0, and CV disclosures by scores; Level 4: The annual frequency distribution of CE, Servitisation, I4.0, and CV disclosures.

5.4.1. Level 1: Extent of CE, Servitisation, I4.0 and CV Disclosures for 5 Year

This section presents a comprehensive analysis of the extent to which Global Fortune 500 companies have disclosed information related to latent variables in level 1 i.e., CE, Servitisation, I4.0, and CV over the past five years, which are as follows:

Table 5. 1: The Extent and Trends of Latent Variable's Disclosure Practices for Each Year

Variable	Year	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. d.
CE	2018	100	3	30	15.17	5.562
	2019	100	4	30	15.94	5.429
	2020	100	3	30	16.86	6.013
	2021	100	2	30	18.35	5.377
	2022	100	3	30	18.38	5.545
SER	2018	100	1	12	9.01	3.503
	2019	100	1	12	9.35	3.301
	2020	100	1	12	9.54	3.242
	2021	100	1	12	10.05	3.020
	2022	100	0	12	9.99	3.053
I4.0	2018	100	2	21	15.91	4.311
	2019	100	2	21	16.77	3.871
	2020	100	8	21	17.08	3.498
	2021	100	4	21	18.05	3.245
	2022	100	8	21	18.36	3.109
CV	2018	100	2	15	9.75	3.341
	2019	100	2	15	10.14	3.499
	2020	100	2	15	10.95	3.151
	2021	100	3	15	11.58	2.938
	2022	100	3	15	11.57	3.082

Where CE=circular economy, SER= servitisation, I4.0= industry 4.0 and CV= control variables.

Table 5.1 provides a summary of the extent and trends of the main variables i.e., CE, servitisation, I4.0 and CV over a five-year period (2018 to 2022), encompassing 100 observations per year for each variable, resulting in a cumulative total of 500 observations. The findings reveal a general upward trend in the variable **CE** disclosure practices over time. Overall, the table indicates that the mean value of the 10R strategies of CE has increased over the years, with relatively minimal variability around the mean, as reflected by the standard deviation. These findings suggest a positive trend towards an overall increase in disclosures related to CE strategies. These findings align with the conclusions of Barreiro-Gen & Lozano (2020) and Opferkuch et al. (2022). However, they contradict the assertions of Gunarathne et al. (2021) and Dagiliene et al. (2020), who claimed that environmental management actions do not directly integrate CE principles and that CE disclosures are generally low.

Moreover, the mean value of variables **servitisation, I4.0 and CV** in the table demonstrates a gradual increase with the Std values. These results indicate a growing trend in total servitisation constructs as well as total I4.0 constructs disclosed in the context of the CE, showing that servitisation is being used as a CE strategy over the five years analysed. This trend indicates that these companies are committed to embracing servitisation as a viable business model within their sustainability reports. This may be

linked to servitisation acting as a catalyst for organisations to adopt more transparent and responsible CE-related disclosure practices. This also implies that the companies under study use the variables servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies for leveraging strategic economic goals, social benefits, and innovative environmental objectives. Disclosing CE implementation ensures that all stakeholders' interests are considered. This is consistent with ST, which suggests that organisations are driven to adopt different frameworks to create value for all stakeholders. Additionally, these results reinforce the proposition by Chen et al. (2022) that the quality of environmental cost disclosure requires enhancement.

5.4.2. Level 2: Frequency distribution of CE, Servitisation, I4.0 and CV Disclosures by Scores for Each Year

Table 5.2 presents the frequency distribution of CE disclosures by scores reported by the sample selected from Global Fortune 500 companies. This analysis provides insights into the trends and patterns of the CE initiatives related to servitisation, I4.0, CV, which are as follows:

Table 5. 2: The Frequency distribution of Latent Variable's Disclosures by Score for Each Year

Construct	Year	0	1	2	3	Total
CE	2018	409	72	112	407	1517
	2019	409	45	89	457	1594
	2020	374	49	94	483	1686
	2021	326	46	95	533	1835
	2022	326	43	98	533	1838
SER	2018	63	25	60	252	901
	2019	49	26	66	259	935
	2020	47	23	59	271	954
	2021	33	20	56	291	1005
	2022	38	19	49	294	999
I4.0	2018	68	67	171	394	1591
	2019	48	63	153	436	1677
	2020	39	46	183	432	1708
	2021	29	28	152	491	1805
	2022	22	26	146	506	1836
CV	2018	112	41	107	240	975
	2019	106	34	100	260	1014
	2020	79	35	98	288	1095
	2021	69	33	69	329	1158
	2022	74	24	73	329	1157

Where CE=circular economy, SER= servitisation, I4.0= industry 4.0 and CV= control variables.

Over the five-year period, there has been a noticeable upward trend in companies disclosing information about the CE initiatives, particularly concerning the 10R strategies, as well as the use of servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies, and related CV. The findings in the table are consistent with the findings of Barreiro-Gen & Lozano (2020) and Opferkuch et al. (2022). However, they contrast with the conclusions of Gunarathne et al. (2021) and Dagiliene et al. (2020), who asserted that environmental management actions do not directly incorporate CE principles and that **CE disclosures** remain low. Moreover, there has been a noticeable increase in **servitisation, I4.0 and CV disclosure levels** over the years. However, the proportion of companies achieving verifiable servitisation disclosures (categories 2 and 3) is lower than the 10R strategies of CE reporting practices. Similarly, there has been a general trend towards increased disclosure for I4.0 initiatives and CV over the years. However, these trends are less pronounced than in 10R strategies of CE reporting practices over the past five years. These findings reveal a mixed outcome for companies' commitment to sustainability and innovation, promoting accountability in their operations. As Gupta et al. (2021) suggested, businesses must encourage innovation while reducing their environmental footprint. The findings in the table support Chen et al.'s (2022) recommendation that the content of ecological cost disclosure needs improvement. Thus, in light of the findings presented in the table, the researcher of the current study has observed that CE related reporting practices are currently becoming popular trend in sustainability reports across manufacturing sector. Which emphasises the significance of adopting a long-term, holistic approach to business operations that considers corporate activities' ESG impacts (Yu et al., 2022).

5.4.3. Level 3: Frequency distribution of Constructs of CE, Servitisation, I4.0 and CV Disclosures by Constructs for 5 Years

The frequency distribution of each construct of the CE disclosure index can provide valuable insights into how sample companies selected from Global Fortune 500 list are addressing various aspects of 10R strategies of CE, reverse logistics stance of servitisation, smart manufacturing perspective of I4.0, and CV which comprises of CE features. The frequency distribution of Constructs of CE, servitisation, I4.0 and CV disclosures by Constructs from the selected companies over a 5-year period is provided in the table below:

Table 5. 3: The Frequency distribution of Latent Variable's Disclosure by Constructs for 5 Years

Constructs	Score 0		Score 1		Score 2		Score 3		Total	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
CER1	104	21%	35	7%	72	14%	289	58%		
CER2	306	61%	37	7%	52	10%	105	21%		
CER3	3	1%	11	2%	54	11%	432	86%		
CER4	63	13%	20	4%	64	13%	353	71%		
CER5	150	30%	46	9%	103	21%	201	40%		
CER6	379	76%	25	5%	24	5%	72	14%		
CER7	415	83%	13	3%	11	2%	61	12%		
CER8	312	62%	32	6%	35	7%	121	24%		
CER9	20	4%	12	2%	18	4%	450	90%		
CER10	92	18%	24	5%	55	11%	329	66%	8470	100%
SER11	7	1%	33	7%	72	14%	388	78%		
SER12	53	11%	19	4%	68	14%	360	72%		
SER13	77	15%	37	7%	77	15%	309	62%		
SER14	93	19%	24	5%	73	15%	310	62%	4794	100%
IND15	17	3%	55	11%	193	39%	235	47%		
IND16	24	5%	18	4%	74	15%	384	77%		
IND17	36	7%	33	7%	97	19%	334	67%		
IND18	84	17%	61	12%	146	29%	209	42%		
IND19	21	4%	23	5%	106	21%	350	70%		
IND20	10	2%	17	3%	75	15%	398	80%		
IND21	14	3%	23	5%	114	23%	349	70%	8617	100%
CBM22	140	28%	45	9%	49	10%	266	53%		
SCM23	15	3%	13	3%	114	23%	358	72%		
CVP24	12	2%	26	5%	200	40%	262	52%		
IED25	215	43%	56	11%	62	12%	167	33%		
SDS26	58	12%	27	5%	22	4%	393	79%	5399	100%

Where CER1=refuse; CER2= rethink; CER3= reduce; CER4= reuse; CER5= repair; CER6= refurbish; CER7= remanufacture; CER8= repurpose; CER9= recycle; CER10= recover; SER11= servitisation as a CE strategy; SER12= waste recovery for servitisation; SER13= minimise usage of virgin material, SER14= end-of-life practices/ reverse logistics; IND15= transparency and accountability; IND16=I4.0-enabled shared platform; IND17= Resource Efficiency IND18= extended lifecycle; IND19= functional efficacy; IND20= innovation through I4.0; IND21= monitoring resource Use; CBM22= circular business model; SCM23= supply chain management: reverse activities/logistics; CVP24= circular value proposition; IED25= investment of Eco-design; SDS26= statement on sustainable development strategy.

Table 5.3 provides a breakdown of frequency distribution of scores (Score 0 to Score 3) for each construct of 10R strategies of CE (CER1 to CER10), servitisation constructs (SER11- SER14), I4.0 constructs (IND15- IND21) and CV constructs (CBM22, SCM23, CVP24, IED25 and SDS26). The findings show that most companies disclose information about most of the 10R strategies of CE, which aligns

with the observation made by Opferkuch et al. (2022) and Roberts et al. (2022). The overall results for frequency distribution of most of the **CE related reporting practices** (presented in the table 5.3) are aligned with Gunarathne et al. (2021). This indicates that sample companies are implementing CE principles as a way to promote sustainability in the products design to encourage more intensive use of resources. This approach is in line with Atif (2023b) who emphasised the growing emphasis on circular design as a critical component of sustainable business practices. However, the researcher failed to detect disclosure about a few of 10R strategies of CE such as refurbishment, repurposing and remanufacturing which could be attributed to variations in the measurement of specific constructs (Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020; Roberts et al., 2022). Therefore, future researchers should reconsider the metric for such constructs to refine it for further investigation.

It has been observed from Table 5.3 that the sample companies in the current study have demonstrated a positive pattern in disclosure practices for revealing the CE constructs i.e., **servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies** and disclosing the reconfiguration of the **CV constructs** in their sustainability reports. The frequency analysis of I4.0 practices presented in the Table 5.3 aligns with the findings of Barnabè & Nazir (2021) and Gunarathne et al. (2021), demonstrating that manufacturing companies included in the sample are taking the advantage of disruptive technologies and reconsidering their business strategies to for a more stable revenue model. In addition, the findings in the Table 5.3 also align with the claims made by Opferkuch et al. (2022, 2023), Roberts et al. (2022), and Tiscini et al. (2022) as they note that more manufacturing companies are disclosing their use of innovation and reverse logistics strategies to reduce waste, explore unique combinations of products and services, and to access new markets.

5.4.4. Level 4: Yearly Trend of CE, Servitisation, I4.0 and CV in CE Disclosures

The records of CE-related disclosure practices by sample companies selected from the Global Fortune 500 list over the five years provides an insight into the trends and initiatives related to 10R strategies of CE, servitisation constructs, I4.0 constructs, and CV constructs. This record has helped the researcher identify how the transition towards circularity is evolving, which could help identify strengths and opportunities for further improvement in implementing CE practices. The findings are as follows:

Table 5. 4: The Yearly Trends of Latent Variable's Disclosure Practices for Each Year

Year	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Percentage (+/-)
CE	1517	1594	1686	1835	1838	(+) 21.16%
SER	901	935	954	1005	999	(+) 10.87%
I4.0	1591	1677	1708	1805	1836	(+) 15.39%
CV	975	1014	1095	1158	1157	(+) 18.66%

Where CE=circular economy, SER= servitisation, I4.0= industry 4.0 and CV= control variables.

It can be observed from Table 5.4 that over the five-year period, the number of companies disclosing information related to CE initiatives has steadily increased by 21.16%, indicating a positive trend towards a general increase in disclosures about CE reporting practices. This aligns with the findings of Barreiro-Gen & Lozano (2020) and Opferkuch et al. (2022) that CE reporting practices are becoming significantly important in the sustainability reports. However, these findings contradict the statement of Gunarathne et al. (2021) and Dagiliene et al. (2020), who claimed that CE disclosures are low.

The findings show that the disclosures on servitisation have increased by 10.87% over a five-year period, suggesting that incorporating servitisation as a CE strategy. These findings align with previous research conducted by Islam et al. (2023) that stresses there is a strong motivation for companies to produce circular products and services for ESG benefits. Thus, the findings demonstrate strong evidence that the sample companies (used in the current study) are committed to incorporate service provision within CEBM as a path to sustainable development and disclosing it to the stakeholders.

Correspondingly, it is observed from Table 5.4 that the reporting practices related to I4.0 initiatives has consistently increased over the years, with a 15.39% growth observed over a five-year period. This trend is supported by studies such as those by Barnabè & Nazir (2021), Gunarathne et al. (2021), Opferkuch et al. (2022, 2023), Roberts et al. (2022), and Tiscini et al. (2022), highlighting the commitment of companies to adapt innovation and sustainable practices and disclose it to their stakeholders. A long-term, holistic approach to business operations that considers the ESG impacts of corporate activities is crucial (W. Yu, Gu et al., 2022 and by disclosing their sustainable practices, as

5.5. Descriptive Analysis

A sample of 100 companies predominantly operating in the manufacturing sector and are listed in the Global Fortune 500 list (published in 2021.) was selected for this study by the researcher. From the sample companies the data for a five-year period (2018-22) was logged using a self-constructed CE disclosure index through content analysis and an accumulated five hundred observations were made by the researcher from the sustainability reports produced by the sample companies. The descriptive analysis including skewness and kurtosis of latent variables i.e., CE, servitisation, I4.0 and CV was performed using SPSS (V 26.0) to gain a valuable insight into the distribution of data.

This step helped the researcher in interpreting that how companies utilise servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies and use CV in controlling these CE transitions. By analysing the skewness and kurtosis of these variables in the descriptive analysis, researchers acquire a deeper understanding of their distributions and tendencies within the context of servitisation and I4.0 adoption in the realm of CE practices. This understanding is pivotal for interpreting the effectiveness and impact of CE disclosure practices on organisational operations, sustainability efforts, and enhance business performance. The researcher believes that the descriptive analysis's results will help advance knowledge of the CE disclosure practices, identify opportunities to simplify the CE reporting process, and support companies in reporting CE-related impact. The result for descriptive analysis is provided below:

Table 5. 5: Descriptive Analysis for Constructs of Latent Variables

Constructs	N	Mean	Std. d.	Skewness	Kurtosis
CER1	500	2.09	1.214	-0.878	-0.930
CER2	500	0.91	1.246	0.823	-1.096
CER3	500	2.83	0.471	-3.168	11.106
CER4	500	2.41	1.040	-1.569	0.911
CER5	500	1.71	1.270	-0.327	-1.575
CER6	500	0.58	1.098	1.550	0.632
CER7	500	0.44	1.012	2.016	2.241
CER8	500	0.93	1.289	0.814	-1.178
CER9	500	2.80	0.672	-3.398	10.478
CER10	500	2.24	1.177	-1.159	-0.389
SER11	500	2.68	0.659	-2.130	3.945
SER12	500	2.47	0.981	-1.730	1.560
SER13	500	2.24	1.120	-1.136	-0.292
SER14	500	2.20	1.172	-1.090	-0.490
IND15	500	2.29	0.795	-0.980	0.449
IND16	500	2.64	0.770	-2.288	4.526
IND17	500	2.46	0.902	-1.625	1.564
IND18	500	1.96	1.101	-0.680	-0.900
IND19	500	2.57	0.768	-1.940	3.263
IND20	500	2.72	0.624	-2.551	6.624
IND21	500	2.60	0.708	-1.922	3.497
CBM22	500	1.88	1.316	-0.523	-1.530
SCM23	500	2.63	0.683	-2.147	4.771
CVP24	500	2.42	0.702	-1.227	1.622
IED25	500	1.36	1.328	0.176	-1.743
SDS26	500	2.50	1.028	-1.763	1.398

Where CER1=refuse; CER2= rethink; CER3= reduce; CER4= reuse; CER5= repair; CER6= refurbish; CER7= remanufacture; CER8= repurpose; CER9= recycle; CER10= recover, SER11= servitisation as a CE strategy; SER12= waste recovery for servitisation; SER13= minimise usage of virgin material, SER14= end-of-life practices/ reverse logistics, IND15= transparency and accountability; IND16=I4.0-enabled shared platform; IND17= Resource Efficiency IND18= extended lifecycle; IND19= functional efficacy; IND20= innovation through I4.0; IND21= monitoring resource Use, CBM22= circular business model; SCM23= supply chain management: reverse activities/logistics; CVP24= circular value proposition; IED25= investment of Eco-design; SDS26= statement on sustainable development strategy.

Table 5.5 presents a comprehensive overview of descriptive statistics for CE constructs, servitisation constructs, I4.0 constructs, and control variables of the CE-disclosure index. These statistics are derived from a robust sample of one hundred manufacturing-based companies from the Global Fortune 500 list over a span of five years. The review of these statistics reveals intriguing findings. According to the findings in Table 5.5, the ten constructs of CE disclosures (CER1-CER10) present varied results. Four of the ten CE constructs (CER2, CER6, CER7, and CER8) have positive skewness, indicating that the data is concentrated on the left side with a few high values. This validates the growing importance of CE reporting practices in sustainability reports. Conversely, the other six constructs

(CER1, CER3, CER4, CER5, CER9, and CER10) show negative skewness, suggesting that the data is concentrated on the right side with lower values. This indicates that manufacturing companies in the sample face numerous challenges in incorporating certain CE strategies in today's volatile, uncertain, and competitive market. This is consistent with the RBV, which suggests that organisations are driven to adopt diverse frameworks to create a circular advantage for all stakeholders in today's competitive market.

The Table 5.5 concludes that the CE constructs (CER1-CER10) fall outside the skewness range (± 1.96) well within the limit suggested by (Ryu, 2011). Similar results are observed for the kurtosis, with seven constructs having negative kurtosis (platykurtic distribution) falling outside the expected range (± 3) and only three constructs showing positive kurtosis within the expected range (± 3) (leptokurtic distribution), indicating the non-normality of data distribution (W. Qu et al., 2020). These findings imply that companies' adaptation of CE-related frameworks and journey of transition towards circularity should be disclosed in their sustainability reports. The reports should detail the companies' CE strategies and describe how they mitigate negative environmental impacts and enhance their long-term ESG viability.

Additionally, the servitisation's constructs exhibit moderately positive mean values in the Table 5.5. These findings suggest that *servitisation* has the potential to positively influence the measured constructs, which are indirectly linked to energy consumption improvements and environmental performance. The results about the constructs of servitisation also indicate that manufacturing firms from the sample are disclosing data about their servitisation strategies and supply chain networks by transparent reporting in order to achieve their ESG goals and ensure the continuity of the business operations. The standard deviation values in the Table 5.5, indicates data variability, suggesting some dispersion in the reporting practices regarding servitisation as a CE strategy. These results are consistent with Singh et al. (2021), who emphasise reporting their operations to stakeholders to establish trust and demonstrate transparency and accountability when engaging with supply chain networks. The findings highlight the significance of reporting stakeholder engagement, positively contributing to ESG impacts in their sustainability reports. Additionally, this emphasis on reporting reflects the dynamic capability of information management and dissemination. By effectively communicating their activities and commitments related to stakeholder engagement and ESG impacts, companies demonstrate their ability to adapt and respond to changing market conditions and stakeholder expectations. This is consistent with DCT, which suggests that this allows organisations to continuously learn, innovate, and improve their sustainability practices, thereby enhancing their long-term competitiveness and resilience in the market.

However, these findings contradict Doni et al. (2019)'s assertion that servitisation does not impact corporate sustainability disclosures. Additionally, the servitisation constructs show a negative skewness, while three servitisation constructs (SER11, SER12, and SER14) demonstrate positive kurtosis, and one construct (SER13) shows negative kurtosis. According to Ryu (2011), these deviations from normality should be considered when analysing and interpreting the data.

Similarly, all the **I4.0 constructs** in the Table 5.5 display negative skewness. Six constructs of I4.0 (IND15, IND16, IND17, IND19, IND20, and IND21) exhibit positive kurtosis, meaning they fall outside the range of ± 3 , suggested by Ryu (2011). However, only one construct (IND18) shows negative kurtosis. These deviations collectively suggest the non-normality of data distribution (W. Qu et al., 2020). The findings highlight the need for further progress and development in CE and digitalisation-related disclosure practices among the sampled manufacturing firms. These firms should consider reporting the proper metric of their adoption of I4.0 technologies as a strategy for advancing CE. The analysis of I4.0-related disclosures shows that most manufacturing businesses use these technologies to improve resource efficiency and reduce negative environmental effects. However, a proper framework for digital disclosures needs to be developed, which requires significant attention. Businesses need to assess the costs and benefits of adopting innovative I4.0 technologies to achieve their environmental goals and report on it in their sustainability reports.

The four **CV** constructs, namely CBM22, SCM23, CVP24 and SDS26, exhibit negative skewness, while IED25 displays positive skewness. Moreover, three constructs (SCM23, CVP24, SDS26) have positive kurtosis, whereas the remaining two (CBM22 and IED25) present negative kurtosis. Notably, most variables show skewness and kurtosis values outside the expected range (± 3), indicating the non-normality of data and distribution difficulties (Ryu, 2011). The researcher believes it is important to assess each CV individually, as they each carry unique characteristics. This assessment will help to identify their central tendency and variability. The results of descriptive statistics for CV constructs CBM22 suggest that the distribution is non-normal. This observation coincides with the findings of Nazir & Doni (2024); D. Rossi et al. (2024) and Tiscini et al. (2022), who observed a significant shift towards CEBM coherence with the amendments introduced by the EU 2015 Act. Similarly, the CV constructs SCM23 exhibits negative skewness (-2.147) and positive kurtosis (4.771), indicating that the average response falls closer to the higher end of the scale (2 and 3 scores), with only a small amount of variability (mean of 2.63). These results are consistent with Fernando et al. (2023); N. M. Hassan et al. (2023) and J. Liu & Lu (2023), suggesting synchronising sustainable SCM with the CE as the best way to address environmental problems. Likewise, the construct CVP24 demonstrates negative skewness (-1.227) and positive kurtosis (1.622), indicating non-normality of data distribution. These descriptive findings are aligned with the research conducted by Cenamor et al. (2017), highlighting the benefits

of using a digital platform to enhance the servitisation approach's value. Additionally, the results align with Chen et al. (2022) suggestion, which indicates businesses should disclose the reconfiguration of their value chain to include the ecosystem. On the other hand, IED25 showcases a slightly right-skewed distribution with thinner tails. These findings support the suggestion made by Chen et al. (2022) that the content of environmental cost related disclosures needs improvement. The researcher believes that observed variability in IED25 strongly indicates that there may be inconsistencies or gaps in the disclosure practices, with certain companies providing limited or insufficient information. Finally, the construct SDS26 presents normality of data distribution suggesting that most companies in the sample are integrating and adjusting their sustainability statements and vision by implementing CE practices. These findings align with the recommendation Ibáñez-Forés et al. (2022) made to revise the fundamental CE reporting framework to consider the broader concept of CE and its role in promoting global sustainability and circular growth.

5.6. Reliability Test of Disclosure Index

Reliability tests are commonly used in quantitative research, and measuring scale reliability is a crucial criterion in content analysis. Malkewitz et al. (2023) suggested that selecting the appropriate reliability test to check internal consistency is more important than selecting a coefficient, as it minimises the chances of human biasness and maximises the reproducibility of research outcomes. Cerri et al. (2023) recommended measuring internal consistencies is the most common reliability test. Thus, to ensure that a research phenomenon is measured accurately, it is essential to conduct a reliability analysis of the research instrument. This helps determine its consistency, which, in turn, provides reliable research outcomes. The most basic and practical way to measure dependability is through internal consistency. It requires only one administration of a single measurement equipment and measures the inter-correlation among constructs that assess the same idea. Therefore, the researcher conducted a Cronbach Alpha and composite reliability to ensure the accuracy and credibility of qualitative results that correspond to the nature of the quantitative investigation. Previously, (Krippendorff, 1980) observed that it is important to note that Cronbach's alpha, a statistical measure used to assess the reliability is based on certain assumptions that are rarely met in empirical research. These assumptions include one-dimensionality and tau-equivalence of data. Both assumptions were met in the current study, with the one-dimensionality of CE, servitisation, I4.0 and CV being present in their overarching themes of resource sustainability and efficiency, service-oriented BMs, and digital transformation in industry. The other assumption is tau-equivalence assumption which was also met as the same scoring definition was used for measuring all the latent variables, including the dependent, independent, and control variables (The scoring definition was selected following previous

disclosure index related studies such as Barreiro-Gen & Lozano (2020); Bogdan et al. (2022); Cenamor et al. (2017); D'Amato et al. (2019); Doni et al. (2019); Gunarathne et al. (2021); A. Hassan et al. (2022); Mirzaei & Shokouhyar (2022); Opferkuch et al. (2022); Scarpellini (2022) and Yang et al. (2019).

5.6.1. Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability

Cela et al. (2024), affirmed that Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability (CR) are statistical measure that assesses the relationship between constructs on a scale. It determines how well these constructs measure the same underlying construct (Raza et al., 2020). An internal consistency level is acceptable if Cronbach's coefficient is above 0.6 (Bag & Rahman, 2023). The reliability of a study's latent variables (CE, servitisation, I4.0 and CV) and their constructs (CER1- CER10 for CE; SER11-SER14 for servitisation; IND15- IND21 for I4.0 and CBM22, SCM23, CVP24, IED25 and SDS25) are usually considered good if the standardised loadings have values above 0.7 and the CR value is greater than 0.6 (N. M. Hassan et al., 2023). The results for Cronbach alpha and CR are as follows:

Table 5. 6: Results for Reliability Tests

Variables and Constructs	Standardised Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability (CR)
CE		0.714	0.746
CER1	0.703		
CER2	0.629		
CER3	0.708		
CER4	0.615		
CER5	0.645		
CER6	0.603		
CER7	0.683		
CER8	0.629		
CER9	0.627		
CER10	0.625		
SER		0.822	0.854
SER11	0.683		
SER12	0.838		
SER13	0.903		
SER14	0.870		
I4.0		0.769	0.793
IND15	0.621		
IND16	0.670		
IND17	0.745		
IND18	0.637		
IND19	0.699		
IND20	0.746		
IND21	0.654		

Variables and Constructs	Standardised Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability (CR)
CV		0.710	0.724
CBM22	0.634		
SCM23	0.733		
CVP24	0.671		
IED25	0.600		
SDS26	0.601		

Where CE= circular economy; SER= servitisation; I4.0= industry 4.0; CV= control variables; CER1=refuse; CER2= rethink; CER3= reduce; CER4= reuse; CER5= repair; CER6= refurbish; CER7= remanufacture; CER8= repurpose; CER9= recycle; CER10= recover; SER11= servitisation as a CE strategy; SER12= waste recovery for servitisation; SER13= minimise usage of virgin material; SER14= end-of-life practices/ reverse logistics; IND15= transparency and accountability; IND16=I4.0-enabled shared platform; IND17= Resource Efficiency IND18= extended lifecycle; IND19= functional efficacy; IND20= innovation through I4.0; IND21= monitoring resource Use; CBM22= circular business model; SCM23= supply chain management: reverse activities/logistics; CVP24= circular value proposition; IED25= investment of Eco-design; SDS26= statement on sustainable development strategy.

Table 5.6 reports the values for reliability tests (Cronbach alpha and CR) result, including the standardised loadings of each construct of the latent variables. It is worth noting that among the ten constructs measuring the CE construct, the internal consistency level is 0.714 and the CR values demonstrate 0.746. On the other hand, the four constructs measuring the SER construct have a Cronbach's alpha level of 0.822. The CR value is 0.854. For the I4.0 construct, the internal consistency level among the seven constructs is 0.769 for Cronbach's alpha, 0.793 for CR. The Control Variables consist of five constructs with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.710, CR value of 0.724. These results suggest that there is moderate to good internal consistency which means that they can measure related constructs reliably.

5.7. Validity Test of Disclosure Index

Validity testing is a critical part of research. Krippendorff (1980) suggested that correlational techniques can accomplish validity testing. It is valid when it shows a high correlation with established measures of the intended trait and low or zero correlations with traits it aims to distinguish from. Hamed Taherdoost & Lumpur (2016) also identifies four types of validity tests: content, criterion, convergent, and discriminant validity. Content validity assesses the relevance and representativeness of measurement constructs; convergent validity evaluates the degree of agreement among measures of the same construct and discriminant validity assesses the ability of a measurement instrument to distinguish between different constructs. For example, N. M. Hassan et al. (2023) and Hariadi et al. (2023) conducted tests on the scale constructs to measure their convergent and discriminant validity.

5.7.1. Convergent Validity: Average Extracted Variance (AVE)

Arsawan et al. (2023) conducted Average Extracted Variance (AVE) which is a convergent validity and this validity results were over 0.5, and the factor loading was over 0.6. This indicates that the discriminant validity conditions of all constructs have been met. Following the given examples, the researcher of the current study used the average variance extracted (AVE) method to determine the convergent validity of the latent constructs and the results are as follows:

Table 5. 7: Results for Average Extracted Variance

Constructs	Average Extracted Variance (AVE)
CE	0.688
SER	0.653
I4.0	0.633
CV	0.653

Where, CE= circular economy; SER= servitisation; I4.0= industry 4.0 and CV= control variables.

The results presented in table 5.7 shows that the AVE value for CE is 0.688, SER is 0.653, I4.0 is 0.633 for AVE, and CV is 0.653. As described by Hair et al. (2014), an AVE value above 0.5 indicates a strong convergent validity, meaning the observed variables are good indicators of the underlying construct.

5.7.2. Discriminant Validity: Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT)

The Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) assesses discriminant validity in SEM. It compares the correlations between constructs (heterotrait correlations) to the average correlations within constructs (monotrait correlations) (Hair et al., 2014; Singhania & Gandhi, 2015).

Table 5. 8: Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) – List

Variables	HTMT
CV <-> CE	0.718
I4.0 <-> CE	0.665
I4.0 <-> CV	0.663
SER <-> CE	0.724
SER <-> CV	0.755
SER <-> I4.0	0.727

Where, CE=circular economy, SER= servitisation, I4.0= industry 4.0 and CV= control variables.

The presented table 5.8 displays the results of HTMT tests, which indicate the strength of relationships between different model constructs of the current study. For instance, the HTMT values for CV <-> CE = 0.718, I4.0 <-> CE = 0.665, I4.0 <-> CV = 0.663, SER <-> CE = 0.724, SER <-> CV = 0.755, and SER <-> I4.0 = 0.727. The results exceeded the recommended threshold of 0.70, proving the scale validity among the respective pairs of constructs.

5.7.3. Content Validity: Pilot Study

According to Fernando et al. (2023), Pilot studies may be considered evidence of validity as they provide preliminary data and insights to improve measurement instruments and study procedures. They conducted a validity test via pilot study of 30 practitioners and their study led to minor language revisions for the exogenous and endogenous variables. Their findings revealed that the factorial loads ranged from 0.714 to 0.899, all above the recommended threshold of 0.7. Similarly, the researcher has conducted a pilot study¹² to assess the construct validity of the CE disclosure index by examining whether the other latent variables (servitisation, I4.0 and control variables) behave as expected based on theoretical predictions.

5.7.4. Criterion Validity: Pearson's Correlation Analysis

Li et al. (2024) suggested that researchers can generate high-quality findings by selecting appropriate concepts to analyse and determining the appropriate measurement methods and instructed to validate the model after determining the variables and equations to build the model to establish confidence in it. Ji et al. (2023) also recommended verifying the correlation of coefficients to confirm the association of study variables before conducting hypothesis testing. Investigating the validity of a research instrument is crucial in determining whether its accuracy and significance are genuine and whether it truly measures what it claims to assess (Krippendorff, 1980). According to Hamed Taherdoost & Lumpur (2016), creating a consistent disclosure index based on prior literature would be beneficial to enhance the validity of voluntary disclosure research. Therefore, the researcher of the current study developed a consistent disclosure index in line with prior literature to ensure the validity of voluntary CE disclosure research. In the current study, the construct validity of the dependent variables of the CE disclosure index were evaluated through Pearson's correlation test.

¹² Please find details about pilot study in Appendix 6: Pilot Study.

Table 5. 9: Correlation Analysis of Dependent Variable (Circular Economy)

Var.	CER1	CER2	CER3	CER4	CER5	CER6	CER7	CER8	CER9	CER10
CER1	1.000									
CER2	.298**	1.000								
CER3	.333**	.168**	1.000							
CER4	.365**	.258**	.299**	1.000						
CER5	.204**	.162**	.160**	.185**	1.000					
CER6	0.015	.016	.078	.130**	.239**	1.000				
CER7	.193**	.264**	.121**	.192**	.249**	.405**	1.000			
CER8	.267**	.223**	.184**	.202**	.193**	.268**	.325**	1.000		
CER9	.274**	.159**	.296**	.362**	.102*	.046	.133**	.140**	1.000	
CER10	.374**	.177**	.191**	.287**	.246**	.146**	.170**	.240**	.302**	1.000

** indicate p<0.01 and * indicate p< 0.05

Where CER1=refuse; CER2= rethink; CER3= reduce; CER4= reuse; CER5= repair; CER6= refurbish; CER7= remanufacture; CER8= repurpose; CER9= recycle; CER10= recover.

Table 5.9 presents the results for Spearman correlation, showing strong correlations between all CE constructs, indicating that the collected data consistently captured the CE content elements across different constructs (CE's 10R strategies). This suggests that there is no issue of multicollinearity, which reinforces the accuracy and reliability of the variables.

5.8. Collinearity Test

Collinearity is a statistical term when predictor variables are not independent (Dormann et al., 2013) and multicollinearity can inflate regression parameter variance and lead to incorrect predictor identification(Hair et al., 2014; Singhania & Gandhi, 2015). Thus, the researcher has conducted collinearity tests, and the results are as follows:

5.8.1. Pair-wise Correlation

According to Dormann et al. (2013), two regressors are considered multicollinear if their pairwise correlation coefficient is lower than 0.3 and higher than 0.8 and advised to avoid using extremely correlated variables. Thus, the researcher conducted a pair-wise correlation analysis, as presented in Table 5.10. The results indicate values greater than 0.3, depicting the absence of multicollinearity. The results are presented as follows:

Table 5 10: Pair-wise Correlation

Variable	CER	SER	IND	CV
CE	1	.550**	.494**	.497**
SER	.550**	1	.580**	.547**
I4.0	.494**	.580**	1	.596**
CV	.497**	.547**	.596**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Where, CE=Total disclosure score for CE; SER= total disclosure score for servitisation; I4.0= total disclosure score for I4.0 and CV=total disclosure score for control variables

Table 5. 11: Correlation Analysis (Part 1)

N.	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)	(14)
(1)	1													
(2)	.310**	1												
(3)	.329**	.176**	1											
(4)	.322**	.245**	.247**	1										
(5)	.201**	.164**	.145**	.158**	1									
(6)	0.025	0.028	0.055	.136**	.238**	1								
(7)	.207**	.253**	.110*	.192**	.239**	.406**	1							
(8)	.277**	.246**	.169**	.209**	.180**	.275**	.315**	1						
(9)	.264**	.151**	.245**	.394**	0.062	0.051	.116**	.139**	1					
(10)	.356**	.177**	.139**	.306**	.224**	.143**	.159**	.246**	.318**	1				
(11)	.205**	.171**	.168**	.108*	.170**	.091*	.163**	.097*	.188**	.252**	1			
(12)	.413**	.260**	.269**	.392**	.172**	0.07	.169**	.185**	.349**	.399**	.312**	1		
(13)	.377**	.255**	.251**	.310**	.259**	.117**	.248**	.174**	.282**	.388**	.436**	.670**	1	
(14)	.399**	.266**	.283**	.264**	.209**	.117**	.244**	.255**	.263**	.323**	.384**	.610**	.744**	1
(15)	.178**	.151**	.176**	.157**	.175**	.132**	.093*	.108*	0.052	.111*	0.074	.227**	.244**	.262**
(16)	.177**	0.082	.139**	.179**	.189**	.102*	.104*	.097*	-0.01	.279**	.230**	.264**	.269**	.234**
(17)	.351**	.207**	.207**	.186**	.134**	0.06	.180**	.181**	.204**	.294**	.273**	.481**	.496**	.432**
(18)	.229**	.219**	.281**	.090*	.174**	.186**	.242**	.230**	0.059	.177**	.250**	.277**	.324**	.346**
(19)	.317**	.193**	.124**	.168**	.231**	.122**	.172**	.111*	.156**	.233**	.300**	.319**	.346**	.314**
(20)	.338**	.182**	.323**	.187**	.143**	0.048	0.088	.165**	.256**	.264**	.370**	.400**	.332**	.292**
(21)	.335**	.146**	.323**	.124**	.244**	0.007	.109*	.186**	.147**	.262**	.158**	.346**	.335**	.348**
(22)	.207**	.351**	.133**	.288**	.139**	0.063	.200**	.148**	.088*	.228**	.239**	.257**	.347**	.353**
(23)	.404**	.188**	.253**	.228**	.137**	0.013	.112*	.125**	.298**	.236**	.317**	.410**	.452**	.398**
(24)	.248**	.144**	.115**	.187**	.118**	.092*	.129**	.234**	.137**	.290**	.188**	.315**	.306**	.318**
(25)	.306**	.288**	.147**	0.087	.198**	.121**	.149**	.213**	0.057	.217**	.194**	.300**	.324**	.318**
(26)	.254**	0.07	0.085	.256**	0.019	-0.02	0.056	.137**	.212**	.191**	0.04	.289**	.216**	.193**

** Indicates p < 0.01 and * indicates p < 0.05

Where (1)=refuse; (2)= rethink; (3)= reduce; (4)= reuse; (5)= repair; (6)= refurbish; (7)= remanufacture; (8)= repurpose; (9)= recycle; (10)= recover; (11)= servitisation as a CE strategy; (12)= waste recovery for servitisation; (13)= minimise usage of virgin material, (14)= end-of-life practices/ reverse logistics; (15)= transparency and accountability; (16)=I4.0-enabled shared platform; (17)= Resource Efficiency; (18)= extended lifecycle; (19)= functional efficacy; (20)= innovation through I4.0; (21)= monitoring resource Use; (22)= circular business model; (23)= supply chain management: reverse activities/logistics; (24)= circular value proposition; (25)= investment of Eco-design; (26)= statement on sustainable development strategy.

Table 5. 12: Correlation Analysis (Part 2)

Construct	(15)	(16)	(17)	(18)	(19)	(20)	(21)	(22)	(23)	(24)	(25)	(26)
(15)	1											
(16)	.305**	1										
(17)	.252**	.252**	1									
(18)	.329**	.257**	.402**	1								
(19)	.275**	.250**	.609**	.392**	1							
(20)	.241**	.415**	.469**	.287**	.381**	1						
(21)	.249**	.332**	.303**	.280**	.247**	.516**	1					
(22)	.217**	.240**	.292**	.333**	.295**	.214**	.129**	1				
(23)	.229**	.273**	.416**	.244**	.365**	.473**	.337**	.339**	1			
(24)	.316**	.223**	.360**	.221**	.261**	.279**	.313**	.213**	.361**	1		
(25)	.215**	.159**	.321**	.235**	.228**	.226**	.175**	.191**	.250**	.304**	1	
(26)	.245**	.263**	.243**	.133**	.204**	.358**	.187**	.282**	.301**	.333**	.202**	1

** Indicates $p < 0.01$ and * indicates $p < 0.05$

Where (1)=refuse; (2)= rethink; (3)= reduce; (4)= reuse; (5)= repair; (6)= refurbish; (7)= remanufacture; (8)= repurpose; (9)= recycle; (10)= recover; (11)= servitisation as a CE strategy; (12)= waste recovery for servitisation; (13)= minimise usage of virgin material, (14)= end-of-life practices/ reverse logistics; (15)= transparency and accountability; (16)=I4.0-enabled shared platform; (17)= Resource Efficiency; (18)= extended lifecycle; (19)= functional efficacy; (20)= innovation through I4.0; (21)= monitoring resource Use; (22)= circular business model; (23)= supply chain management: reverse activities/logistics; (24)= circular value proposition; (25)= investment of Eco-design; (26)= statement on sustainable development strategy.

Table 5.11 presents the part-1 correlation of each construct of latent variables, and Table 5.12 presents the part-2 correlation of each construct of latent variables. It is worth noting that all variables (in Tables 5.11-5.12) have values less than 0.80 (Hair et al., 2014). Consequently, there is no need to worry about multicollinearity.

5.8.2. Multicollinearity Correlation

Gerged et al. (2023) used a correlation matrix to test for multicollinearity but recommended using Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) analysis to reduce the risk of multicollinearity before using the indicators in the analysis. Likewise, Gonella et al. (2023) conducted VIF for each independent variable and found that the VIF values were < 3.3 , eliminating multicollinearity issues. Similarly, Islam et al. (2023) also checked for potential collinearity problems by ensuring $VIF < 3$ before running the statistical analysis. Thus, the researcher decided to conduct VIF analysis as well to confirm the absence of multicollinearity.

Table 5. 13: Multicollinearity Analysis

Coefficients			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	SER	.601	1.665
	I4.0	.553	1.808
	CV	.583	1.714
a. Dependent Variable: CE			

Where, CE= circular economy, SER= servitisation, I4.0= industry 4.0 and CV= control variables.

Table 5.13 presents the results for multicollinearity analysis (VIF) of individual constructs of latent variables (CE, servitisation, I4.0 and CV). Across all variables, the VIF values ranged from 1.145 to 2.824, indicating relatively low levels of multicollinearity. The VIF results for individual constructs are as follows: CER1= 1.424; CER2= 1.214; CER3= 1.186; CER4= 1.346; CER5= 1.159; CER6= 1.308; CER7= 1.362; CER8=1.265; CER9= 1.290; CER10= 1.307; SER11= 1.247; SER12= 1.911; SER13= 2.824; SER14= 2.377; IND15= 1.225; IND16= 1.308; IND17= 1.837; IND18= 1.346; IND19= 1.699; IND20= 1.726; IND21= 1.435; CBM22= 1.189; SCM23= 1.300; CVP24= 1.287; IED25= 1.145; SDS26= 1.220. It should be noted that variables such as CBM22, CER 7, CER 8, and others demonstrated VIF values close to or below 1.5, suggesting minimal correlation with other predictors, indicating that they contribute meaningfully to the model without excessively inflating standard errors or compromising the reliability of the regression coefficients.

5.9. Outlier Detection

According to Osborne (2002), outliers are data points (observations) with unique attributes that deviate significantly from the rest of the data in a dataset. In case of disproportionation of outliers, the data normality and statistical tests can be skewed, leading, leading to biased parameter estimates and inflated standard errors (Hosseinifard et al., 2009). Thus, the researcher has presented the results boxplot to identify the outliers as follows:

Figure 5. 2: Box Plot for Latent Variables (CE, servitisation, I4.0 and CV)

Source: Author's Creation (SPSS)

Figure 5.2 presents a box plot representing the data distribution of latent variables: CER is CE, SER is servitisation, IND is I4.0, and CV is control variables. From the plot, it can be observed that CER is likely to have a normal distribution since this variable has no outliers. However, some values suggest a slight deviation from a perfectly normal distribution, although they do not indicate any significant departure from normality. However, SER, IND, and CV have outlier points highlighted at the bottom range. For SER, the outliers are 25,363, 396, 398 and 397. For IND, the outliers are 106, 121, 326*, 327, 387, 436, 437, 439, 466 and 499, with 326* being an extreme outlier. Similarly, CV also has outliers, which are 83, 466, 467 and 468, but none of them are extreme values. SER, IND, and CV indicate that data points or observations deviate significantly from the normal range as they are much lower than expected values. The researcher has observed that assumptions of normality may not hold for these variables (SER, IND and CV), which should be considered in multivariate analysis before applying statistical analyses (such as SPSS) that assume normality (Jobst et al., 2022; W. Qu et al., 2020).

5.10. Normality Test

According to Hosseinifard et al. (2009), non-normal data is a serious concern due to its skewness. This could lead to compromise of validity and reliability of results (Y. G. Zhao et al., 2021). Hair et al. (2014) recommended conducting a normality test in multivariate analysis to ensure that the assumptions of parametric statistical tests, such as regression analysis, are met. Thus, the researcher has performed normality test on dependent variable (CER), independent variables (SER and IND) and control variable (CV) of the current study to assess the normal distribution. The normality test results are presented through graphical representations such as a histogram and quantile-quantile plot (Q-Q plot). Additionally, numeric methods such as the Shapiro-Wilk is presented.

5.10.1. Graphical Method

The researcher conducted a normality test in the current study and presented the results using two graphical methods. The histogram and Q-Q plotting were presented to visually demonstrate normality, as both methods are commonly used in academic research to assess data distributions.

Figure 5 3: Histogram with Normal Curve for Latent Variables (CE, servitisation, I4.0 and CV)

Source: Author's Creation (SPSS)

Figure 5.3 shows a histogram overlaid with a normal distribution curve for CE, servitisation, I4.0 and control variables. The top-left histogram shows the results for servitisation, indicating non-normality in distribution. The top-right histogram presents the graphical representation for the CE normality test, suggesting a closer-to-normal distribution. Similar results can be seen for the I4.0 histogram (bottom-left) and control variables (Bottom-right). These results suggest that the data's CE, I4.0 and control variables distribution, as depicted by the histogram, closely resembles the shape of a bell curve, which is characteristic of a normal distribution. At the same time, servitisation's distribution is non-normal.

Figure 5. 4: Q-Q Plot for Latent Variables (CE, servitisation, I4.0 and CV)

Source: Author's Creation (SPSS)

The results of a Q-Q plot for CE (top-left), servitisation (top-right), I4.0 (bottom-left) and control variables (bottom-right) generated from SPSS are presented in Figure 5.4. This graphical method determines whether a dataset's distribution is normal. It should be noted that minor deviations from the diagonal line may not necessarily indicate a departure from normality. According to Morea et al. (2022), normal distribution is considered if the Q-Q plot does not have a heavy tail. The observed distribution for CE does not exhibit extreme values in the tails compared to the reference distribution. Likewise, the plot demonstrates that CER is approximately symmetric with slight right skewness, and both the tails are relatively lighter than those of normal distribution. While servitisation, I4.0 and control variable's plot present deviations from the straight line, indicating to non-normal distribution.

5.10.2. Numerical Method

Table 5. 14: Shapiro-Wilk Test of Normality

Variable	Obs.	W	Sig.
CE	500	0.991	0.004
SER	500	0.757	0.000
I4.0	500	0.874	0.000
CV	500	0.933	0.000

Where, CE= circular economy, SER= servitisation, I4.0= industry 4.0 and CV=control variables.

The table 5.14 below shows the results of a normality test conducted on the latent variables (CE, servitisation, I4.0 and CV). The results for Shapiro-Wilk test indicate a significant deviation from a normal distribution. However, it is important to note that statistical significance alone should not be the only criterion for determining whether the data is normally distributed. A p-value close to 0.05 may indicate that the data approximates a normal distribution well enough for many analyses, particularly if the **departure from normality** is insignificant and the sample size is large (Zhao et al., 2021; Pietrulla, 2022).

5.10.3. Rationale for Avoiding Transformation

Transformations such as logarithmic or square root transformations help stabilise the variance and better approximate a normal distribution, thereby improving the validity of subsequent statistical analyses (Qu et al., 2020; Z. Liu et al., 2020; Stottlemire, 2023). Osborne (2002) instructed that data transformation should only be used if the non-normality of data is evident, as it could create curvilinear relationships, which could complicate the interpretation. Likewise, Zhao et al. (2021) discussed several transformation procedures for handling non-normal correlated variables and

recommended selecting the most effective transformation method to make the statistical modelling more reliable and accurate. For instance, Craig & Diga (1998) employed a combination of multivariate analysis techniques, logarithmic transformations, and regression diagnostics to construct and validate a comprehensive regression model. Burritt et al. (2016) applied a square root transformation to their dependent variable to improve normality and meet the assumptions of multi-regression analysis. Similarly, Li et al. (2008) identified the non-normality in their independent and control variable based on skewness and kurtosis analysis and later applied square root transformation to normalise. It is important to note that Cooke (1998) suggested that transforming independent variables is preferable to transforming dependent variables in regression analysis. This is because transforming the dependent variable can disrupt its relationship with other regressors and change the error distribution, affecting the results' validity. Consequently, Ji et al. (2022) standardised their non-normal dataset by transforming independent variables using square root transformation. As the aim of the current study is to assess CE disclosure by examining the utilisation of the servitisation and the I4.0 as integral components of CE strategy. However, the descriptive analysis shows that CE has a positive skew while Servitisation, I4.0 and CV present a negative skewness. The slight non-normality of the dependent variable (CE) may not be a significant concern if other assumptions are met (Jobst et al., 2022), such as it can be observed that CE is likely to have a normal distribution since this variable has no outliers (refer to Figure 5.4). The presence of outliers in the data for certain years (2018, 2021, and 2022) suggests that there were instances where the values of the CE variable deviated substantially from the norm, either by being unusually high (2018) or unusually low (2021, 2022). At the same time, the researcher found that three variables, servitisation, I4.0, and CV, do not follow a normal distribution pattern. Despite trying various transformations, the researcher was unable to standardize or normalize these datasets. Thus, the researcher will not transform the dependent variable because Osborne (2002) instructed that data transformation should only be used if the non-normality of data is evident, as it could create curvilinear relationships, which could complicate the interpretation. For this reason, the researcher has decided to use Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) as it is a more flexible statistical technique that can handle non-normal data (Palmer, 2008). The decision to employ PLS-SEM aligns well with the objectives and structure of the current study. Given the complexity of the model, which involves multiple variables, a dependent variable (CE comprising ten constructs), two independent variables (servitisation with four constructs and I4.0 with seven constructs) and a control variable (comprising five constructs), PLS-SEM is suitable for analysing the relationships among these variables (Raza et al., 2020). Additionally, PLS-SEM is adept at handling predictive studies that identify causal relationships (Hair et al., 2014), making it a perfect choice for

the current research. With twenty-six constructs distributed across the variables, PLS-SEM can effectively capture the relationships within the population data.

5.11. Factor Analysis and Goodness of Fit

In the current study, a model fit statistics derived from PLS-SEM is used to evaluate how well the observed data fits the hypothesised model in structural equation modelling (SEM) and other statistical modelling techniques. These statistics offer insights about the model's overall fit to the data, helping researchers assess the validity of the measurement model (Bhatti et al., 2023). Chen & Chen (2024) tested the factor analysis of their scale and goodness of fit test by performing the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Chi-square tests in Bartlett's testing. The results showed a KMO value of 0.932, greater than 0.7. The Chi-square value in Bartlett's test was 18,385.559, with a significance level 0.000. This indicates that the scale passed the significance test at a level of 0.001, and the data are suitable for factor analysis. The validity of the factor analysis results is ultimately dependent on other factors, such as the appropriateness of the research design, the validity of the measurement instruments used, and the robustness of the statistical analysis (Takyi-Annan & Zhang, 2023).

Table 5. 15: KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.803
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1345.359
	Df	6
	Sig.	<.001

Where Df= degree of freedom and sig.= significance

Table 5.15 presents the results for KMO and Bartlett's test. The normal range for KMO deemed suitable for factor analysis is 0 to 1 (Chen & Chen, 2024). In this case, the KMO measure is 0.803, suggesting a moderately to highly suitability for factor analysis. The test statistic is an approximate chi-square value compared to a chi-square distribution with degrees of freedom (df) equal to the number of variables in the analysis. In this case, Bartlett's test statistic is approximately 1345.359, with 6 degrees of freedom. The associated p-value (<.001) indicates that the null hypothesis (that the variables are uncorrelated) is rejected, suggesting that the correlation matrix is not an identity matrix and that there are significant correlations among the variables. The researcher evaluated the quality of the data fit by examining the statistics derived from PLS-SEM for two measures: standardised root mean square residual (SRMR) and normed fit index (NFI). The normal range for an acceptable SRMR value is less than 0.08, while an NFI value between 0 to 1 is considered good (with higher values closer to 1 indicating a better fit) (Hair et al., 2014). The results for SRMR and NFI were 0.076 and 0.683,

respectively, which fall within the acceptable range. Therefore, the model measures indicate a relatively *good fit for statistical modelling*.

5.12. Statistical Analysis: Structural Modelling

The researcher utilised the bootstrapping technique in PLS-SEM to conduct statistical analysis for the current study to assess the significance of servitisation and I4.0 being used as a strategy in global Fortune 500 companies examining their disclosure practices. The current study formulated a model to gain constructive insights through research hypotheses (H1-H4). Specifically, the fourth research objective (RO4) aims to evaluate the impact of combining CE, Servitisation, and I4.0, including the control variables. This will be done by analysing the company's disclosure practices related to the effects and transition practices associated with this combination. Additionally, the fourth research question (RQ4) aims to analyse the company's reporting practices on the effects and transition practices related to this combination to provide constructive information on its impact. The statistical results support a positive and direct relationship between CE, servitisation, I4.0 and control variables to answer RQ4.

The bootstrapping process in PLS-SEM was applied, which involves resampling the dataset multiple times to estimate the distribution of model parameters and assess their statistical significance (Hair et al., 2014). The settings used for bootstrapping in this analysis include an initial weight of 1.0 assigned to model parameters, a maximum of 3000 iterations allowed during the optimisation process, and a stop criterion set to 10^{-7} , indicating that the process terminates when the change in parameter estimates falls below this threshold. The analysis results are standardised, providing parameter estimates scaled to a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. The analysis does not utilise settings based on Lohmoeller's recommendations, and a weighting scheme based on the paths in the structural model is employed. These settings ensure that the bootstrapping process effectively estimates the model parameters and assesses their significance, providing robust and reliable results for the PLS-SEM analysis. Figure 5.5 shows the graphical results of structural modelling, namely, path coefficients for latent variables and outer loadings of each indicator.

Figure 5. 5: Graphical Results of Main Structural Model

***p < 0.01; **p < 0.05; ns = not significant

Where CE= circular economy; SER= servitisation; I4.0= industry 4.0; CV= control variables; CER1=refuse; CER2= rethink; CER3= reduce; CER4= reuse; CER5= repair; CER6= refurbish; CER7= remanufacture; CER8= repurpose; CER9= recycle; CER10= recover; SER11= servitisation as a CE strategy; SER12= waste recovery for servitisation; SER13= minimise usage of virgin material, SER14= end-of-life practices/ reverse logistics; IND15= transparency and accountability; IND16=I4.0-enabled shared platform; IND17= Resource Efficiency IND18= extended lifecycle; IND19= functional efficacy; IND20= innovation through I4.0; IND21= monitoring resource Use; CBM22= circular business model; SCM23= supply chain management: reverse activities/logistics; CVP24= circular value proposition; IED25= investment of Eco-design; SDS26= statement on sustainable development strategy.

Table 5.15 presents the results of the structural model, showcasing the path coefficients, T-values, F-square values, p-values, and overall outcomes for each hypothesised effect which are as follows:

Table 5. 16: Results of Structural Model

Effect	Path Coefficients	T-Value	F-Square	P- Value	Results
SER -> CE	0.365	3.745	0.133	0.000***	Supported
I4.0 -> CE	0.175	0.087	0.028	0.931	Not Supported
I4.0 -> SER	0.592	14.624	0.540	0.000***	Supported
CV -> CE	0.212	1.664	0.042	0.096	Not Supported
I4.0 -> SER -> CE	0.216	3.620		0.000***	Supported
R²					
CE	0.418				
SER	0.351				
Adjusted R²					
CE	0.415				
SER	0.35				

Notes: ***p < 0.05; ns = not significant

Where, CE= circular economy, SER= servitisation, I4.0= industry 4.0, CV= control variables

5.12.1. Findings and Discussion on H1

H1: The adoption of servitisation positively effects the level of CE disclosures.

Table 5.16 demonstrates the results of structural modelling derived from PLS-SEM. The path coefficient measures the strength and direction of the relationship between the predictor variable (servitisation) and the outcome variable (CE). The path coefficient between servitisation and CE is 0.365, which indicates a positive relationship between these two constructs which means that the sample companies are reporting about using servitisation as a CE strategy. The t-value measures the statistical significance of the path coefficient. The t-value of 3.745 ($p < 0.001$) indicates that the relationship between servitisation and CE is statistically significant which means that companies reporting about using servitisation as CE strategy are leveraging the CE disclosure practices. The total effect of 0.398 (with a p-value of less than 0.001) from servitisation to CE suggests that increasing servitisation is associated with increasing CE practices. The f-square value of 0.133 indicates that servitisation explains approximately 13.3% of the variance in CE. The R^2 represents the proportion of variance in the dependent variable (CE) that can be explained by the independent variable (servitisation). An R^2 of 0.418 indicates that approximately 41.8% of the variance in the CE can be explained by servitisation. The direct effect of servitisation on CE (0.365) suggests that changes in servitisation directly lead to changes in CE practices. This effect is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The results of current study reveal a significant positive relationship between servitisation and CE, indicating that companies leveraging servitisation strategies are also adopting CE practices (Atif, 2023b, 2023a; Atif et al., 2021). This finding is consistent with the assertions in the literature regarding

the interplay between servitisation and CE as drivers for resource efficiency and sustainable business practices (Cagliano et al., 2017; Cainelli et al., 2020; Tukker, 2015). As highlighted in the literature review, servitisation and CE are often portrayed as complementary concepts contributing to resource reduction and increased product longevity (Scheel et al., 2020). Our findings support this notion by demonstrating a positive association between servitisation and CE, as evidenced by the path coefficient of 0.365. This suggests that companies adopting servitisation strategies will likely engage in CE practices such as closed-loop supply chains and resource efficiency initiatives (Reim et al., 2016, 2019).

Moreover, the literature emphasises the role of multi-stakeholder partnerships in fostering servitisation and CE initiatives, enabling organisations to gain a competitive advantage and create more efficient supply chain systems (Bustinza, Lafuente, et al., 2019). The results of current study align with these assertions, indicating that servitisation facilitates adopting CE practices through collaborative efforts with stakeholders (Baah et al., 2022; Freeman et al., 2021). This accentuates the importance of partnerships and collaborations in driving sustainability initiatives across value chains (M. Chen et al., 2022; Muller et al., 2022).

Additionally, the literature highlights the significance of extending the product lifecycle and implementing circular business models to capture the potential circular value of goods (Bressanelli et al., 2019b; Lieder et al., 2017). Thus, these findings support the creation of circular value proposition through servitisation by demonstrating a positive relationship between servitisation and CE, suggesting that servitisation contributes to CE by enabling product maintenance, repair, and reuse. This highlights the role of servitisation as a strategy for decreasing environmental risks and promoting sustainable consumption and production patterns (D'Agostin et al., 2020). Therefore, the current study provides empirical evidence to support the claims made in the literature regarding the relationship between servitisation and CE. By leveraging servitisation strategies, companies can enhance resource efficiency, reduce environmental impact, and drive sustainable growth.

5.12.2. Findings and Discussion on H2

H2: *The adoption of I4.0 positively effects the level of CE disclosures.*

The hypothesis regarding the relationship between I4.0 and CE may be rejected. Although a positive path coefficient of 0.175 suggests a direct impact of I4.0 on CE practices, the coefficient is relatively smaller compared to the relationship with servitisation. Furthermore, the total effect 1.199 from I4.0 to CE is not statistically significant, as indicated by the p-value greater than 0.05. This suggests that the original sample may not have a significant relationship between I4.0 and CE practices. The f-square

value of 0.028 indicates that I4.0 explains approximately 2% of the variance in CE. Additionally, the relatively low R2 value of 0.418 and the non-significant t-value of 0.087 further support the lack of a significant relationship between these variables. Therefore, based on these results, the hypothesis regarding the positive relationship between I4.0 and the CE may not be supported. These findings are contradicting with the claims made by Barnabè & Nazir (2021); Gunarathne et al. (2021); Opferkuch et al. (2022), (2023); Roberts et al. (2022) and Tiscini et al. (2022). demonstrate a company's commitment to sustainability and innovation, promoting accountability in its operations. It has been demonstrated that a company's dedication to sustainability and innovation may foster accountability challenges in its operations (Di Vaio et al., 2022). Although I4.0 is believed to significantly impact the development of CE initiatives, coherent and comprehensive disclosure practices related to I4.0 still need to be developed. The current study's results provide only a partial understanding of CE disclosure practices in the context of I4.0. The current study's findings stand in contrast to the propositions put forth by Rossi et al. (2020) and Chari et al. (2022). While Rossi et al. (2020) posited that leveraging I4.0 technologies in developing circular products would enhance environmental sustainability, our findings suggest otherwise. Similarly, Chari et al. (2022) advocated for manufacturers to focus on adaptability capability to bolster their value proposition and competitive advantage. However, our study's results present a different perspective on the relationship between adaptability capability and market competitiveness.

5.12.3. Findings and Discussion on H3

H3: The adoption of I4.0 technologies positively effects the level of servitisation in the disclosure practices, and vice versa.

The provided table 5.16 illustrates the path coefficient, t-value, F-square, p-value, and the results of the effect from I4.0 to servitisation. With a path coefficient of 0.592, indicating a positive relationship, and a remarkably high t-value of 14.624, the effect is statistically significant. The F-square value of 0.540 denotes that the effect explains 54% of the variance in the dependent variable. Furthermore, the p-value of 0.000*** confirms the significance of the relationship, supporting the hypothesis that there is indeed a positive and significant impact of I4.0 on servitisation. This finding aligns with the existing literature, emphasising the pivotal role of I4.0 technologies in facilitating the transition towards servitisation (Weking et al., 2020). As highlighted by Weking et al. (2020), firms in the I4.0 era face the challenge of managing vast amounts of data, necessitating the adoption of I4.0 technologies to derive valuable insights. The results corroborate this assertion, indicating that integrating I4.0 technologies contributes to advancing organisational servitisation initiatives. The literature review of

the current study has proposed that I4.0 technologies will augment CE reporting as data-driven circular products and CE disclosure index would help the practitioners to compute and visualise the results and impact of CE from design throughout the circular product's lifetime (the manufacturer will be aware of each part (s) and parameter (s) of a circular product that would eventually ease the developed CE disclosure index's applicability) which will facilitate their practicability and help them to uptake in industrial setup. Furthermore, the literature highlights the importance of leveraging digital technologies to extend the product lifecycle and close the loops in the CE (Okorie et al., 2021; Xia et al., 2022). Our findings support this notion by demonstrating that I4.0 technologies are crucial in operationalising circular product-consortium services and establishing performance indicators for efficiency and effectiveness (Isaksson et al., 2018). Additionally, the increasing use of digital functions has prompted firms to reconsider traditional approaches to order management and service development due to the complexity of modern information economics (Mourtzis et al., 2020). The current study's results provide empirical evidence of this trend, indicating that integrating I4.0 technologies fosters a paradigm shift in operational capabilities towards a more agile and adaptive approach.

Moreover, the literature highlights the significance of real-time analysis enabled by I4.0 technologies, particularly in big data analytics (Doni et al., 2019; Kohtamäki & Partanen, 2016b). Our findings support this assertion by demonstrating that utilising I4.0 technologies facilitates the analysis of unstructured data, enabling organisations to detect and mitigate risks in manufacturing activities (Reim et al., 2016). However, it is important to note that despite the potential benefits of big data analytics, many production systems still struggle to fully leverage the capabilities of smart devices (Frank, Dalenogare, et al., 2019). In conclusion, the current study provides empirical evidence of the positive and significant impact of I4.0 on servitisation, in line with the theoretical propositions outlined in the literature. By embracing I4.0 technologies, organisations can enhance their operational capabilities, extend the product lifecycle, and drive innovation in service delivery. However, challenges remain in fully harnessing the potential of big data analytics, underscoring the need for continued research and investment in technological infrastructure and capabilities.

5.12.4. Findings and Discussion on H4

H4: The combined adoption of servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies effects the level of CE reporting practices.

Table 5.16 depicts the outcomes of a path analysis model, which aims to elucidate the indirect impact of I4.0 on CE through servitisation mediation. Specifically, the path model posits that I4.0 -> SER -> CE

represents the indirect effect of I4.0 on CE, which Servitisation influences. The statement is in line with the assertion made by D'Amato et al. (2019) and Scarpellini et al. (2020) that I4.0-enabled shared platforms will prioritize co-creation and data-driven platforms, which will play a crucial role in promoting the CE approach. These platforms will extend the product's life cycle, assess the company's eco-friendly product efforts, stress eco-innovation and CE objectives, and help evaluate the company's eco-innovation practices and environmental compliance efforts.

The path coefficient of 0.216 reflects the strength and direction of this indirect relationship. This relationship is statistically significant, as indicated by a t-value of 3.620. Moreover, the p-value of 0.000*** confirms the statistical significance of the indirect effect of I4.0 on CE through SER. These findings denote a significant indirect effect of I4.0 on the CE through Servitisation, and the model result is interpreted as "Supported". However, there is not a statistically significant direct relationship between the CV and CE (0.212, $p < 0.001$). These results indicate that contrary to the findings of previous studies such as Nazir & Doni (2024); D. Rossi et al. (2024); Tiscini et al. (2022), which suggested that companies are improving their CE-related disclosures by implementing certain practices related to CE, such as enhancing their value propositions and sustainable development strategies and investing in circular/green initiatives and Fernando et al. (2023); N. M. Hassan et al. (2023); J. Liu & Lu (2023) regarding the synchronisation of circular SCM practices. This finding challenges the assumption that companies may not make necessary changes to selected CVs directly, resulting in lower possible CE disclosures. Therefore, further investigation may be warranted to understand the nuanced interplay between control variables and CE initiatives better. Moreover, the results of the current study alligns with the claims of Cenamor et al. (2017) which advocate for a platform approach to achieve servitisation through digitalisation, prompting the evaluation of firms employing low-cost data-driven management systems.

Moreover, the current study's findings contradict the claims made by D'Agostin et al. (2020) that I4.0 technologies are crucial for assessing circularity readiness and managing associated risks and that they represent a dynamic capability for firms. At the same time, these findings also contradict the statement made by Bressanelli et al. (2018) that I4.0 technologies facilitate residual value stewardship and align with the RBV perspective of leveraging internal resources for sustained competitive advantage. This strategic approach prioritises stakeholder interests and emphasises responsible and sustainable practices to meet societal expectations. The study highlights the importance of understanding how CE influences business performance, which highlights the focus of RBV and ST on long-term value creation and accountability. Thus, the findings substantiate the theoretical claims regarding the positive relationship between servitisation and CE. By adopting servitisation strategies, companies can enhance resource efficiency, reduce environmental impact, and achieve sustainable

growth, in line with ST emphasising the importance of partnerships and multi-stakeholder collaborations.

5.13. Robust Analysis

In the robust analysis, two additional models will be presented to explore further the relationship of the trio-combination of CE, Servitisation, and I4.0. These models will investigate the impact of the trio-combination under two different conditions: with control variables (CV) and without control variables. The researcher believes that the results of these analyses will provide valuable insights into the nuanced effects of the trio-combination on the company's disclosure practices, helping to elucidate the mechanisms underlying these relationships and informing future research and practical implications. Therefore, for robust analysis, the researcher has divided the dependent variable (CE) into three 3 sub-sets which are based on the distinct stages of the CE-10R strategy, and the corresponding activities associated with each phase ¹³to test the influence of servitisation and I4.0 on each phase. Therefore, two additional models were run to test six effects (E1-E6), the details are as follows:

5.13.1. Sub-Sets of CE

The researcher has divided the dependent variable, CE, into three sub-sets based on the distinct stages of the CE-10R strategy. Each subset corresponds to specific activities associated with each phase of the strategy. This division allows the researcher to test the influence of Servitisation and I4.0 on each phase individually.

- **CE-Phase 1: Circular Design (R1: refuse, R2: rethink, R3: reduce)**

This phase focuses on the initial design and development of products and processes with CE principles. The emphasis of this stage is believed to minimising waste and resource consumption from the outset through strategies such as refusal, rethinking product design, and reducing material usage. The rationale behind this phase lies in recognising that sustainable and circular practices should be integrated into the design phase to maximise their impact on resource efficiency and waste reduction. The resource-based view (RBV) theory elaborates on this phase, emphasising the importance of developing sustainable products and processes that efficiently use resources and minimise waste.

¹³ The researcher ran the model for each component of the latent variables, namely CE (10 constructs), servitisation (4 constructs), and I4.0 (7 constructs), both with and without the constructs of CV (5 constructs). Due to the large amount of data, which included components of each latent variable, the researcher has presented the most impactful results.

- **CE-Phase 2: Responsible Consumption and Production (R4: reuse, R5: repair, R6: refurbish, R7: remanufacture, R8: repurpose)**

This phase involves post-manufacturing activities aimed at prolonging the life cycle of products and minimising waste generation. Activities such as reuse, repair, refurbishment, remanufacturing, and repurposing contribute to resource conservation and create additional value through servitisation. The rationale behind this phase is to highlight the importance of dynamic capabilities theory (DCT) in enabling manufacturers to develop effective processes and strategies for responsible consumption and production. DCT emphasises a firm's ability to adapt and change in response to environmental and social conditions, which is crucial for developing strategies that reduce environmental impact and promote social responsibility in the consumption and production phase.

- **CE-Phase 3: Return of Used Product (R9: recycle, R10: recover):**

This phase focuses on the end-of-life stage of products, where used products are returned to the manufacturer for recycling and recovery of materials. It involves adopting I4.0 technologies and the servitisation BM to optimise resource utilisation and promote sustainability in reverse logistics operations. This phase's rationale addresses environmental and economic concerns related to the return of used products, considering ST perspectives. ST emphasises the importance of considering the interests of all stakeholders, including customers, employees, suppliers, and the environment, in developing sustainable and responsible strategies for returning used products to the economy.

5.13.2. Models

The researcher has prepared two additional models to comprehensively understand the relationship between CE, servitisation, and I4.0 to uncover the mechanisms underlying their affiliations.

- Model 1: Trio-Combination of CE, Servitisation and I4.0 with CV.
- Model 2: Trio-Combination of CE, Servitisation and I4.0 without CV

5.13.3. Effects

The effects listed below describe the relationships between Servitisation, I4.0, and CE phases, with and without the assistance of CV.

- **Effect 1 (E1):** *Servitisation with the assistance of CV has a positive impact on CE-Phase 1 (R1: Reuse, R2: Rethink and R3: Reduce).*
- **Effect 2 (E2):** *Servitisation with the assistance of CV has a positive impact on CE-Phase 2 (R4: Reuse, R5: Repair, R6: Refurbish, R7: Remanufacture, R8: Repurpose).*

- **Effect 3 (E3):** Servitisation with the assistance of CV has a positive impact on CE-Phase 3 (R9: Recycle, R10: Recover).
- **Effect 4 (E4):** I4.0 with the assistance of CV has a positive impact on CE-Phase 1 (R1: Reuse, R2: Rethink and R3: Reduce).
- **Effect 5 (E5):** I4.0 with the assistance of CV has a positive impact on CE-Phase 2 (R4: Reuse, R5: Repair, R6: Refurbish, R7: Remanufacture, R8: Repurpose).
- **Effect 6 (E6):** I4.0 with the assistance of CV has a positive impact on CE-Phase 3 (R9: Recycle, R10: Recover).

5.13.4. Results of Model 1: Trio-Combination of CE, Servitisation and I4.0 with CV

The first model will assess the relationship of the trio-combination of CE, Servitisation, and I4.0 while considering the influence of CV (results are presented in Figure 5.6). This model aims to understand how the trio-combination interacts with and influences the company's disclosure practices while considering the potential confounding effects of control variables.

Figure 5. 6: Results of Structural Model for 1

Where , CE-Phase 1= R1: Reuse, R2: Rethink and R3: Reduce; CE-Phase 2= R4: Reuse, R5: Repair, R6: Refurbish, R7: Remanufacture, R8: Repurpose; CE-Phase 3= R9: Recycle, R10: Recover; SER= servitisation; I4.0= industry 4.0; CV= control variables; CER1=refuse; CER2= rethink; CER3= reduce; CER4= reuse; CER5= repair; CER6= refurbish; CER7= remanufacture; CER8= repurpose; CER9= recycle; CER10= recover; SER11= servitisation as a CE strategy; SER12= waste recovery for servitisation; SER13= minimise usage of virgin material, SER14= end-of-life practices/ reverse logistics; IND15= transparency and accountability; IND16=I4.0-enabled shared platform; IND17= Resource Efficiency IND18= extended lifecycle; IND19= functional efficacy; IND20= innovation through I4.0; IND21= monitoring resource Use; CBM22= circular business model; SCM23= supply chain management: reverse activities/logistics; VPP24= circular value proposition; IED25= investment of Eco-design; SDS26= statement on sustainable development strategy.

Table 5. 17: Results of Structural Model 1

	Effect	Path Coefficients	T-Value	P- Value	Results
E1	CE-Phase 1 -> SER -> CV	0.254	4.818	0.000***	Significant
E2	CE-Phase 2 -> SER -> CV	0.262	5.784	0.000***	Significant
E3	CE-Phase 3 -> SER -> CV	0.121	6.278	0.000***	Significant
E4	CE-Phase 1 -> I4.0 -> CV	0.218	3.166	0.002***	Significant
E5	CE-Phase 2 -> I4.0 -> CV	0.121	2.204	0.028***	Significant
E6	CE-Phase 3 -> I4.0 -> CV	0.056	0.875	0.381	Not Significant

Notes: ***p < 0.05; ns = not significant

Where, CE-Phase 1= R1: Reuse, R2: Rethink and R3: Reduce; CE-Phase 2= R4: Reuse, R5: Repair, R6: Refurbish, R7: Remanufacture, R8: Repurpose; CE-Phase 3= R9: Recycle, R10: Recover; SER= servitisation; I4.0= industry 4.0 and CV=control variables.

The following table 5.17 displays the outcomes of the path analysis, containing the path coefficients, t-values, p-values, and the corresponding significance levels for each effect examined in the model. It can be observed from the table that the initial path (**E1**) indicates a significant positive correlation between activities in CE-Phase 1 (Reuse, Rethink, and Reduce) and Servitisation while controlling for CV. The path coefficient is 0.254, which means that a one-unit increase in CE-Phase 1 activities leads to a 0.254-unit rise in Servitisation, given that other variables are constant in their disclosure practices. These results are consistent with Doni et al., (2019), suggesting servitisation enhances environmental performance by leveraging responsible production and consumption. In this respect, the suggestion presented by Nazir & Doni (2024) was also asserted, as the results verify that service disclosure practices lead to circularity initiatives by repairing, reusing, repurposing, and recycling products. Additionally, the following path (**E2**) reveals similar outcomes, indicating a significant positive correlation between activities in CE-Phase 2 (Reuse, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture, and Repurpose) and Servitisation while controlling for CV. The path coefficient is 0.262, indicating that CE-Phase 2 activities have a slightly stronger impact on Servitisation than CE-Phase 1. However, in the case of the following path (**E3**), there is a significant positive relationship between CE-Phase 3 (Recycle and Recover) activities and Servitisation while controlling for CV. Still, the path coefficient (0.121) is less than CE-Phase 1 and CE-Phase 2, indicating a relatively weaker effect of CE-Phase 3 activities on Servitisation. Moreover, in **E4**, a significant positive correlation exists between CE-Phase 1 activities and I4.0 activities while controlling for CV. The path coefficient is 0.218, implying that CE-Phase 1 activities positively influence I4.0 adoption. Similarly, while heading for CV, **E5** shows a significant positive correlation between CE-Phase 2 and I4.0 activities. However, the path coefficient (0.121) is less than CE-Phase 1, suggesting a weaker impact of CE-Phase 2 activities on I4.0 adoption. Lastly, **E6** has no significant relationship between CE-Phase 3 and I4.0 activities while controlling for CV. The p-

value (0.381) is greater than 0.05, indicating that CE-Phase 3 activities do not significantly influence I4.0 adoption. These results are aligned with the conclusion presented by Tiwari & Khan (2020) that the need for investments in sustainability projects and sustainable accounting and reporting has created several challenges. In response, some countries have established standards for implementing CE principles in organisations and monitoring strategies. However, these standards are still in the early stages of implementation and must provide clear guidelines for sustainable accounting and reporting (Scarpellini, 2022).

The findings contradict the DCT theoretical framework, which suggests that I4.0 mediates the impact of ESG (Felsberger et al., 2022). The results of the current study align with the conclusion presented in the research by Hafezi & Zolfagharinia (2018) that the idea of creating circular products highlights the need for manufacturers to possess dynamic capabilities. They must devise and craft efficient and intelligent procedures that boost capability to fulfil demand by utilising resources after the manufacturing phase, minimising waste, and co-creating additional value through a servitisation approach (Bressanelli et al., 2018a). Based on the research findings, CE-Phase 1 and CE-Phase 2 activities significantly positively impact both Servitisation and I4.0 adoption. However, the impact of CE-Phase 3 activities could be stronger and more significant for I4.0 adoption. Moreover, when controlling for CV, the significance of the relationships observed becomes stronger. In addition, the R^2 for CE-Phase 1 is 0.329, indicating that the independent variables included in the model explain approximately 32.9% of the variance in CE-Phase 1 activities (Reuse, Rethink, and Reduce). This suggests that the model accounts for a moderate amount of variability in the Circular Design phase of the CE-10R strategy.

Similarly, the R^2 for CE-Phase 2 is 0.210, indicating that the independent variables explain approximately 21.0% of the variance in CE-Phase 2 activities (Reuse, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture, and Repurpose). This suggests that the model captures moderate variability in the CE framework's Responsible Consumption and Production phase. Finally, the R^2 for CE-Phase 3 is 0.248, indicating that the independent variables explain approximately 24.8% of the variance in CE-Phase 3 activities (Recycle and Recover). This suggests that the model explains moderate variability in the CE strategy's Return of the Used Product phase. While the models for each phase of the CE strategy do explain a moderate amount of variability in their respective activities, a significant portion of the variance may be linked to Nazir & Doni (2024) claim that firms which proactively embrace sustainability and service innovation are better positioned to capture market share, attract investment, and outperform competitors in the long run. Ultimately, this drives business growth and success. The current study's findings provide additional evidence to support the assertion made by Alkaraan et al. (2022) who discovered that strategic investment decision-making (SIDM) practices for

CTTI4.0 have increased over time and differ across various industry sectors. The researchers also established that I4.0 disclosure has a favourable effect on financial performance. Thus, this indicates that CV captured by the model (CBM22, SCM23, CVP24, IED25 and SDS25) may influence the activities within each phase of the CE strategy (Castilla-Polo & Sánchez-Hernández, 2022; Xu et al., 2021). These findings support the idea that governments regulate compliance with sustainability goals, influencing corporate strategies (Kuo & Chang, 2021). Validating the fact that sample companies are adopting proactive approaches to sustainability and service innovation, firms can enhance their resilience and adaptability in an ever-changing business landscape (Simmou et al., 2022).

5.13.5. Results of Model 2: Trio-Combination of CE, Servitisation and I4.0 without CV

The second model examines the trio-combination of CE, Servitisation, and I4.0 without considering the influence of control variables. This model allows for a more focused analysis of the direct relationship between the trio-combination and the company's disclosure practices without the potential impact of external factors represented by CV.

Figure 5. 7: Results of Structural Model for 2

Where , CE-Phase 1= R1: Reuse, R2: Rethink and R3: Reduce; CE-Phase 2= R4: Reuse, R5: Repair, R6: Refurbish, R7: Remanufacture, R8: Repurpose; CE-Phase 3= R9: Recycle, R10: Recover; SER= servitisation; I4.0= industry 4.0; CER1=refuse; CER2= rethink; CER3= reduce; CER4= reuse; CER5= repair; CER6= refurbish; CER7= remanufacture; CER8= repurpose; CER9= recycle; CER10= recover; SER11= servitisation as a CE strategy; SER12= waste recovery for servitisation; SER13= minimise usage of virgin material, SER14= end-of-life practices/ reverse logistics; IND15= transparency and accountability; IND16=I4.0-enabled shared platform; IND17= Resource Efficiency IND18= extended lifecycle; IND19= functional efficacy; IND20= innovation through I4.0; IND21= monitoring resource Use; CBM22= circular business model; SCM23= supply chain management: reverse activities/logistics; CVP24= circular value proposition; IED25= investment of Eco-design; SDS26= statement on sustainable development strategy.

Table 5. 18: Results of Structural Model for 2

	Effect	Path Coefficients	T-Value	P- Value	Results	Results
E1	CE-Phase 1 -> SER w/o CV	0.314	6.077	0.000***	0.314	Significant
E2	CE-Phase 2 -> SER w/o CV	0.304	6.912	0.000***	0.304	Significant
E3	CE-Phase 3 -> SER w/o CV	0.410	7.229	0.000***	0.410	Significant
E4	CE-Phase 1 -> I4.0 w/o CV	0.309	5.578	0.000***	0.309	Significant
E5	CE-Phase 2 -> I4.0 w/o CV	0.189	4.272	0.000***	0.189	Significant
E6	CE-Phase 3 -> I4.0 w/o CV	0.116	1.981	0.048***	0.116	Significant

Notes: ***p < 0.05; ns = not significant

Where, CE-Phase 1= R1: Reuse, R2: Rethink and R3: Reduce; CE-Phase 2= R4: Reuse, R5: Repair, R6: Refurbish, R7: Remanufacture, R8: Repurpose; CE-Phase 3= R9: Recycle, R10: Recover; SER= servitisation; I4.0= industry 4.0; w/o= without and CV=control variables.

The following table 5.18 shows the path analysis results conducted to test CE phases' effects on Servitisation and I4.0 adoption without control variables. The analysis focused on the relationships between CE-Phases, Servitisation, and I4.0. The findings indicate a positive relationship between CE-Phase 1 activities (Reuse, Rethink, and Reduce) and Servitisation without control variables (**E1**). The path coefficient is 0.314, indicating a positive influence of CE-Phase 1 on Servitisation. The results of current study are consistent with those suggested by Sihvonen & Partanen (2017), who argued that the term "reuse" is frequently used in environmental reporting. These findings contradict the claims made by Barreiro-Gen & Lozano (2020), who asserted that organisations prioritise reduction and recycling over repair and remanufacturing. Similarly, the current study found a significant positive relationship between CE-Phase 2 activities (Reuse, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture, and Repurpose) and Servitisation without control variables (**E2**). The path coefficient is 0.304, indicating that CE-Phase 2 positively influences Servitisation. This is consistent with Sihvonen & Partanen (2017) highlighted that environmental reports increasingly feature repair, refurbishment, and remanufacturing to promote sustainability. These results support the argument that firms that adopt sustainable practices and prioritise service innovation are better positioned to outperform competitors, capture market share, and achieve long-term business growth and success (Dagiliene et al., 2020; López-Cubillos et al., 2022). Furthermore, the CE-Phase 3 activities (Recycle and Recover) also show a significant positive relationship with Servitisation without control variables (**E3**). The path coefficient is 0.410, indicating that CE-Phase 3 positively influences Servitisation. These findings support Scarpellini (2022) claims, indicating that common indicators of CE include the amount of waste generated and diverted away from landfills, the proportion of materials recycled or reused, and the percentage of products engineered for longevity. Additionally, the analysis found that CE-Phase 1 activities have a significant positive relationship with I4.0 adoption without control variables (**E4**). The path coefficient is 0.309,

suggesting a positive influence of CE-Phase 1 on I4.0 adoption. Similarly, the study found that CE-Phase 2 activities have a significant positive relationship with I4.0 adoption without control variables **(E5)**. The path coefficient is 0.189, indicating that CE-Phase 2 positively influences I4.0 adoption. Finally, CE-Phase 3 activities have a significant positive relationship with I4.0 adoption without control variables, although the significance is marginal ($p = 0.048$). The path coefficient is 0.116, indicating a weaker but still positive influence of CE-Phase 3 on I4.0 adoption **(E6)**.

In addition, the analysis revealed that R^2 for CE-Phase 1 is 0.308, meaning that the independent variables included in the model account for approximately 30.8% of the variance in CE-Phase 1 activities (Reuse, Rethink, and Reduce). R^2 for CE-Phase 2 is 0.196, indicating that the independent variables explain approximately 19.6% of the variance in CE-Phase 2 activities (Reuse, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture, and Repurpose). Finally, R^2 for CE-Phase 3 is 0.238, suggesting that the independent variables explain approximately 23.8% of the variance in CE-Phase 3 activities (Recycle and Recover). The findings suggest that all phases of the CE strategy are positively impacted by Servitisation and I4.0 adoption in the absence of control variables in promoting sustainable and innovative business practices. These findings are consistent with the RBV theoretical framework, which emphasises utilising and harnessing valuable, rare, and inimitable resources to achieve sustainable competitive advantage (Kozlenkova et al., 2014; Zahra, 2021).

The theoretical perspective suggests that the CE phase focusing on the end-of-life stage of products, with the return of used products for recycling and recovery, involves adopting I4.0 technologies and the servitisation BM. This integration optimises resource utilisation and promotes sustainability in reverse logistics operations. This phase's rationale addresses environmental and economic concerns, aligning with ST perspectives Al-Shaer et al., (2022).

However, these findings contrast with Bressanelli et al. (2018) statement that I4.0 technologies facilitate residual value stewardship and align with the Resource-Based View (RBV) perspective, leveraging internal resources for sustained competitive advantage. Instead, the strategic approach prioritises stakeholder interests and emphasises responsible and sustainable practices to meet societal expectations. This study highlights the importance of understanding how CE influences business performance, highlighting the focus of RBV and ST on long-term value creation and accountability.

In conclusion, while I4.0 technologies and the servitisation BM are instrumental in optimising resource utilisation and promoting sustainability in reverse logistics operations, their effectiveness in facilitating residual value stewardship and ensuring long-term competitive advantage may depend on the alignment with responsible and sustainable practices, as emphasised by ST. This highlights the

importance of considering stakeholder interests and societal expectations in shaping CE strategies for sustainable business performance.

5.14. Summary of Results of Statistical Models

This study investigates the relationship between CE, servitisation, I4.0, and CV among manufacturing companies over five years (2018-2022). It uses a main model to test hypothesised relationships between H1-H4. Moreover, it conducts a robustness analysis to test the effects of E1 to E6 using both Model 1 and Model 2. Table 5.19 provides a detailed overview of the study's findings, summarising the statistical results for the main model and the robustness analysis for both Model 1 and Model 2.

Table 5. 19: Summary of Results of Statistical Models

H/E	CE-Phase 1	CE-Phase 2	CE-Phase 3	Servitisation	I4.0	CV	Result
Main Model							
H1	Included	Included	Included	Included	Excluded	Included	Significant
H2	Included	Included	Included	Excluded	Included	Included	Significant
H3	Excluded	Excluded	Excluded	Included	Included	Included	Not Significant
H4	Included	Included	Included	Included	Included	Included	Significant
Robust Model 1							
E1	Included	Excluded	Excluded	Included	Excluded	Included	Significant
E2	Excluded	Included	Excluded	Included	Excluded	Included	Significant
E3	Excluded	Excluded	Included	Included	Excluded	Included	Significant
E4	Included	Excluded	Excluded	Excluded	Included	Included	Significant
E5	Excluded	Included	Excluded	Excluded	Included	Included	Significant
E6	Excluded	Excluded	Included	Excluded	Included	Included	Not Significant
Robust Model 2							
E1	Included	Excluded	Excluded	Included	Excluded	Excluded	Significant
E2	Excluded	Included	Excluded	Included	Excluded	Excluded	Significant
E3	Excluded	Excluded	Included	Included	Excluded	Excluded	Significant
E4	Included	Excluded	Excluded	Excluded	Included	Excluded	Significant
E5	Excluded	Included	Excluded	Excluded	Included	Excluded	Significant
E6	Excluded	Excluded	Included	Excluded	Included	Excluded	Significant

Where, H/E= hypothesis/effect; H1= Hypothesis 1; H2= hypothesis 2; H3= hypothesis 3; H4= hypothesis 4; E1= effect 1; E2= effect 2; E3= effect 3; E4=effect 4; E5=effect 5 and E6= effect 6; CE-Phase 1= R1: Reuse, R2: Rethink and R3: Reduce; CE-Phase 2= R4: Reuse, R5: Repair, R6: Refurbish, R7: Remanufacture, R8: Repurpose; CE-Phase 3= R9: Recycle, R10: Recover; SER= servitisation; I4.0= industry 4.0; CV= control variables.

5.15. Chapter Summary

The current study has developed a CE disclosure index and used it to conduct a systematic content analysis. This methodology caters to quantitative and qualitative analysis. The researcher used SPSS version 29.0 to test and conduct a preliminary analysis of the variables. After conducting measurement models, the reliability assessment revealed strong internal consistency among the latent variables (CE, servitisation, I4.0, and CV). Cronbach's alpha coefficients ranged from 0.710 to 0.822, and composite reliability coefficients from 0.724 to 0.854. The average variance extracted (AVE) results indicated good reliability, ranging from 0.633 to 0.688. Validity tests, including HTMT values and correlation analysis, confirmed acceptable discriminant and construct validity. Collinearity assessment showed normal distribution for CE but deviation for servitisation, I4.0, and CV. Normality tests demonstrated normal distribution for CE, I4.0, and control variables but non-normal distribution for servitisation. Goodness-of-fit analysis, encompassing KMO, Chi-square, SRMR, and NFI statistics, suggested a relatively good fit for the model measures, with KMO at 0.803, Chi-square at 1345.359, SRMR at 0.076, and NFI at 0.683. These findings affirm the PLS-SEM analysis's reliability, validity, and model fit.

Additionally, the structural data analysis was mainly descriptive since the data was revealed to be non-normal. Furthermore, PLS-SEM was used to assess the significance of servitisation and I4.0 being used as a strategy in global Fortune 500 companies examining their disclosure practices. The current study formulated a model to gain constructive insights through research hypotheses (H1-H4). Specifically, the fourth research objective (RO4) aims to evaluate the impact of combining CE, Servitisation, and I4.0, including the control variables. This will be done by analysing the company's disclosure practices related to the effects and transition practices associated with this combination. Additionally, the fourth research question (RQ4) aims to analyse the company's reporting practices on the effects and transition practices related to this combination to provide constructive information on its impact. The statistical results support a positive and direct relationship between CE, servitisation, I4.0 and control variables to answer RQ4. However, there is not a statistically significant direct relationship between the CV and CE (0.212, $p < 0.001$). Hence, the interplay between CE, servitisation, and I4.0 is evident from their collective influence on CE disclosure practices. While each construct individually contributes to CE, their combined effect (CE+servitisation+I4.0) will likely be more significant in driving sustainable business practices.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

6.1. Introduction

This chapter provides a comprehensive summary of the key findings obtained from the analysis of the current study. Section (2) presents the research findings according to each objective and question, discussing how these findings contribute to the existing knowledge of CE-related reporting practices. Section (3) demonstrates the implications of the current study. Section (4) discusses the limitations experienced by the researcher during the research process and presents opportunities for future researchers to build on the current study's findings.

6.2. Conclusion

The current study investigates the relationship among CE, Servitisation, and I4.0 technologies and how they are reported among Global Fortune 500 companies. The study is motivated by the potential of integrating these concepts to enhance business sustainability and competitiveness. The problem addressed is the increasing popularity of sustainability reporting among corporations and the need for a clear approach to report on CE integration with servitisation and I4.0 being used as CE strategies. The complexity of existing metrics and frameworks, such as GRI standards (which capture waste management aspects of CE), Circulytics (which poses management biases and partially captures sector-specific challenges), and LSE (which requires consistency that can restrict the exploration of new materials), poses challenges for businesses. These challenges lead to concerns about greenwashing. The researcher identified a gap in the need for a holistic framework for CE-related reporting practices. This indicates a need for developing a robust framework to properly monitor and report CE performance from the early design phase of a circular product through its entire lifecycle, across various industrial sectors. Thus, embedding environmentally responsible practices into servitisation strategies and developing effective tools to distinguish genuine CE practices from false reporting (greenwashing) seems crucial. Therefore, the current study aims to develop a CE disclosure index that could effectively monitor companies' implementation and reporting practices throughout a circular product's lifecycle. This index will cover CE's 10R strategies (used to classify the CE reporting parameters that measure the CE impact), servitisation, and I4.0 as integral components of the CE strategy. The research methodology comprises three steps: (i) establishing relationships between key variables (CE, servitisation, and I4.0); (ii) developing a CE disclosure index, which includes the items of 10R strategies of CE, items of servitisation to detect if servitisation is being used to bring back used/discarded products into the cycle. I4.0 items to detect the role of I4.0 items is to detect the circular, data-driven, and stakeholder-oriented approach to facilitate CE indicators and the features

of CE that need to be reconfigured to ease the transition towards circularity; (iii) conducting measurement and statistical analysis using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The adopted methodology caters to both quantitative and qualitative analysis. Four research objectives (RO1-RO4) and associated research questions (RQ1-RQ4) were formulated to accomplish this research aim, concentrating on investigating the adoption, extent of disclosure methods, and impact analysis of integrating CE, servitisation, and I4.0.

6.2.1. Main Findings of RO1

Research Objective 1 (RO1): *To explore and explain the interconnectedness of CE, servitisation, and I4.0 by analysing the adoption of I4.0 technologies and implementation of servitisation as a CE strategy.*

Research Question 1 (RQ1): *How can the synergy between servitisation and I4.0 technologies be leveraged as a CE strategy by the manufacturing industry?*

The researcher set RO1, which delved into integrating I4.0 as a CE strategy, unveiling its potential to modernise manufacturing processes and drive sustainability initiatives forward. The findings (covered in headings 2.1-2.9 of Chapter 2: Literature review) illuminated the transformative power of digital technologies, particularly I4.0, in optimising resource utilisation, enhancing operational efficiency, and fostering environmental stewardship within manufacturing contexts. This study's culmination highlights the significance of integrating reverse-logistics perspectives within servitisation and harnessing the potential of I4.0 as a pivotal component of a comprehensive CE strategy. The researcher rigorously pursued the first research objective (RO1), leading to valuable insights into the nexus between CE, servitisation, and I4.0 and their collective influence on sustainability and business performance. The literature review was crucial in helping the researcher establish relationships among latent variables (CE, servitisation, and I4.0). Reviewing existing literature, the researcher gained insights into how these concepts are interconnected and contribute to sustainability and competitiveness in business practices, developing a theoretical framework for understanding the integration of servitisation and I4.0 as integral components of CE strategy.

The overall findings of the literature review discussed the emergence of the CE as a critical component of sustainability reporting (Ivic et al., 2021; Opferkuch et al., 2022; Tiscini et al., 2022). However, companies often need more systematic reporting of their commitments towards using servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies within their disclosure practices. The CE disclosures refer to the information that companies present in their sustainability reports regarding their ESG impacts related to CE practices. This includes outlining efforts to minimise waste, enhance resource efficiency, and foster

CLSC systems across their operations, supply chains, and products (Roberts, Georgiou, et al., 2022). It has been observed that most of the prior studies agree that CE may manifest in diverse formats, including quantitative metrics, narrative explanations, case studies, or visual depictions (Sihvonen & Partanen, 2017; Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020). Common circular economy indicators focus on diverting the waste generated and diverted from landfills (GRI). However, these indicators use complicated metrics that can be easily misreported. They measure the proportion of materials that are recycled or reused (LCA) and the likelihood of misconduct in reporting the proportion of products designed for durability (Circulytics) (Dagiliene et al., 2020). A comprehensive framework for disclosing information about companies' CE practices has been observed to ensure their ability to demonstrate commitment towards promoting sustainability and enhancing transparency and accountability (Scarpellini et al., 2020).

Moreover, it has been observed from the literature review that CE has often been regarded as a major catalyst of economic growth and development across developed and developing economies (Brown and Lee, 2019; Tykkyläinen, 2019). However, there has been a limited focus on understanding how businesses integrate CE principles into their operational frameworks and how they disclose the effects and implementation of CE transitions (Roberts et al., 2022). Previous research in this area has predominantly concentrated on Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) (Quick & Inwinkl, 2020; Adhikari Parajuli et al., 2021; Al-Shaer et al., 2022; Yu, et al., 2022), with relatively less attention paid to CE strategies. Additionally, prior studies that have explored CE have often been confined to specific countries such as China (Yang et al., 2019; Yu, et al., 2022), India (Singh et al., 2021), and Sri Lanka (Gunarathne et al., 2021), relying on case studies (Opferkuch et al., 2022; Zheng et al., 2022). Therefore, the key takeaway from the literature review is the pressing need for a comprehensive disclosure index that accurately measures and reports circularity metrics. This includes circular design, responsible production and consumption, and progress towards CE transition. Recognising this need, our study contributes by constructing a self-developed CE disclosure index guided by the 10R strategy of CE.

6.2.2. Main Findings of RO2

Research Objective 2 (RO2): To investigate the frequency and depth of CE, servitisation and I4.0's reporting practices by Global Fortune 500 listed companies

Research Question 2 (RQ2): *What is the frequency and extent of CE, servitisation, and I4.0 reporting practices in the sustainability reports of Global Fortune 500 companies?*

RO2 focused on investigating the extent of disclosure practices related to CE, servitisation, and I4.0 by Global Fortune 500 listed companies. The researcher identified a gap in the literature regarding a harmonised and internationally acknowledged framework for CE reporting. The researcher realised that the global market must have a globally accepted index/framework that consistently measures CE implementation and sets benchmarks. Once in place, this index would enable companies to report the extent and depth of their CE transition to a wider range of stakeholders for a more transparent and sustainable future. It would also be beneficial for investors, as it would allow companies to maintain a check and balance regarding the CE transition. Thus, this objective aimed to assess the current state of disclosure practices concerning the latent variables (CE, servitisation and I4.0). Therefore, the researcher set the RQ2 to align with RO2. Synthesising the role of servitisation as a CE strategy revealed its instrumental function in promoting sustainability across various business domains (by assessing the role of servitisation and I4.0 being used as CE strategies). For example, manufacturers in the sample shifted towards a service-oriented model, which led to fostering resource efficiency and waste reduction through digitalisation. The researcher presented the results of disclosure practices using four levels of analysis: (i) the extent of overall CE, servitisation, I4.0, and CV; (ii) the overall frequencies of CE, servitisation, I4.0, and CV; (iii) the frequencies of CE, servitisation, I4.0, and CV disclosures by scores, and (iv) the yearly frequencies of CE, servitisation, I4.0, and CV disclosures.

Level 1: The extent of overall CE, servitisation, I4.0, and CV: Level 1 presents a comprehensive analysis of the extent to which Global Fortune 500 companies have disclosed information related to latent variables (CE, servitisation, I4.0) over five years (2018-2022). The analysis reveals several noteworthy trends over the five years. Firstly, the CE constructs exhibit a steady increase, indicating an upward trend in the disclosure of CE-related practices. Similarly, the extent of servitisation constructs shows a momentum-driven increase over the years despite some fluctuations in variability. This suggests a growing emphasis on integrating servitisation practices within the CE framework, indicating that companies are committed to embracing servitisation as a viable business model within their sustainability reports. This is consistent with the idea that servitisation acts as a catalyst for organisations to adopt more transparent and responsible CE-related disclosure practices. Likewise,

the analysis of I4.0 constructs also revealed a significant and consistent upward trend over the five years. This indicates growing importance and increasing disclosure of I4.0-related practices within CE reporting practices, suggesting that companies use I4.0 as a CE strategy for leveraging strategic economic goals, social benefits, and innovative environmental objectives. Lastly, the findings related a similar upward trend within CV constructs, highlighting a positive trajectory in the CE-related disclosure practices over the years studied. These trends suggest a concerted effort by companies to embrace sustainability and circularity within their operations. It won't be wrong to claim that disclosing CE implementation ensures all stakeholders' interests are considered (this aligns with the ST that organisations adopt different frameworks to create value for all stakeholders). Additionally, these findings reinforce the proposition by Chen et al. (2022) that the quality of environmental cost disclosure requires enhancement. These insights of the level 1 analysis aids to the comprehension of the evolving landscape of sustainable business practices and provide valuable information for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers alike.

Level 2: The overall frequencies of CE, servitisation, I4.0, and CV: The second level analysis examined the frequency of CE disclosures by scores, demonstrating a significant improvement in the extent and quality of CE reporting practices from 2018 to 2022. The findings reveal that there has been a notable shift towards more verifiable disclosure practices, with an increasing proportion of companies falling into higher categories (2 and 3). This indicates a trend towards providing more comprehensive and reliable CE-related disclosures. Similarly, the disclosure levels for servitisation initiatives have consistently increased, albeit at a slightly lower proportion compared to CE. The disclosure levels for I4.0 initiatives also show a general upward trend, although less pronounced than for CE and servitisation constructs. The findings revealed that there has been a gradual improvement in reporting on I4.0-related initiatives, and the analysis of CV items further reinforces the increasing trend in the quality of CE disclosures over the years. The growing number of CE disclosures shows enhanced quality and comprehensive reporting on sustainability and CE efforts. This reflects an increasing dedication among companies to transparency, responsible business practices, and being held accountable. These findings are consistent with Gupta et al. (2021), highlighting the need for companies to balance innovation with environmental accountability. The increasing trend and its impact are important for all involved parties and should be recognised. Additionally, the results show that reporting practices related to corporate environmentalism are gaining popularity in sustainability reports within the manufacturing industry. This highlights the importance of embracing a comprehensive, long-term approach to business operations that considers corporate activities' ESG impacts, as advocated by Yu et al. (2022) and Chen et al. (2022). Overall, the research outcomes of level 2 coherent with the

findings of Barreiro-Gen & Lozano (2020) and Opferkuch et al. (2022). However, they contrast with the conclusions of Gunarathne et al. (2021) and Dagiliene et al. (2020), who asserted that environmental management actions do not directly incorporate CE principles and that CE disclosures remain low.

Level 3: The frequencies of CE, servitisation, I4.0, and CV disclosures by scores: The third level analysis provides a detailed breakdown of the frequencies of each construct of CE, servitisation, I4.0, and CV disclosure practices, revealing valuable insights into the distribution of responses across different categories. The findings reflect a significant proportion of companies disclosing CE and Resource Management information. This pattern persists across all constructs (CE, servitisation, I4.0 and CV), with varying frequencies and percentages for each score category, highlighting the nuanced nature of disclosure practices among sample companies. However, the analysis also reveals notable pattern variations across CE, servitisation, I4.0 and CV constructs. The findings indicate that many companies provide a substantial proportion of CE-related disclosures. Overall, the findings provide a comprehensive overview of score distribution for each construct, facilitating a deeper understanding of disclosure practices and highlighting areas where companies may need to enhance their reporting to align with evolving sustainability expectations and standards. The positive pattern in CE-related disclosure practices demonstrates that manufacturing companies are leveraging disruptive technologies and reconsidering their business strategies for more stable revenue models. These research outcomes are coherent with the conclusions of Barnabè & Nazir (2021) and Gunarathne et al. (2021), showing that companies are taking advantage of innovative technologies. Additionally, the findings align with Opferkuch et al. (2022, 2023), Roberts et al. (2022), and Tiscini et al. (2022), who note that more manufacturing companies are disclosing their use of innovation and reverse logistics strategies to reduce waste, explore unique combinations of products and services, and access new markets. This alignment with previous research reinforces the validity and importance of our current findings.

Level 4: The annual frequency distribution of CE, Servitisation, I4.0, and CV disclosures: The researcher assessed the disclosure practices of sample companies (selected from the Global Fortune 500 list) regarding CE-related reporting practices over five years. The research provided valuable insights into current trends and initiatives related to the 10R strategies of CE, servitisation, I4.0, and CV constructs. It identified the evolving transition towards circularity and strengths and opportunities for further improvement in implementing circular economy practices. The findings reveal that reporting practices related to I4.0 initiatives have consistently increased, which is supported by studies

such as those by Barnabè & Nazir (2021), Gunarathne et al. (2021), Roberts et al. (2022), Opferkuch et al. (2022, 2023), and Tiscini et al. (2022). These studies highlight companies' commitment to adapting innovative and sustainable practices and disclosing them to stakeholders. Disclosing circular practices can enhance businesses' reputation, brand image, and market position. Similarly, the research outcomes of the current study suggest that servitisation and I4.0 are pivotal in catalysing organisations to adopt more transparent and responsible CE disclosure practices. The 10R strategies of CE, coupled with technological advancements and additional services provision, not only enhance organisations' reputations but also build trust with stakeholders, consistent with the claims of ST (Azcarate-Aguerre et al., 2022; F. Ayala et al., 2021; Isaksson et al., 2018). Overall, the findings show a positive trend in CE-related disclosure practices, with the number of companies disclosing information on CE reporting practices consistently increasing each year. These findings indicate a growing awareness and emphasis on transparency and accountability in reporting practices among companies in the context of CE reporting.

6.2.3. Main Findings of RO3

Research Objective 3 (RO3): To investigate the extent of CE reporting practices related to using servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategy by Global Fortune 500 listed companies.

Research Question 3 (RQ3): *To what extent do Global Fortune 500 companies report on the integration of servitisation and I4.0 as part of their CE strategies?*

RO3 is aimed to examine the extent of CE reporting practices related to servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies by Global Fortune 500 listed companies. Thus, the researcher set up RQ3 to determine how much these companies report on integrating servitisation and I4.0 as part of their CE strategies (as presented in heading 5.5. Descriptive analysis in Chapter 5: Findings and Discussion).

The descriptive statistics and other analyses in Chapter 5 reveal a favourable trend towards increased CE disclosures for 10R strategies, aligning with the findings of Barreiro-Gen & Lozano (2020) and Opferkuch et al. (2022). This contradicts the conclusions of Gunarathne et al. (2021), Dagilienne et al. (2020), and Roberts et al. (2022), which indicated low CE disclosures and a lack of direct incorporation of CE principles in environmental management actions. These findings underscore the importance of establishing relationships and engaging with supply chains, making the research more engaging and relevant.

The researcher observed that most companies in the sample integrate and adjust their sustainability statements and vision by implementing CE practices. This is consistent with the RBV framework, which indicates that firms must incorporate CE strategies to gain a competitive edge in today's volatile and uncertain market. Additionally, these findings align with the recommendation of Ibáñez-Forés et al. (2022) to address the fundamental aspects of circularity while promoting global sustainability. The findings suggest that companies are leveraging servitisation and I4.0 technologies to improve resource efficiency and reduce negative environmental impacts.

In conclusion, the descriptive analysis results reveal that the convergence of I4.0 and servitisation accelerates the transition towards a CE paradigm, wherein products are designed for longevity, reuse, and regeneration. This fosters long-term customer relationships rooted in value creation and shared responsibility for environmental conservation. The results provide a comprehensive overview of CE constructs, servitisation constructs, I4.0 constructs, and control variables, highlighting areas for improvement in reporting practices and the potential for these strategies to enhance business performance and sustainability efforts.

6.2.4. Main Findings of RO4

Research Objective 4 (RO4): *To explore the implications of CE reporting practices, specifically examining the use and impact of servitisation and I4.0 as integral components of CE strategy in disclosure activities.*

Research Question 4 (RQ4): *What are the implications of incorporating servitisation and I4.0 into CE reporting practices, and how do these integrations impact the transparency, accountability, and overall sustainability performance of Global Fortune 500 companies?*

The researcher of the current study established RO4, which aimed to examine the impact of combining CE, servitisation, and I4.0 by analysing the company's reporting practices on the effects and transition practices related to this combination. This objective evaluated the impact of integrating CE, servitisation, and I4.0 on disclosure practices, aligning with RQ4. This assessment shed light on the sample's evolving landscape of CE-related disclosure practices. Based on RQ4, the researcher developed four hypotheses (H1- H4) to provide insights into the relationships between the latent variables and their impact on CE-related disclosure practices. The Main model was developed, including H1-H4, and each hypothesis (H1- H4) addressed different aspects of the relationships among CE, servitisation, and I4.0.

Furthermore, two additional models were run for robust analysis. Since the data was non-normal, the researcher used PLS-SEM to assess the models (one main model and two for robust analysis).

Findings of Main Model: The findings for H1 revealed a significant positive relationship between servitisation and CE, indicating that companies adopting servitisation strategies also engage in CE practices. These findings are consistent with prior literature (Atif, 2023b, 2023a; Atif et al., 2021; Cagliano et al., 2017; Cainelli et al., 2020; Tukker, 2015), highlighting the complementary nature of servitisation and CE in promoting resource efficiency and sustainable business practices.

While a positive relationship between Industry 4.0 and corporate efficiency was hypothesised for H2, the study's results indicate that this relationship may not be significant. This suggests further investigation is needed to understand the nuanced interplay between Industry 4.0 and corporate efficiency. Contrary to some prior research (Barnabè & Nazir, 2021; Gunarathne et al., 2021; Roberts et al., 2022; Tiscini et al., 2022; Opferkuch et al., 2022, 2023), which proposed a significant impact of I4.0 on CE initiatives, the current study's main statistical findings contradict this assumption. This indicates a more thorough investigation is required to comprehend the nuanced interplay between I4.0 and CE.

H3 was set to test the relationship between servitisation and I4.0, and the findings provide evidence supporting a positive and significant impact of I4.0 on servitisation, aligning with existing literature (Weking et al., 2020). This suggests that integrating I4.0 technologies facilitates the transition towards servitisation and enhances operational capabilities, in line with leveraging digital technologies to extend the product lifecycle and drive innovation in service delivery. These findings contradict some prior research (Tiscini et al., 2022; Rossi et al., 2024; Nazir & Doni, 2024; Fernando et al., 2023; Hassan et al., 2023; Liu & Lu, 2023) but aligns with the proposition that I4.0-enabled platforms prioritise co-creation and data-driven approaches to promote CE initiatives (D'Amato et al., 2019; Scarpellini et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the study identifies a significant indirect effect of I4.0 on CE through servitisation for H4, highlighting the importance of considering the interplay between these factors. In summary, the statistical analysis confirms a significant positive relationship between servitisation and CE, as well as between I4.0 and servitisation. However, the direct relationship between I4.0 and CE may not be significant, highlighting the need for additional research. The integration of these strategies highlights their potential to enhance business performance and sustainability efforts through improved resource efficiency and transparency in reporting practices.

Robust Analysis: Later, two additional models were run to investigate the relationship between CE, servitisation, and I4.0 under different conditions (i.e., with and without CV). The researcher divided the dependent variable (CE) into three sub-sets based on distinct stages of the CE-10R strategy (E1-E6), and the influence of servitisation and I4.0 on each CE phase was tested. The statistical results of Model 1 indicated that the effect of I4.0 with CV on CE-Phase 3 (R9: Recycle, R10: Recover) is not significant. This may be linked to the need for significant impact observed in integrating I4.0 technologies with Circular Value in these processes, attributed to ineffective implementation and unrealised synergies between these elements. This aligns with the findings of Ramsheva et al. (2020), who suggested that effective integration and collaboration across the entire supply chain network are essential for realising the benefits of I4.0 technologies and addressing challenges in transitioning to a CE. The study emphasises the need to measure the value of I4.0 technologies in mitigating technical, economic, compliance, and logistic challenges, which could impact product functional efficacy and sustainability (Frank, Dalenogare et al., 2019). Additionally, Kristensen and Remmen (2019) highlighted the potential of I4.0 to reduce operating costs through end-to-end integration, contributing to value creation in product development and manufacturing processes. However, the lack of a significant impact may also be influenced by the phased nature of the transformation from linear to CBMs, as indicated by Hernandez (2019) and Michelini et al. (2017). This suggests that the

realisation of benefits, including financial gains, from circular product strategies may vary in the short and long term. Kozlenkova et al. (2014) and Sajjad et al. (2015) further highlight the positive impact of circular products on revenue streams, highlighting the incentive for businesses to engineer durable products. Oghazi and Mostaghel (2018) echoed this sentiment, emphasising the increasing trend of businesses leveraging I4.0 technologies to prolong the lifecycle of resources and deliver efficient functionality to customers. Thus, while I4.0 holds potential for enhancing CE practices, the lack of significant impact on recycling and recovery processes (CE-Phase 3) observed in this study may stem from challenges in realising synergies, addressing supply chain complexities, and navigating the phased transition to CBM. Further research and strategic collaboration across the supply chain network are necessary to unlock the full potential of I4.0 in advancing CE initiatives. However, Model 2 results suggest that servitisation and I4.0 adoption in the absence of CV positively impact all phases of the CE strategy, promoting sustainable and innovative business practices. These findings are consistent with the RBV theoretical framework, which emphasises utilising and harnessing valuable, rare, and inimitable resources to achieve sustainable competitive advantage (Kozlenkova et al., 2014; Zahra, 2021).

6.3. Implications

The findings of this study hold several implications for theory, practice, and policy within the realm of CE strategies, particularly concerning the integration of reverse-logistics perspectives within servitisation and I4.0-enabled approaches. These implications are delineated below:

6.3.1. Theoretical Implications

The current study employs a triangulation of theories—RBV, DCT, and ST—to develop a comprehensive understanding of sustainable strategies for circular product development. This triangulation addresses the lack of a theoretical framework covering environmental sustainability and social responsibility in business strategy formulation. RBV is utilised to elaborate on the CE principles, focusing on the efficient utilisation of resources and waste reduction to achieve sustainable competitive advantage by using servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies. It involves designing sustainable products and processes that minimise waste and optimise resource utilisation, which are the basic principles of CE. The findings of the main model contrast Bressanelli et al. (2018) statement that I4.0 technologies facilitate residual value stewardship and align with the RBV perspective, leveraging internal resources for sustained competitive advantage. Instead, the strategic approach prioritises stakeholder interests and emphasises responsible and sustainable practices to meet societal expectations. This study highlights the importance of understanding how CE influences business

performance, highlighting the focus of RBV and ST on long-term value creation and accountability. In the second phase, "Responsible Consumption and Production," the DCT is utilised. Manufacturers are urged to develop dynamic capabilities to design efficient processes and effectively use post-manufacturing resources. This stage explores the correlation between responsible consumption and production practices and various aspects of I4.0 and servitisation, aiming to gain a competitive market advantage. Lastly, in the third phase, "Return of Used Product," ST guides the assessment of the role of I4.0 technologies in adopting the servitisation model. This phase involves returning used products to manufacturers through reverse logistics, promoting the development of circular products with optimal resource utilisation. ST emphasises considering stakeholders' interests, including customers, employees, suppliers, and the environment, in developing sustainable strategies for product return. Overall, this triangulation of theories offers a comprehensive framework for understanding and implementing sustainable strategies across all phases of product development, from design to end-of-life management. The results reveal that the study's social contribution lies in its alignment with ST, which highlights the significance of prioritising the interests of all stakeholders in the development of sustainable and responsible strategies for product return. By emphasising the inclusion of stakeholders such as customers, employees, suppliers, and the environment, the study promotes a holistic approach to decision-making that considers the broader societal impacts of business practices. This approach fosters transparency, accountability, and ethical responsibility within organisations, ultimately contributing to promoting social welfare and environmental stewardship. By acknowledging and addressing stakeholders' diverse needs and concerns, the study advocates for creating sustainable value that extends beyond financial gains, thereby fostering a more inclusive and equitable society.

6.3.2. Practical Implications

There is a significant gap in the research highlighting the need for a comprehensive framework for measuring the implementation and impact of CE throughout a product's lifecycle. This study aims to fill this gap by introducing a reliable and valid CE measurement tool i.e., CE Disclosure Index, that includes the servitisation and I4.0 constructs. Although, embracing circular strategies is crucial for *minimising risks, capitalising on opportunities, and reaping long-term ESG benefits*. However, through implementing the self-developed CE disclosure index, businesses can set a benchmark for measuring their corporate accountability in key activity disclosures, such as the CE, servitisation, and I4.0-related information.

Aside from fulfilling regulatory and legal responsibilities, management should focus on providing *transparent and comparable disclosures to their stakeholders*. Thus, businesses can use this self-

developed CE disclosure index to measure and report on how they are using servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies to benefit individuals, groups, and organisations including their own. This can help them disclose their collaborative relationships with various stakeholders who have the same interest and/or are affected by the company's operations.

Furthermore, engaging stakeholders in CE reporting is not just a task but an effective strategy that can significantly **enhance organisational competitiveness**. Stakeholders may also bring valuable knowledge and insights due to this reporting that can help improve organisation's internal practices. Effective stakeholder engagement is crucial for the manufacturing sector and can positively impact the implementation and reporting of CE practices.

Additionally, by using the provided self-developed CE disclosure index for reporting, manufacturing companies can effectively align their decisions and activities with their CE objectives and broader mission. While organisations may be at different stages of CE implementation, they should consistently strive to **foster a culture of CE and report on their perceived impact**. Although, it may be crucial to integrate stakeholders' feedback and recommendations about the strategic development and execution of sustainable and circular business practices. This integration promotes better governance and the successful implementation of CE strategies.

The findings show that the firms in the sample have low levels of disclosure related to I4.0 and its role in **driving innovation and creating positive ESG impacts**. Modifying the I4.0 criteria could encourage businesses to disclose reliable information about adopting digital solutions that lead to meaningful progress towards circularity. Hence, companies are encouraged to utilise the CE disclosure index to report the adoption of digital transformation and mitigate the adverse environmental effects using I4.0 solutions deliberately and transparently.

6.3.3. Policy Implications

The study offers valuable guidance to manufacturing firms seeking to adopt CE strategies by highlighting the potential benefits and challenges associated with integrating reverse logistics, servitisation, and I4.0 technologies. It provides actionable insights for managers and decision-makers on designing and implementing effective CE initiatives that drive environmental sustainability and enhance operational efficiency. Moreover, the findings highlight the importance of transparent reporting practices in communicating the impact of combined CE strategies on firm performance. This insight is particularly relevant for companies seeking to enhance stakeholder trust and credibility through comprehensive sustainability disclosures.

Moreover, the current study's findings have significant implications for policymakers and regulatory bodies looking to promote sustainable business practices and encourage the adoption of CE principles.

Policymakers can use the insights gained from this research to create policies that incentivise companies to adopt CE strategies, implement servitisation models, and integrate I4.0 technologies in the manufacturing sector. This research has shown that not all businesses using CE principles implement them. Therefore, it is essential to establish standards to ensure CE implementation. Policymakers can use the study's findings to design regulatory frameworks that promote greater transparency and accountability in corporate sustainability reporting. Moreover, this study is the first to incorporate servitisation and demonstrate its role in bringing used products back to the cycle with the help of an I4.0-enabled shared platform. Policymakers and researchers can use the self-developed CE disclosure index to compare the sustainability performance of different companies and hold them accountable for their CE practices. This can foster a culture of responsible business practices and environmental stewardship among organisations. Policymakers can also consider implementing measures to support and incentivise companies committed to implementing CE strategies, adopting servitisation models, and leveraging I4.0 technologies. In summary, this study's implications go beyond academia and offer practical guidance for policymakers in their efforts to promote CE principles and advance sustainability goals within manufacturing industries. By embracing the integration of reverse logistics, servitisation, and I4.0-enabled approaches, organisations can build a more sustainable and resilient future, aligning with broader policy objectives to foster ESG sustainability.

6.4. Limitations and Opportunities for Future Researchers

It is important to acknowledge certain limitations inherent in the current study, which should be considered when extrapolating the results. One of the limitations of the current research is related to its scope. The study primarily focuses on manufacturing firms, potentially overlooking the applicability of CE strategies in other sectors, such as services or agriculture. Moreover, the findings are based on a specific set of manufacturing firms, potentially limiting their generalisability to companies operating in different geographical regions or industries. While the study employs a triangulation of theories (RBV, DCT, and ST) to understand sustainable strategies, it may overlook other relevant theoretical perspectives, such as the Triple Bottom Line and socio-technical theory, that could provide additional insights into adopting and implementing CE strategies. Another limitation may be linked to errors in the study's findings due to self-reported data and subjective assessments, which could introduce biases. Future research should incorporate objective measures and independent evaluations to ensure more reliable results.

Furthermore, the study primarily provides a snapshot of CE strategies adoption and implementation. Longitudinal analysis could offer insights into the evolution of CE practices over time and the long-term impacts on firm performance and sustainability outcomes. Addressing these limitations further

enriches our understanding of the complexities surrounding adopting and implementing CE strategies in manufacturing firms. Thus, research exploring the effectiveness of CE strategies in diverse industry contexts and alternative theoretical frameworks to gain a more comprehensive accord of the phenomenon is recommended. Certain research opportunities have been identified by researchers of the current study that may contribute to a more holistic understanding of sustainable business practices on a global scale, which is as follows:

6.4.1. Advancing Research on CE Implementation and Methodological Refinement

The CE paradigm and the I4.0 concept emerged from various European countries, suggesting potential differences in the implementation and impact of CE strategies across regions and different organisational settings with varying economic, social, and political structures. One significant limitation of the current study is its exclusive focus on large organisations (sample selected from Global Fortune 500 list). While these companies often have the resources and infrastructure to implement CE practices, the findings may not be entirely generalisable to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) because it is mandatory for large organisations to publish their financial and non-financial reports (annual or integrated reports), providing a wealth of data on their ESG practices, which is not always the case for SMEs. This mandatory reporting can influence the transparency and extent of CE practices observed in large organisations. In contrast, SMEs often face different challenges, such as limited financial resources, less access to advanced technologies, and fewer specialised staff, which can impact their ability to adopt and report on CE strategies. Consequently, the insights gained from this research may not fully capture the experiences and obstacles encountered by SMEs. Therefore, it is recommended for future research to include a more diverse range of organisations to provide a more comprehensive understanding of CE implementation across different business sizes and reporting practices. Moreover, besides some earlier research that have focused on specific country like India (M. P. Singh et al., 2021), China (Yang et al., 2019; Yu, et al., 2022); Sri Lanka (Gunarathne et al., 2021) using case studies (Opferkuch et al., 2022; Zheng et al., 2022). Therefore, it is apparent that there has been lack of a holistic disclosure index that measure and report the circularity metric (circular design: resource use; responsible production and consumption and progress in the transition towards CE) in a credible manner. Thus, more comprehensive studies are required to investigate the extent of CE implementation. These studies will help determine whether manufacturers utilise servitisation and Industry 4.0 as CE strategies. The disclosure index utilised in this study is self-developed and may encounter constraints when subjected to critical analysis. Explaining guidelines and standards may need to be more accurate in the implementation framework of CE, which inherently involves complex and multifaceted dimensions,

including informal and corporate societal aspects. Consequently, the subjective assessment of CE strategies and the evaluation of servitisation and I4.0 as a CE strategy may be open to diverse interpretations. Thus, the findings require validation through future disclosure assessments.

6.4.2. Exploring Regional Disparities in CE Adoption: Cross-Regional Analysis

Additionally, by not including a comparative analysis between developing and developed countries, the study may need to pay more attention to important nuances in how different regions respond to the production and consumption of circular products, services, or policies. This limitation may affect the generalisability of the research findings, as they may need to fully capture the diversity of experiences and challenges faced by companies operating in different parts of the world. Therefore, future research endeavours could address this limitation by comparing the adoption and impact of CE strategies, servitisation models, and I4.0 technologies between developing and developed countries. This comparative analysis would provide valuable insights into the unique challenges and opportunities faced by companies in different regions, enabling a more comprehensive understanding of the global landscape of sustainable business practices. Specially from African regions, which play a significant role in the second-hand market for circular products. By incorporating companies from diverse geographic locations, future studies can ensure a more representative sample and contribute to a more inclusive and holistic understanding of the CE on a global scale.

6.4.3. Insights and Contradictions: Understanding the Interplay of CE, servitisation and I4.0

The current study provides valuable insights into the relationships between servitisation, CE, and I4.0 in the context of global Fortune 500 companies' disclosure practices. While some relationships are supported by empirical evidence and align with most prior literature, others present challenges and call for further investigation better to understand their implications for sustainable business practices and innovation. This study not only advances scholarly understanding of CE strategies but also provides actionable insights for businesses seeking to navigate the complexities of sustainability in a rapidly evolving global landscape. However, the findings of the current study contradict the studies of Barnabè & Nazir (2021); Gunarathne et al. (2021); Opferkuch et al. (2022), (2023); Roberts et al. (2022) and Tiscini et al. (2022), as it demonstrates that CE and I4.0 do not have a significant relationship. There is a high chance that the researchers might have misinterpreted or missed some I4.0 components. Therefore, it is recommended that future researchers conduct extensive studies to assess how manufacturing companies embrace the principles of circularity, harnessing the transformative potential of servitisation and I4.0 and adopting transparent reporting practices to ensure a more sustainable and resilient future. Another recommendation is to explore the

accountability challenges, as it has been demonstrated that a company's dedication to sustainability and innovation may foster accountability challenges in its operations (Di Vaio et al., 2022).

6.4.4. Unravelling Complexity: Investigating Lease Dynamics in CE and I4.0 Integration

According to the findings of this research, it is recommended that future studies focus on exploring the relationship between leasing practices and CE principles as the main variables. This recommendation is based on the significant impact of leasing activities on sustainability and environmental outcomes, particularly in light of recent changes to accounting standards like IFRS 16. With these changes, lessees are now required to recognise lease assets and liabilities on their balance sheets Yu, (2019), which can affect their leasing decisions and compliance with CE principles. Leasing arrangements are vital in shaping companies' resource utilisation and waste management strategies and can influence their adherence to CE principles. Therefore, future studies can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of leasing as a tool for promoting sustainability and reducing environmental impact by examining how leasing practices intersect with CE principles.

6.4.5. CE Initiatives and R&D Tax Credits: A Path to Innovation and Policy Support

Additionally, future researchers are encouraged to explore the possible connection between CE initiatives and Research and Development (R&D) tax credits. R&D tax credits are incentives provided by the government to encourage investment in innovation and technological development. These credits encourage companies to invest in R&D activities, which can lead to innovation across various industries (Mitchell et al., 2019), including those related to CE practices. As policy interventions aimed at promoting sustainability and innovation, R&D tax credits can enhance our understanding of the mechanisms driving innovation in the context of CE transitions (Bustinza, Gomes, et al., 2019). This research area could inform the design of more effective policy instruments to support these transitions.

6.5. Chapter Summary

This chapter presents the key findings of the research objectives (RO1-RO4) and research questions (RQ1- RQ4). A significant gap in CE-related research highlights the need for a comprehensive framework to report and disclose the implementation and impact of CE throughout a product's lifecycle. This study addresses this gap by introducing the CE Disclosure Index, incorporating servitisation and I4.0 constructs, to help businesses benchmark and report their CE practices and stakeholder engagement transparently. This study's key findings emphasise how companies should implement servitisation and I4.0 as CE strategies and related disclosure practices. The statistical

results validate the positive relationship between servitisation and CE. However, the relationship between CE and I4.0 reveals mixed results. The key takeout indicates that while firms have low disclosure levels regarding I4.0, adopting the CE Disclosure Index can encourage more transparent reporting and effective integration of digital solutions for sustainable practices. Furthermore, this chapter provides theoretical and practical implications, offering actionable insights for manufacturing firms. The policy implications suggest that policymakers can incentivise the adoption of CE, servitisation, and I4.0 integration in manufacturing by leveraging companies to use digital solutions for sustainable practices and fostering better governance. Research findings can also be used to design regulatory frameworks that promote transparency and accountability in sustainability reporting. The researcher recommends that future researchers conduct comparative assessments between developing and developed countries on CE principles, servitisation, and I4.0 technologies. Additionally, the study highlights the need for a comprehensive disclosure index to measure circularity metrics across regions, which may overlook regional differences in CE adoption and impact. The current study's findings suggest that CE and I4.0 may not exhibit a significant relationship, prompting the need for more extensive research. Therefore, exploring accountability challenges in sustainability and innovation practices is recommended for a more resilient future.

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Appendix

Appendix 1: Definitions of Servitisation

Reference	Definition and Details
Tim Baines	Servitisation, as defined by Tim Baines (Lightfoot et al., 2013), encapsulates the idea of manufacturers providing services intricately linked to their products. This concept highlights the close integration of services with tangible goods, offering customers a more comprehensive solution.
Neely (2008)	Servitisation is described as an organisational innovation aimed at enhancing abilities and procedures for generating shared value. This involves a strategic move from merely vending products to offering Product-Service Systems (PSSs), where the emphasis is on delivering holistic solutions that meet customer needs more effectively.
de Moura Leite et al. (2020)	Servitisation is categorised as a trend wherein manufacturing firms progressively incorporate service components into their offerings. This evolving approach signifies a strategic transformation in BMs, reflecting a broader industry shift towards providing integrated solutions that encompass both products and services.
Summary of Definitions	Servitisation is widely perceived as a strategy offering competitive advantages in implementing innovative BMs (Kühl et al., 2019; Weigel & Hadwich, 2018). Numerous research has investigated the relationship among servitisation and the manufacturing industry, with significant growth observed over the past two decades (de Moura Leite et al., 2020; Kühl et al., 2020; Rymaszewska et al., 2017; Santamaría et al., 2012). The strategic and competitive benefits for companies that offer services closely linked to their products are significant (Frank, Mendes, et al., 2019). Moreover, servitisation, as defined by various scholars, emphasizes customer-centricity, necessitating the development of new competencies and capabilities (Isaksson et al., 2018). Various definitions of servitisation exist and out of which, the researcher of current study has selected the ones that are particularly relevant to the current study.

Appendix 2: Types of Services

Reference	Types of Services	Details
Mathieu (2001)	Customer Support Services	Current research indicates that servitisation involves the provision of a tailored bundle comprising products and services aimed at meeting individualized customer requirements to generate customer value (Tukker, 2015). Servitisation basically entails a move from sales-focused businesses to those emphasising servitisation models (Kristensen & Remmen, 2019a). A service typology proposed by Mathieu (2001) categorises servitisation into two forms: services that support customers include the operational lease of an asset and result-oriented services
	Result-oriented Services	It is apparent from this description of different types of services that servitisation emerges as a cost-effective megatrend in today's technological landscape, representing a process that enhances the value of manufactured goods by integrating services with products (Kühl et al., 2019b; Rymaszewska et al., 2017). This burgeoning phenomenon in BMs, known as servitisation, has gained significant traction among companies (Frederiksen et al., 2021; Bustinza, Gomes et al., 2019; Lightfoot et al., 2013). Many organisations are increasingly integrating intelligent digital systems with machines and devices, allowing them to operate independently and communicate with other systems and devices (Lightfoot, Baines, and Smart, 2013; Mourtzis et al., 2020; Li et al., 2021). Consequently, an increasing number of companies are leveraging digital systems to offer an assorted variety of services to their clients and customers (Santamaría et al., 2012; Reim et al., 2019; Kohtamäki et al., 2020).
Lightfoot et al. (2013)	Base Services	Another type of servitisation is outlined by Baines and Lightfoot, discussed about three types of services in accordance with market offerings such as base services, which encompass the fundamental or core services provided by manufacturing firms, typically associated with the product itself. For instance, this may include offering a mechanism or an interrelated component along with the product.
	Intermediate Services	which extend beyond basic offerings and involve services such as repair and maintenance, when the service provider or manufacturer is more involved than the basic service provisions.
	Advanced Services	Advance services represent a higher level of service provision, where the revenue stream is linked to product usage and may involve contractual agreements outlining shared rewards and risks associated with the products
Kühl et al., (2019b)	Product-centric PSS	Within servitisation literature, Product-Service System (PSS) is an interchangeable term envisioned to foster customer loyalty and attract new market segments (López-Cubillos et al., 2022; Pakurár et al., 2019; Romero & Rossi, 2017). Additionally, Tukker (2015) defines PSS as combining physical goods and non-material offerings to fulfil specific customer needs, identifying eight archetypal types of PSS. In the product-oriented category, the manufacturer retains responsibility for additional services like repair and maintenance.

Reference	Types of Services	Details
	Usage-centric PSS	In Use-Oriented PSS, customer demands take precedence. PSS serves to influence consumer consumption behavior, minimize resource consumption, and enhance technical capabilities, ultimately driving firm efficiency (Sassanelli et al., 2016; Sousa & Cauchick Miguel, 2015).
	Outcome-oriented PSS	Result-oriented PSS focuses on delivering services or capabilities tailored to customer demands, prioritising efficiency, and environmental sustainability. In the face of heightened competition driven by new market entrants offering superior services at lower costs, businesses are increasingly adopting PSS. Consumers are expected to make informed choices considering continuing contracts and evaluating deciding whether to buy a product outright or opt for PSS with all its associated expenses (Fagnoli et al., 2022; Kühl et al., 2018). Although eco-efficient PSS has the possibility of sustained expansion, firms need to be bold in updating their models to meet evolving consumer expectations (Bhatti et al., 2023). These systems establish an eco-friendlier and resource-conscious sector through the practice of re-use and remanufacturing, contributing to environmental well-being by reducing resource exploitation and waste emissions (Compagnoni, 2022).
Dev, Shankar, & Swami (2020)	CLSC Remanufacturing Model	Nevertheless, Dev, Shankar, & Swami (2020) proposed a CLSC remanufacturing model, leveraging reverse logistics to develop a service base where manufacturers oversee the process of returning products for potential reutilization, reevaluation, or recycling. Service-oriented companies strive to expand their market presence by providing physical products along with value-added non-material services at competitive rates (Reim et al., 2016).
Compagnoni (2022)	Environmental Product Responsibility (EPR)	ERP can be closely linked with PSS through their shared goal of promoting environmentally sustainable practices as it plays a crucial role in promoting environmentally friendly practices through various legal and contextual frameworks (Azcarate-Aguerre et al., 2022; Campbell-Johnston et al., 2020; Kristensen & Remmen, 2019). Manufacturers are encouraged to incentivize product returns over disposal and design processes that preserve resources, time, and expenses, in accordance with the sustainable value proposition of PSS (López-Cubillos et al., 2022; Nakata & Bahadir, 2020; Zhang et al., 2020).

Appendix 3: A Detailed Literature Review Linking Servitisation and I4.0 with CE ¹⁴

1. Introduction

The manufacturers are transforming significantly from LE BM to CEBM (van Stijn & Gruis, 2019). This shift is facilitated by self-optimization and self-configuration, enhancing system dynamism and competence (D'Agostin et al., 2020). According to Mishra et al. (2020), scalability, connectivity, security, service quality (QoS), dependability, modular design, networking features, integration, and compatibility are the key attributes of I4.0. There's a notable change in SCM, where I4.0 technologies are instrumental in integrating value networks to achieve system transparency (Beier et al., 2021; Peker et al., 2020; Saberi et al., 2019). Experts often call this relationship the "Digitalisation of CE" (Camacho-Otero et al., 2018; Chauhan et al., 2022; Fernández-Portillo et al., 2022; Neligan et al., 2022). However, transitioning towards circularity through I4.0 poses uncertainties in structural challenges and strategy formulation (Oghazi & Mostaghel, 2018; Ormazabal et al., 2018; Rajput & Singh, 2019), market dynamics (Kama, 2015; Łękańska-andrinopoulou et al., 2021), product design (Dev, Shankar, & Swami, 2020; P. Zheng et al., 2019), processes (Bag, Wood, et al., 2020), and policies (Hartley et al., 2020; Kama, 2015; Nielsen, 2020; Pietrulla, 2022; Zhou et al., 2020). For instance, through empirical study, Bag, Wood, et al. (2020) investigated the integration of dynamic remanufacturing and green manufacturing capabilities into smart logistics systems. Similarly, D'Amato et al. (2019) and Khan et al. (2022) suggested an I4.0 imposed digital manufacturing tool that could help improve sustainable supply chain operations. Additionally, various studies delved into different context of CE and I4.0, covering topics like barricades of digital manufacturing, the 10R imperatives, improved manufacturing capacities, the effects of CE capabilities in driving I4.0 implementation, and the Procurement 4.0 concept. Despite advancements, several research gaps persist in theoretical knowledge literature, such as determining the timing of the paradigm shift to CE/sustainability, understanding associated risks, assessing the achievability and measurability of the transition, and whether manufacturing firms should adhere to this transformation. Hence, this study aims to construct a framework that consolidates knowledge on latent variables, directing on the ubiquitous integration of I4.0 technologies in developing circular products, fostering a collaborative data-driven sustainable socio-technical system that enhances firms' resilience from disruptions and uncertainties (Sousa-Zomer et al., 2018; Reim et al., 2019; Ching et al., 2022).

2. Material-flow in Smart Manufacturing

Numerous firms are grappling with integrating I4.0 technologies to boost efficiency and productivity (Mura et al., 2020). A plethora of novel concepts and combinations have emerged, such as the fusion of I4.0 with sustainability (Ching et al., 2022), green SCM (Zahraee et al., 2018; Rinaldi et al., 2021; Feng et al., 2022; Bag & Rahman, 2023), human-centric innovation (Horbach & Rammer, 2019; Nielsen, 2020), circular strategies (Franconi et al., 2022; Geissdoerfer et al., 2017; Khan et al., 2022; Prieto-Sandoval et al., 2019), blockchain and CE (Karamchandani et al., 2021; Nandi et al., 2021; Okorie et al., 2022; Saberi et al., 2019; Teisserenc & Sepasgozar, 2021), supply chain optimisation (Chari et al., 2022; Howard et al., 2019), lean manufacturing in I4.0 (Ciano et al., 2020; Jum'a et al., 2022; Romero & Rossi, 2017; Shashi et al., 2019; Sony, 2020), Sustainable Smart Manufacturing (Fatimah et al., 2020; Kohtamäki et al., 2022; Majeed et al., 2021), CE innovation (Bag et al., 2022; Cainelli et al., 2020; Fernando et al., 2023; Horbach & Rammer, 2019; Ranta et al., 2021), and design for value (De Pádua Pieroni et al., 2018; Mura et al., 2020; Nakata & Bahadir, 2020; Pittri et al., 2023).

Acknowledging sustainability as a guiding principle leading towards circularity, which aims to enhance resource efficiency and energy efficacy (Charro & Schaefer, 2018), it's evident that I4.0 technologies are indispensable, transforming the co-creation of value (Rehman et al., 2016). Consequently, many

¹⁴ This appendix provides a comprehensive review of the literature on CE, servitisation, and I4.0 technologies. It aims to elucidate the theoretical foundations, key concepts, and interconnections between these domains, supporting the research objectives outlined in the Chapter 2: Literature Review.

authors agree that I4.0 will advance additive manufacturing towards circularity that is reliant on sustainable resources. Simultaneously, I4.0 is emerging as the next phase in the value-driven evolution of manufacturing, supporting digital transformation, sustainability, and resilience among adept employees (Alkaraan et al., 2022; Philbin et al., 2022).

The CE paradigm propels the circular flow of materials for value extraction, aligning with sustainability principles (Neligan et al., 2022; Pham et al., 2019), major businesses are embracing the implementation of CE principles within their BMs to endure themselves in the marketplace (Puglieri et al., 2022). CE and sustainability offer a pathway for integrating environmental aspects into development (Barón Dorado et al., 2022; van Stijn & Gruis, 2019).

Nazir & Doni (2024) introduced the design principles outlined by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, known as the 9Rs, which include Reusing the used product or its components for new products, rethinking BMs, reduce the usage of virgin resources, enhance efficiency, outsource used products, and repair or maintaining defective products, refurbishing and upgrading products, remanufacturing components of discarded products, repurposing redundant products, and recycling materials (Minunno et al., 2020; Pedreño-Rojas et al., 2020; C. Zhang et al., 2023). Figure 8.1 delineates how the CE approach fosters product sustainability, preserving value over an extended period owing to smart manufacturing, which is driven by the integration of automated processes and network connectivity and leads to the creation of durable designs, continually enhancing data transfer and transparency.

Figure 8. 1: Product Lifecycle and CE Principles

Source: (Atif, 2023a)

Figure 8.1 depicts the lifecycle of a product within a Closed-loop-supply-chain framework. The illustration portrays the initial phases of product development, encompassing organisation, creativity, and the conversion of ideas into detailed designs. Circular design principles mirror the iterative cycle delineated by the product's lifespan. The focal challenge lies primarily in navigating the secondary and tertiary markets (Cano et al., 2022; Kama, 2015). Consequently, it becomes imperative for manufacturers to cultivate enduring customer relationships through cost-effective asset data management facilitated by the integration of robotics and concurrent software departments (J. Rossi et al., 2020). The researcher of the current study is suggesting that data gleaned from smart gears, robotics, and scalable AI, leveraging accumulated data for learning and advancement, enables

organisations to monitor cycles and act responsibly (Tavera Romero et al., 2021). Subsequently, industries are increasingly turning to digital twins to pioneer advanced circular products with heightened practical efficacy (Martín et al., 2021). Through the utilisation of this "product digital twin," enterprises can bridge the simulated and physical realms to scrutinise the performance of a circular product under various conditions, effecting changes in the virtual sphere to ensure subsequent circular and sustainable products purpose as envisioned in real-world scenarios (Ulmer et al., 2022).

3. Information-flow in Smart Manufacturing

Smart manufacturing is frequently depicted as a mechanism for revolutionising through digital automation and the orientation of value networks and product lifecycle optimisation. Additionally, Ibarra et al. (2018) conducted a literature scrutiny exploring how I4.0 technologies enhance manufacturing and administration at the company level, suggesting that I4.0 encompass diverse cutting-edge tools and systems to revolutionise industrial processes. Robotics stands at the forefront, incorporating advanced robotic technologies that seamlessly integrate sensors and interfaces to enhance automation and precision in manufacturing operations. Additive Manufacturing, another pivotal component, harnesses data from 3D printers to fabricate prototypes swiftly and efficiently, offering unparalleled flexibility in design iteration and production. Augmented Reality emerges as a transformative tool, increasing real-world objects with computer-generated perceptual information and facilitating enhanced visualisation, training, and troubleshooting in industrial settings. Cloud Computing plays a fundamental role by fostering grid stimulus among intellectual arrangements, facilitating seamless data amalgamation across interconnected stakeholders, and enabling the management of vast datasets in open systems. Big data analytics, a cornerstone of I4.0, entails the evaluation of substantial data streams from Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) and Customer Relationship Management (CRM) to augment real-time decision-making processes, enabling businesses to derive actionable insights and drive efficiency (Sony, 2020).

Furthermore, it would be accurate to assert that the fourth industrial revolution has stimulated the development of circular products, systems, and informed decisions, all these different components of business are interconnected and have an impact on each other. Intelligent devices create an innovative network through intelligent machinery, IoT, CPS, cloud computing, AI, and cognitive computing (Fraga-Lamas et al., 2021). This transition enables businesses to antedate market trends and allocate resources more efficiently. Facilitating statistics allotment across the value chain, digital twins extant several opportunities for the manufacturing sector (Alvarez-Aros & Bernal-Torres, 2021), linking the entire spectrum of strategy and manufacturing to comprehensive data, from initial design concepts to final products (Atif, 2023a; Pittri et al., 2023). This analytics-driven approach to reconditioning also assists in deciding the feasibility of transitioning the towards circularity (Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020). CE paradigms prioritise remanufacturing and integration of I4.0 technologies appears to be a suitable solution (Nielsen, 2020). Innovations in I4.0 highlight the evolving shift from circular product engineering into a socially oriented specialisation (Atif, 2023a). The shift towards circularity aims to meet the need for customised sustainable products and intelligent services, which are critical to developing sustainable and resilient production systems (Maddikunta et al., 2021). Computerisation increases the likelihood of lowering the workforce expenses throughout the design, development, and production cycles, allowing companies to modify circular products using the collected data from various phases, leveraging relevant information for management in response to changing customer demands (Prieto-Sandoval et al., 2019). Moreover, the concept of a CE combined with I4.0's digital innovation can create smart products and services that use several technologies. This can enhance the perceived value of the products through mass customization tailored to meet customers' individual needs.

Figure 8. 2: Data sharing within a Data-driven Platform

Source: (Atif, 2023a)

Figure 8.2 depicts the author's creation of a connected data management platform. It can be observed from the figure that using I4.0 technologies creates an interconnected system that enhances connectivity, granting admittance to permitted participants (Rupa et al., 2021). The cloud storage gateway converts the sensor-collected statistics before storing it in cloud computing, enabling distant sharing of streamlined data among approved stakeholders, as Charro & Schaefer (2018) discussed. Moreover, Howe et al. (2020) and Waller & Fawcett (2013) emphasize that prognostic material stream assessment and multi-dimensional decision scrutiny can be used to respond to changing market conditions when evaluating CE strategies. Chen et al. (2022) suggest that data helps in revealing concealed information and trends within raw datasets gathered through big data analytics. Furthermore, Okorie et al. (2022) propose a blockchain-driven platform that transforms amorphous data into an organised and structured format. It is crucial in today's globalised context, where supply chains must be more innovative, resilient, and wasteful (Chen et al. (2022). Grossi et al. (2021) and Mathew et al. (2020) observed the main obstacle to remanufacturing as the need for more data sharing within the supply chain. Moreover, Dhar Dwivedi et al. (2021) suggest that I4.0 technologies aid to overcome technical, commercial, and logistical challenges while enhancing regulatory compliance. However, Chiappetta Jabbour et al. (2020) highlight transparency and confidentiality concerns as significant hi-tech challenges of I4.0. According to Rupa et al. (2021), blockchain technology is highlighted as highly secure for resilience in I4.0's increasing digital functions. It can improve the system's security, traceability, and sustainability. Modern economics challenges businesses to reconsider the notion of directives, reevaluate entities' roles over time, and redesign measures (Saber et al., 2019). Simultaneously, Fraga-Lamas et al. (2021) proposes integrating human-centric and techno-centric innovation for sustainable manufacturing solutions.

4. Risk Detection in Smart Manufacturing

Integrating CE principles into BMs promotes adopting sustainable policies, prioritizing minimal waste generation and efficient resource allocation via automated processes (Anastasiades et al., 2020). This transition towards sustainability fosters resilience, preparing businesses to navigate uncertainties, with I4.0 technologies providing an allied and supple data-driven platform to achieve a harmonious collaboration between machines and humans for increased ESG advantages (Atif, 2023b; Cenamor et al., 2017). In an environment characterized by unstructured data and high uncertainty, I4.0 technologies enable risk detection at various stages of manufacturing activities through employee training and smart devices (Hock-Doepgen et al., 2020). To address data-related challenges and enhance productivity, organisations are exploring blockchain technology, which provides a secure platform for data sharing among stakeholders using algorithms for data validation (Bai et al., 2021;

Carminati et al., 2018; Cenamor et al., 2017; Karamchandani et al., 2021; Nandi et al., 2021; Okorie et al., 2022; Saberi et al., 2019).

As a secure digital ledger, blockchain technology facilitates data generation and tracking (Cho et al., 2021), ensuring online accessibility and sharing protection through unique digital signatures along the supply chain network. Through human-machine collaboration and interaction, I4.0 leverages technologies to drive optimal outcomes, generating massive data on product usage and efficacy (Atif, 2023a; Kjaer et al., 2019; Linder et al., 2017; Nag et al., 2022). Enterprises utilise digital threads to monitor product conditions, enhance functionality, and trace locations, facilitating real-time decision-making insights (Cainelli et al., 2020; Feng et al., 2022; Nielsen, 2020). I4.0 offer a unique advantage in making firms resilient through sustainable solutions, improving manufacturing processes, optimizing resource use, and reducing energy consumption (Cainelli et al., 2020; Tukker & Tischner, 2006).

Resilient manufacturing firms can swiftly navigate disruptions and uncertainties, ensuring continuity in the face of internal and external risks (Chari et al., 2022; Settembre-Blundo et al., 2021; Soomro et al., 2022). However, discretion and confidentiality issues remain perilous insufficiencies of I4.0 technologies (Chiappetta Jabbour et al., 2020; Rupa et al., 2021), although blockchain technology presents a protected solution for pliability (Atif, 2023a). Thus, the correlation between I4.0 and CE paradigms has been extensively explored by various authors from multiple perspectives, including product regeneration (Bag & Rahman, 2023; Gonella et al., 2023; Howard et al., 2019; Morsetto, 2020), BM rethinking (Felsberger et al., 2022), resource usage reduction (Chiappetta Jabbour et al., 2020; Estensoro et al., 2021; Kama, 2015; Makhoulfi et al., 2022; Tukker, 2015), and stakeholder perception assessment (S. Gupta et al., 2019; Baah et al., 2022; S. K. Singh et al., 2022).

6. Linking I4.0 and Servitisation

Research on servitisation has placed significant emphasis on understanding the success and failure of organisations at the organisational level (Rymaszewska et al., 2017; Kühl et al., 2020). This focus fosters innovation manoeuvres, introducing additional value-added services (Kozlenkova et al., 2014). Acknowledging the heterogeneous resources of organisations (Spanos & Lioukas, 2001), it becomes evident that appropriate infrastructure is crucial for identifying innovation requirements and effectively dispersing technological innovations (Chuang & Lin, 2015; Kiel et al., 2017). I4.0 commonly enhances online scheduling and monitoring systems by optimising parameters (Mourtzis et al., 2020; Osterrieder et al., 2020; Rajput & Singh, 2019). Cloud-operated dashboards facilitate timely intervention for manufacturing process adjustments (Bressanelli et al., 2018b; Rosa et al., 2020; Sousa-Zomer et al., 2018).

Moreover, adapting the Lease-first-then-sell (LFTS) approach, as indicated by (Bal & Badurdeen, 2020; Seddon & Currie, 2017), can increase profits by reducing production costs through the use of remanufactured components, thereby boosting income (Tavera Romero et al., 2021). Additionally, an integrated Product-Service System (PSS) from a life-cycle perspective, as presented by Shihundla et al. (2019), seeks to diminish expenses and related service interruptions. Hence, the incorporation of effective products and proficient services necessitate a supportive infrastructure that guarantees the accessibility of servitisation (Michelini et al., 2017; Lyons et al., 2020; Peker et al., 2020). For instance, 3D printers are often cited as an example of additive manufacturing, facilitating servitisation by enabling activities such as chartering and maintaining capital goods and rapid prototyping (de Moura Leite et al., 2020).

7. Stimulating Resource Management

The implementation of the CE paradigm significantly impacts SCM, aiming to optimize or reduce supply chain activities to minimise material flow and enhance economic rewards (Adel & Wiesner, 2015; Bal & Badurdeen, 2020; Bressanelli et al., 2019b). Innovative product design becomes crucial to facilitate the reuse, refurbishment, upgrading, and maintenance of products (Okorie et al., 2021; Xing et al., 2022). The literature on I4.0 and servitisation is still evolving, with some studies viewing

servitisation as a transformative process that adds value through the integration of I4.0 technologies (Lyons et al., 2020; Reim et al., 2019; Rymaszewska et al., 2017). Companies must integrate servitisation elements into their plans and develop robust supply chain networks to ensure resilience and minimise interruptions, thereby promoting sustainability (Han et al., 2020; Rachmawati et al., 2021; Chari et al., 2022). I4.0 technologies, leveraging massive datasets, focus on identifying novel BMs and market trends (Dev, Shankar, & Swami, 2020; Tavera Romero et al., 2021) to enhance product competence (Rossi et al., 2020), improve service quality through strategies like SERQUAL (Mishra et al., 2020; Rokonuzzaman et al., 2020; Raza et al., 2020), and optimise infrastructure-related activities (Ciano et al., 2020; A. Gupta & Singh, 2021). Automation facilitated by I4.0 is believed to enhance business operational efficiency (Ejsmont et al., 2020; Pillai et al., 2021). Hardware components and software capabilities amalgamated for data and algorithmic dispensation are increasingly favoured in I4.0 (Rajput & Singh, 2019; Di Nardo et al., 2020; Mourtzis et al., 2020; Y. Zhao et al., 2021).

8. Digital Servitisation

As previously discussed, I4.0 is categorised into two groups based on their purposes: front-end and base technologies. Front-end technologies aim to transform advanced manufacturing, intelligent products, efficient supply chains, and streamlined operations to enhance material and labour productivity (de Moura Leite et al., 2020). Operational and market needs drive these activities. On the other hand, base technologies connect or link front-end knowledges through intelligence, providing an additional edge that distinguishes the I4.0 notion from earlier industrial revolutions (Dalenogare et al., 2018). This advancement requires using advanced predictive devices to process information into meaningful data systematically, elucidating uncertainties and establishing well-informed decisions (Majeed et al., 2021). I4.0 can be primarily characterised as IT-enabled advancements in existing economic, operational processes and systems, with wide-ranging organisational ramifications alongside technological impacts (Romero et al., 2021; Tavera Romero et al., 2021). For example, IoT facilitates the collection of data, often referred to as "Big Data" (Osterrieder et al., 2020). Data scientists analyse big data across four extents: volume, variety, velocity, and veracity, employing specialised analytics to utilise data mining techniques for pattern recognition and predictive modelling (Amani & Fadlalla, 2017). Data extraction and suitable analytics empower strategic executives to formulate sustainability-focused choices (Sivarajah et al., 2017). Despite its significant impact, researchers have minimally addressed the impact of I4.0 on supply chain operational frameworks. Zheng et al. (2022) emphasized how I4.0 technology changes the value proposition in BMs by empowering solutions that improve consumer operational procedures. Internal infrastructure within the supply chain and customer affiliation needs to be adapted accordingly. Rymaszewska et al. (2017) I4.0 is instrumental in establishing an interconnected, agile, and flexible collaborative platform. It suggests a service-centric BM encompassing manufacturing and production offerings, integrated analytics services, comprehensive management support, information classifications, and thriftily viable mass personalisation facilitated by end-user amalgamation for developing circular products via Product-Service Systems (PSS) (Atif, 2023b; Pinheiro et al., 2019).

Appendix 4: Prior Studies on CE, Servitisation and I4.0 Disclosure

Reference	Details
Singh et al. (2021)	Singh et al. (2021) steered a content analysis of 29 manufacturing SMEs listed on India's Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) to develop an SME sustainability disclosure index. The study aimed to improve the index by involving stakeholders in materiality analysis and including service-based SMEs in future research for comparison. Additionally, the study suggested conducting a comparative study between large sector enterprises (LSE) and MSMEs to understand the position of social responsibility practices in each sector. The authors recommended that large firms engage their supply chain partners, particularly SMEs, to promote green practices and social aspects for a sustainable supply chain. These actions would have direct and indirect economic impacts on large firms, SMEs, and society through the socio-economic development of the local community. The study also suggested promoting strategic tie-ups with investors, lending agencies, and higher education institutions to leverage SMEs' social and environmental responsibility.
Gunarathne et al. (2021)	According to Gunarathne et al. (2021), the study aims to investigate the "practice-reporting portrayal gap" of Sri Lankan companies in practicing the principles of the CE through their sustainability and integrated reporting. The findings suggest that Sri Lankan companies strongly invest in environmental management principles to enhance their sustainability performance. However, there is a lack of direct embodiment of CE principles. The researchers recommend researching CE-related disclosures in different countries, industries, or regions to bridge this gap and promote circularity. They also suggest strong macro-level support and guidance could motivate companies towards circularity.
Barreiro-Gen and Lozano, (2020)	According to Barreiro-Gen and Lozano (2020), there is a need for further research to focus on the micro-level to understand how organisations are implementing the CE. Their survey of 256 global organisations showed that most organisations focus on reducing and recycling rather than repairing and remanufacturing. They also found that some organisations engage with the 4Rs (reduce, reuse, recycle, and recover) without necessarily framing it under the CE umbrella. In contrast, others who claim to apply CE have low levels of engagement with the 4Rs. The researchers suggest that CE should be applied beyond firm's more holistically through better alliance among stakeholders on CE activities.
Roberts et al. (2022)	The study by Roberts et al. (2022) conducted a content analysis of 28 global firms from three sectors (aerospace & defense, motor vehicle and parts, and transportation) over four years (2012, 2014, 2016, and 2018) to investigate biodiversity and CE disclosure practices. The results showed that, overall, the level of disclosure was low, with many companies providing minimal and vague information. Some companies scored zero in all disclosure constructs, indicating a lack of knowledge of the concepts of biodiversity and CE. However, there was an increase in the level of disclosures on both biodiversity and CE between 2012, 2014, and 2016, followed by a small decrease in 2018. The transportation industry was the lowest in disclosing biodiversity and CE. The motor industry provided more disclosure on biodiversity and CE than the aerospace & defense sector. The study suggested that more attention is required to increase awareness about biodiversity and CE and how these concepts can add value to companies. Additionally, future research should investigate biodiversity and CE in more sectors and explore how accounting can affect the CE transition and how accounting barriers for the CE can be mitigated.

Reference	Details
Opferkuch et al. (2022)	According to Opferkuch et al. (2022), their content analysis of European companies in sustainability rankings revealed that almost all the companies reference CE explicitly in their sustainability reports. However, only 7% of these companies integrate CE within all five sustainability reporting elements. Furthermore, less than one-third of the companies included both targets and indicators for CE, indicating that CE content within sustainability reports is largely superficial and unpredictable.
Dagilene et al. (2020)	Dagilene et al. (2020) found that organisations in the EU manufacturing segment need to report significant information about the CE. They observed that the most reported closed loop was R1 (i.e., reduce), indicating that companies mainly focus on reducing materials. Furthermore, the researchers found that disclosures of reuse, recycle, and recover information in the reports of manufacturing companies needed to be more comprehensive from the perspective of the CE. The resource efficiency approach, which involves minimizing raw materials and creating shorter and closed loops, must be more clearly disclosed in environmental reporting.
D'Amato et al. (2019)	Based on the study by D'Amato et al. (2019), CE was found to be a common theme across all companies and sectors, indicating its omnipresence and homogeneity. Green Economy (GE) was the second most frequent concept, more prevalent in the forest and mining sectors. Bioeconomy (BE) was under-represented in all reports except for the forest sector. The study also found limited interlinkages between these sustainability concepts. However, the strongest connection was found between CE and BE, particularly regarding the efficiency and recycling of bio-based resources.
Scarpellini et al. (2020)	The study by Scarpellini et al. (2020) aimed to investigate the relationship between dynamic capabilities, environmental accounting practices, corporate social responsibility (CSR), and accountability in businesses operating in Spain. The researchers employed Partial Least Squares Path Modeling (PLS-PM) to analyze data collected from 87 questionnaires. The study found a positive correlation between firms' CS (Corporate Sustainability), their environmental accounting practices, and their level of CSR and accountability. The results also revealed that stakeholders' pressure, which acts as a mediator, had a significant effect on the CS of firms. This finding contributes to the existing literature on the topic of stakeholder pressure and its impact on corporate behavior at the micro-level. Overall, this study highlights the importance of environmental accounting practices and CSR for businesses that aim to improve their CS. The findings suggest that businesses must be responsive to stakeholder pressures to improve their environmental performance and CSR practices.
Yang et al. (2019)	Yang et al. (2019) explored the complementarity of CE practices in Chinese manufacturers from 293 firms in China. This study highlights the importance of examining the complementarity of CE practices to achieve more effective and comprehensive CE implementation. The study found a complementary relationship between the two main CE practices, eco-design (ECO) and reverse activities (RA), in Chinese manufacturing firms. Specifically, the results indicated that firms that adopt eco-design practices are more likely to engage in reverse activities and vice versa. However, further research is needed to extend the analysis to other CE practices and supply chains to understand CE practices and their interactions better.
Doni et al. (2019)	The study by Doni et al. (2019) examined the affiliation among servitisation and sustainability actions among European manufacturing companies through content analysis of 208 EU-listed companies. The study aimed to explore how servitisation can support tackling environmental issues and drive improvements in environmental performance, as well as to determine if the level of servitisation can change the BM. The results indicate that servitisation can enhance environmental performance by

Reference	Details
	improving energy consumption. However, the study found no evidence that servitisation affects corporate sustainability disclosure or other environmental policies such as emissions-reduction policies, environmental assurance, and environmental SCM.
Sihvonen and Partanen's (2017)	Sihvonen and Partanen's (2017) study aimed to explore the eco-design practices of companies within the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) sector with an emphasis on quantitative ecological goals. The researchers used content analysis to analyze data from 43 companies across the globe. The study found that companies that publish quantitative environmental targets for their products are more likely to adopt lifecycle thinking, which considers the durability of products and their potential for remanufacture. Furthermore, the study revealed that these quantitative targets are positively associated with environmental performance measures, such as the capability to report quantitatively on flows of reclaimed products and positions in external rankings. Companies that adopt lifecycle thinking and prioritize product durability and remanufacturing are likelier to achieve their quantitative targets and improve their environmental performance measures. Additionally, companies that report quantitatively on flows of reclaimed products and achieve high rankings in external assessments can signal their commitment to sustainability to stakeholders and customers.

Appendix 5: Constructs of the CE Disclosure Index

The CE-disclosure index was developed after a thorough literature review and identification of research gaps. The following is an explanation of how to measure each construct of the CE, servitisation, and I4.0 constructs. It provides a rigorous and standardised framework for assessing companies' CE-related disclosure practices.

Construct	Measure
CER1= Refuse	The first construct of CE is “CER1= Refuse”, according to Opferkuch et al. (2022), refuse is a vital principle of CE, which involves rendering a product obsolete by discontinuing its function or providing a radically different product that serves the same function. This principle aims to prevent the creation of waste and promote resource efficiency. Thus, the researcher is interested in exploring whether companies are taking proactive steps to remove unsustainable products from their production cycles, which can help promote circularity and reduce waste. This approach may provide a more nuanced understanding of how companies implement CE practices and help identify specific areas where improvements can be made. However, it is important to ensure that the grading criteria are clearly defined and consistently applied across all reports to guarantee that the research outcomes are accurate and non-biased.
CER2= Rethink	The second construct was “CER2= Rethink”, Roberts et al. (2022) suggests that CE is causing companies to rethink their business strategies, leading to more stable revenue models, adoption of disruptive technologies, waste reduction, exploration of innovative product and service combinations, and collaboration to access new markets. On the other hand, Gunarathne et al. (2021) suggest that one way to promote sustainability is to design products that encourage more intensive use. This approach is consistent with the growing interest in circular design as a key component of sustainable business practices (Atif, 2023b). Circular design principles aim to reduce waste and promote resource efficiency by designing products that can be easily disassembled, repaired, or reused at the end of their lifecycle. Companies can reduce their negative impact on the environment and create more sustainable BMs by incorporating circularity principles into product design. Simultaneously, Opferkuch et al. (2022) emphasise the need for a comprehensive redesign of products, components, materials, businesses, and supply chains to achieve effective regeneration. Thus, the researcher decided to score this construct by examining whether the company reports about designing a circular product or their plans to make the product more intensive through design.
CER3= Reduce	The third construct is “CER3= Reduce”, Opferkuch et al. (2022) suggests that CE's "Reduce" principle involves increasing product use or manufacturing efficiency by reducing the consumption of natural resources and reducing the overall environmental consumption burden. At the same time, Roberts et al. (2022) indicates that companies can use nature-focused corporate sustainability initiatives such as the United Nation's recommended 17 sustainable development goals (SDG)s and Agenda 2030, as well as the GRI Standards, to reduce the environmental impact by managing waste, improving the circular design, and reducing waste disposal from the production. These initiatives align with SDG12: responsible production and consumption, promoting sustainable use and management of resources to minimise environmental impact and ensure long-term availability. While Gunarathne et al. (2021) suggest that companies often report producer-oriented activities from a dematerialisation

Construct	Measure
	<p>stance under the "Reduce" strategy rather than their consumer-oriented initiatives to promote decreased consumer consumption and usage of products. The researcher is using a comprehensive approach to investigate the adoption of the "Reduce" strategy in CE practices. This involves identifying the percentage of reclaimed products and their packaging materials for each product category among the sample companies. This will provide valuable insights into the extent to which companies are implementing the "Reduce" principle of CE to improve their resource efficiency and their initiatives to reduce their customers' consumption habits.</p>
CER4= Reuse	<p>The fourth construct is "CER4= Reuse", Reusing, upcycling, and reclaiming materials is vital to reducing waste and promoting sustainability. This CE strategy is consistent with the findings of Opferkuch et al. (2022), who suggest a comprehensive redesign of circular products incorporating reusable components and circular supply chains is needed to achieve effective regeneration. Reusing involves salvaging a previously discarded product, provided it is still functional and can serve its original purpose. Gunarathe et al. (2021) recommend designing circular components of products to enable their reuse and simplify returning them to specific material or nutrient cycles (Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020; GRI, 2021; Roberts et al., 2022). Thus, the researcher set a few keywords such as "reclaim materials," "second-hand goods," "reuse," and "upcycle" to determine the overall amount of waste produced, it is important to categorize it according to the different types of waste streams. This involves identifying which types of waste can be recovered and reused and which types of waste must be disposed of, such as tailings in the mining sector, electronic waste in the electronics sector, or food waste in the agriculture or hospitality sector. By examining this CE strategy, the researcher is trying to gain insights into the company's efforts towards reducing waste and promoting sustainability involves encouraging the reuse of discarded products that are still functional among consumers.</p>
CER5= Repair	<p>The fifth construct is "CER5= Repair", as highlighted by Opferkuch et al. (2022), the effectiveness of CE strategies may vary depending on the specific context and implementation. Therefore, it's important to carefully evaluate the outcomes of any CE initiatives to determine their effectiveness and adjust strategies accordingly. Likewise, Barreiro-Gen & Lozano (2020) affirmed and suggested providing consumers with a repairing and maintenance approach. The organisations can focus on reducing, repairing, refurbishing, and recycling their resources internally and externally. Therefore, the researcher will assess the company's sustainability reports to identify the extent that repairing and regular maintenance of a product can help extend its lifespan and reduce the need for costly replacements. This is in line with the CE principles because by repairing and maintaining products, companies can reduce waste and save money by avoiding the need for expensive replacements.</p>
CER6= Refurbish	<p>The sixth construct is "CER6= Refurbish", as Barreiro-Gen & Lozano (2020) pointed out, refurbishing may entail reintroducing an outdated product and bringing it into the modern era. However, as indicated by Opferkuch et al. (2022), it can also entail looking at how businesses are closing the CE loop through refurbishing, which refers to remodelling the used resources and materials in a closed system to reduce waste. Scalable refurbishing and restorative initiatives can help organisations to increase efficiency and reduce waste by extending the lifespan of products and reducing the need for</p>

Construct	Measure
	replacements. Updating their products and machinery may boost productivity while minimising their environmental impact. Thus, the researcher is evaluating how the Company reports on scalable refurbishment projects that aim to improve productivity through upgrades while lowering waste because the focus on scalable refurbishing and restorative initiatives aligns with the principles of CE and can help organisations to achieve their sustainability goals while improving their bottom line.
CER7= Remanufacture	The seventh construct is “CER7= Remanufacture”, Barreiro-Gen & Lozano (2020) indicated a need for more consensus on implementing a single CE principle within organisations. Opferkuch et al. (2022) affirmed that different factors, such as the nature of their products and services, can impact the approach. However, various strategies can be employed to move towards a more circular model, such as using parts from discarded products in new products, remanufacturing, and reducing waste. According to Roberts et al. (2022), one potential issue is that it is not always clear from the design of targets and indicators whether returned products and materials are being remanufactured or sent to landfill, which can have very different sustainability impacts. Additionally, (Gunarathne et al. (2021) suggested that companies need to be transparent about their end-of-life strategies. Therefore, the researcher explores remanufacturing activities among the sample, such as using parts from discarded products in new products. It can help reduce waste, save resources, and benefit companies in the long run by helping them gain strategic legitimacy.
CER8= Repurpose	The eighth construct is “CER8= Repurpose”, According to Opferkuch et al. (2022), repurposing refers to taking an construct or material originally intended for one purpose and using it for another. Repurposing involves using discarded products or their parts to create new products with different functions. This falls under repurposing, not remanufacturing, for a sustainable and CE.
CER9= Recycle	The ninth construct is “CER9= Recycle”, according to Opferkuch et al. (2022) recycling refers to the material’s process that can produce the same quality as the original (high grade) or lower (low grade). Where manufacturers aim to replace non-renewable resources with material made from recycled or renewable materials. Barreiro-Gen & Lozano (2020) suggest that organisations prioritise reducing and recycling over repairing and remanufacturing, focusing on internal efforts. Simultaneously, Roberts et al. (2022) defined <i>recycling</i> as the most common CE process where used materials are treated to make them suitable for reuse (GRI, 2021). On the other hand, Gunarathne et al. (2021) emphasised that the true recycling involves optimising products rather than just recycling sub-optimally designed products to minimize waste. Therefore, the researcher plans to investigate sample companies to identify if they report their total waste provide the weight of hazardous and non-hazardous waste diverted from or to disposal in metric tons and include a waste composition breakdown to estimate recycling activities.
CER10= Recover	The tenth construct was “CER10= Recover”, Opferkuch et al. (2022) have pointed out that the volume of waste incinerated for energy recovery, as indicated by metrics such as the percentage of waste materials recovered, may not necessarily reflect a company's preference for higher-ranked CE strategies such as reuse. Additionally, comparing changes in these metrics over time may not accurately capture a company's progress towards circularity or the sustainability impacts of each CE strategy. For instance, a higher level of

Construct	Measure
	circularity should result in fewer natural resources being consumed. Therefore, the researcher intends to investigate companies that report on recycling used products, which processing resources to acquire equivalent (premium-grade) or inferior (substandard-grade) calibre to assess their CE efforts.
SER11= Servitisation as a CE strategy	The first construct was “SER11= Servitisation as a CE strategy”, Li et al. (2015) argue that by adopting servitisation, firms can diversify their revenue streams and reduce their dependence on the sale of tangible products alone. Additionally, Doni et al. (2019) examined how firms communicate their ESG information about adopting servitisation, which involves taking back used constructs from customers for recycling or reuse in the production cycle and suggested future researchers replicate the analysis with an in-depth assessment of the companies’ service infusion. Thus, the researcher is assessing if sample companies report on adding service provision into their Product consortium, which aims to Bring back used constructs from the customers back to the production cycle.
SER12= Waste Recovery for servitisation	The second construct is “SER12= Waste Recovery for servitisation”, Scarpellini et al. (2020) point out that waste recovery can play a crucial role in managing CEBM and enhancing the quality of their environmental disclosure. To examine this, the researchers evaluated companies based on their reporting of whether mixed recycling is manually or mechanically sorted and separated into different material types before being sent to manufacturers for conversion into new products. This highlights how the servitisation approach can promote better waste recovery and contribute to a more sustainable CEBM.
SER13= Minimising usage of virgin Material	The third construct is “SER13= Minimising usage of virgin Material”, One key aspect of infusing servitisation approach with CE is the dematerialisation of resources and recycled materials. Moreover, Scarpellini et al. (2020) suggest that CE emphasises the importance of reducing companies' dependence on virgin raw materials and transitioning towards more sustainable production processes prioritising renewable resources. Thus, assessing companies' reporting about their use of recycled materials and their efforts towards dematerialisation seemed a suitable construct for CE disclosure. This construct will provide insights into their adoption of circular business practices.
SER14= End-of Life practices/Reverse Logistics	The fourth construct is “SER14= End-of Life practices/Reverse Logistics”, little research has examined end-of-life practices and reverse logistics through a servitisation approach through CE-related disclosure to date. Mirzaei & Shokouhyar (2022) suggest incorporating CEBM to maximise resource value through a regeneration model at the end of each product's service life. Therefore, the researcher assesses companies reporting “tightening the circle” by moving from recycling to reuse through Loop, which aims to develop a global reuse platform that allows customers to return the used construct easily.
Transparency and Accountability	The first construct is “IND15= Transparency and Accountability”, a recent study by Cenamor et al. (2017) strongly advocates using a platform approach to achieve servitisation through digitalisation. While the current study was primarily focused on B2B manufacturing firms, it suggested future researchers explore IT-enabled interactions using a platform approach in B2C contexts, which are significantly different. Therefore, in the current study, the researcher evaluated companies that successfully implemented a low-cost data-driven management system, enabling them to provide eco-friendly products with high sustainability. This system allows for rapid reconfiguration and remanufacturing using reusable and recyclable materials and components.

Construct	Measure
	Because I4.0-enabled platforms can enhance transparency and accountability by providing greater visibility, traceability, collaboration, and predictive insights into the supply chain and production processes. This can help businesses enhance their ESG performance while boosting their marketplace competitiveness.
IND16= I4.0-enabled shared platform	The second construct is “IND16= I4.0-enabled shared platform “, the I4.0-enabled shared platform, as explained by Cenamor et al. (2017), suggests that a platform approach may prompt firms to address servitisation by defining new roles. Atif (2023) proposes that leveraging the CE paradigm depends on two propositions. The first proposition involves co-creation and increased perceived value through servitisation. In contrast, the second proposition relates to using data-driven platforms that employ I4.0 technologies for shaping strategy and providing decision support. Therefore, this study will explore how companies successfully utilized a data-sharing, I4.0-enabled platform to address ESG challenges.
IND17= Resource Efficiency	The third construct is “IND17= Resource Efficiency”, Scarpellini et al. (2020) outline CE's primary objectives as reducing material flow, achieving resource/energy efficiency, and renewing natural and social capital over multiple phases. In the current study, the researcher assessed whether companies reported on their efforts towards resource efficiency by analysing innovation or experimenting with product design or services to develop a resource-efficient product.
IND18= Extended Lifecycle	While the fourth construct is “IND18= Extended Lifecycle “, Scarpellini et al. (2020) highlight the importance of eco-innovation as a key feature in the transition towards a CE. Therefore, the researcher analysed whether companies reported on modifying their products' design or services, such as implementing product design strategies and providing repair services that prioritize sharing or renting to extend product life to reduce waste because <u>eco-innovation was more likely to report on these types of modifications.</u>
IND19= Functional Efficacy	The fifth construct is “IND19= Functional Efficacy “, according to Scarpellini et al. (2020), the CE framework encourages businesses to prioritise the sharing or renting of products, which can increase the functional efficiency of products. Thereby reducing the need for producing new products and reducing waste generation where functional efficiency is essential for achieving sustainability in a CE. Thus, the researcher assessed if companies report their goal regarding creating products designed to last longer, perform better, and easily repair, reuse, or recycle, thereby reducing their environmental impact and maximizing their economic value.
IND20= Innovation through I4.0	The sixth construct is “IND20= Innovation through I4.0”, in the current study, the researcher followed Scarpellini et al. (2020) to evaluate firms actively engaged in eco-innovation and CE practices, providing insights into the current state of eco-innovation and CE adoption among the sample. The researcher will evaluate companies' reports to assess the environmental compliance of products or services through innovative feature replacement, which aims to <u>become more environmentally conscious that comply with regulations.</u>
IND21= Monitoring Resource Use	Finally, the seventh construct is “IND21= Monitoring Resource Use “, as highlighted by D’Amato et al. (2019), it is important to monitor inputs and outputs and promote natural resource efficiency through recycling and using residues and side streams. Thus, the researcher will assess If companies are reporting about the transition to smart services and upgrade contracts using

Construct	Measure
	I4.0 technologies to evaluate if companies are focusing on achieving their resource efficiency and eco-efficiency targets.

Appendix 6: Pilot Study

There are still some limitations associated with manual content analysis, such as the chance that only selected keywords are applied, so there is a high chance of misleading as the context of the sentence may need to be clarified. The manual content analysis technique consisted of keyword searching, a method employed in studies to highlight areas in the report. To ensure all information was captured, direct keywords such as “circular economy”, “servitisation”, “servitisation”, “industry 4.0”, “disclosure” were searched. Later explicit keywords, implicit keywords and other keywords¹⁵ were searched. Then, the downloaded sustainability reports were searched for CE, servitisation and I4.0-related disclosures, where, if present, the content was analysed to ensure no omission of disclosures. The final sample consisted of companies from the Global Fortune 500 list. The sample represents manufacturing companies from a variety of industries.

Krippendorff (1980) observed that it is important to note that Cronbach's alpha, a statistical measure used to assess the reliability is based on certain assumptions are rarely met in empirical research. These assumptions include one-dimensionality and tau-equivalence of data. However, in the current study, both assumptions were met, with the one-dimensionality of CE, servitisation, and I4.0 being present in their overarching themes of resource sustainability and efficiency, service-oriented business models, and digital transformation in industry. The tau-equivalence assumption was also met as the same scoreboard was used for measuring all variables, including the dependent, independent, and control variables and following previous CE, servitisation and I4.0 focused disclosure related studies (Barreiro-Gen & Lozano, 2020; Bogdan et al., 2022; Cenamor et al., 2017; D’Amato et al., 2019; Doni et al., 2019; Gunarathne et al., 2021; A. Hassan et al., 2022; Mirzaei & Shokouhyar, 2022; Opferkuch et al., 2022; Scarpellini, 2022; Yang et al., 2019), a self-developed disclosure index was conducted. An internal consistency level is acceptable if Cronbach's coefficient is above 0.6 (Bag & Rahman, 2023). As a result, the researcher used the SPSS (IBM SPSS Statistics 29.0) software to conduct Cronbach Alpha analysis and the results show a high level of internal consistency among the 26 constructs that were analyzed. The Cronbach's alpha score of 0.879 indicates a very good internal consistency level within all variables. They demonstrate high internal consistency, meaning they can measure related constructs reliably. Furthermore, the correlation approach-validity test was used and the absence of multicollinearity in the current study has been observed, reinforcing the accuracy, validity, and reliability of variables.

Later to ensure consistency, a pilot study was conducted on a manufacturing company over five years (2018-2022), with the primary researcher performing manual content analysis and taking notes on how to score selective codes. Other researchers (a PhD student from the same department of school-who is not involved in writing the paper and a supervisor) then participated in data collection, and discrepancies were resolved through discussions. Later, the self-developed CE-disclosure index and preliminary results were presented at various conferences and refined based on feedback from reviewers, academic attendees, and practitioners. The researchers collected valuable feedback and gained insights beyond their theoretical knowledge. Additionally, they regularly shared their findings and sought input from one another to ensure that the research remained relevant and addressed the evolving needs and challenges related to CE in businesses worldwide.

¹⁵ List of keywords has been included in the CE Disclosure Index presented in Chapter 2: Literature review

Appendix 7: List of Companies (Sample)

No.	Company Name	No.	Company Name
1	AEON	50	Indian Oil
2	Airbus	51	Intel
3	Alphabet	52	JBS
4	Amazon	53	Johnson & Johnson
5	Amerisource Bergen	54	Kroger
6	Anheuser-Busch InBev	55	LG Electronics
7	Apple	56	Lockheed Martin
8	ArcelorMittal	57	Louis Dreyfus
9	Archer Daniels Midland	58	Lukoil
10	Aviation Industry Corp. of China	59	Maersk Group
11	BASF	60	Marubeni
12	BHP Group	61	McKesson
13	BMW Group	62	Mercedes-Benz Group
14	Boeing	63	Microsoft
15	Bosch	64	Nestlé
16	BP	65	Nissan Motor
17	Cardinal Health	67	Pemex
18	Carrefour	66	PepsiCo
19	Chevron	68	Petrobras
20	China Mobile Communications	69	Petronas
21	China National Petroleum	70	Pfizer
22	China Railway Engineering Group	71	Phillips 66
23	China Southern Power Grid	72	Procter & Gamble
24	China State Construction Engineering	73	PTT (Global Chemical Public Company)
25	Christian Dior	74	Raytheon Technologies
26	Cisco Systems	75	Reliance Industries
27	Costco Wholesale	76	Roche Group
99	CVS Health	77	Rosneft Oil
28	Dongfeng Motor	78	SAIC Motor
29	Dow Chemicals	79	Samsung Electronics
30	E. ON	80	Saudi Aramco
31	Edeka Zentrale	81	Seven & I Holdings
32	Electricité de France	82	Siemens
33	Enel	83	Sinopec Group
34	Engie	84	Sony
35	Equinor	85	State Grid Corporation of China
36	Exxon Mobil	86	Stellantis
37	Ford Motor	87	Telefónica
38	Fortum	88	Tesco
39	Gazprom	89	Tokyo Electric Power
40	General Motors	90	Total Energies
41	Glencore	91	Toyota Motor

No.	Company Name	No.	Company Name
42	GSK	92	Trafigura Group
43	Hitachi	93	Unilever
44	Home Depot	94	Valero Energy
45	Hon Hai Precision Industry	95	Verizon Communications
46	Honda Motor	96	Vodafone Group
47	HP	97	Volkswagen
48	Hyundai Motor	98	Walgreens Boots Alliance
49	IBM	100	Walmart